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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Meaning
AC	Associated Countries
CA	Consortium Agreement
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CoP	Community of Practice
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPN	Data Protection Notice
EGET	European Gender Equality Taskforce
ERA	European Research Area
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GE	Gender Equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
IPV	Intimate Partner Violence
MS	EU Member States
NIP	National Impact Plan
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
R&I	Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Background

This benchmark report presents a state-of-the-art analysis of the current policy development on Gender-Based Violence (GBV) in the European Research Area (ERA). It is developed within the ongoing GENDERACTIONplus project, which contributes to the coordination of the gender equality and inclusiveness objectives of the new European Research Area (ERA).

The main objectives of the report are to:

- set a baseline understanding of current state of research on GBV in Higher Education (HE)
- give an overview of relevant policy developments on GBV in ERA, mainly targeting national authorities and research funding organisations (RFO)
- give an overview of the overall policy framework on GBV concerning ERA stakeholders
- generate recommendations for policy development targeting the European Commission (EC), EU member states (MS) and Associated Countries (AC), national authorities, RFOs, and future research

The analysis in the report builds on an extensive and systematic research review, collecting all peer-reviewed research journal articles globally on GBV in HE since 2017 (> 2 000 publications). Further, benchmark survey data on policy development on GBV in ERA is analysed, collected from responses by the GENDERACTIONplus partners (comprised of 16 countries/regions and 20 RFOs). Finally, a thorough collection and analysis of the current overall policy framework on GBV in ERA establishes important knowledge on relevant gaps and promising strategies for future policy development. The results in summary from these empirical parts of the report are as follows:

Research review on GBV in HE

- The research described in the global section, heavily dominated by the USA, and the research described in the ERA, differ in terms of content and thematic focus. For instance, bystander initiatives are frequently examined in the included research reviews, but only represented in one of the included ERA articles. Another thematic difference is the focus on prevention and prevalence in the reviews, while the ERA articles to a higher degree focus on relationship violence between students.
- Another gap identified, specifically in the ERA material, is that between the strong focus on students' experiences of GBV and its weak relation to development of HE infrastructure for prevention of GBV. Many of the articles focus on students in different ways, such as examining students' relations, experiences, behaviours, and predictors in relation to GBV. The generated knowledge in these studies is only, to a small extent, included in research on policy development. This results in a gap between students' lived experiences of GBV and the development of HE institutions' preventive work.

- There is a clear gap in the overall material with regards to samples. An absolute majority of the included research focuses on students as a sample, and very few studies focus on staff in HE specifically, and not one identified article or review focused on doctoral students.
- Samples predominantly consist of majority group students. The lack of diversity and intersectional perspectives is a clear gap in the overall material, with the obvious exception of the specific search on intersectionality.
- The search on intersectionality can be categorised into two parts: Around half of the articles discuss individual experiences and prevalence of GBV in HE from an intersectional perspective as a way of building more inclusive knowledge. The other half focus on intersectionality as a tool for change. The institutional and structural levels of HE is analysed through an intersectional lens in different ways.
- Research Funding Organisations are a central part of the HE infrastructure, yet there is a complete lack of research on RFOs regarding GBV in HE.
- Findings regarding conceptual framework and methodology in this material confirm previous research results. Use of a wide range of scales, surveys and methodologies results in a variety of measures and numbers to describe GBV in HE. This in combination with the broad conceptual framework and varied definitions of GBV makes comparisons between studies and contexts challenging.

Policy analysis – national and regional level

- None out of the 15 countries or regions participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey has a national or regional policy against GBV in RFOs in place.
- None out of the 15 countries or regions participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey has a policy against GBV in RPOs in place, which include measures for RFOs.
- Only two out of 15 responding partners in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have a national or regional policy against GBV in place for RPOs.
- Concepts used in policies are left undefined and mainly cover either some forms of GBV or only SH and discrimination.
- An intersectional approach is missing throughout the analysed policy documents, with the single exception of Ireland where, especially the national framework policy, takes important steps towards making visible and using an intersectional lens in its aims and strategies.

Policy analysis – research funding organisations

- Five out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have developed policies on GBV since 1 May 2021.
- One out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have measures targeting applicants.

- Three out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey prioritise funding research on GBV.
- Two out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have responded there have been recent policy developments targeting the safety of researchers.
- Two out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have responded there are procedures for information on GBV misconduct by PIs or researchers and procedures for sanctions.

Policy analysis – overall ERA framework on GBV

- The ERA policy framework on GBV builds to a large extent on the principles and suggested strategies and measures developed in the Istanbul Convention.¹
- The ERA policy framework lacks a consistent overall structure. Instead, it is composed of divergent policies targeting different stakeholders with measures and strategies not always clearly aligned.
- The Ljubljana declaration on GE² has been widely endorsed by MS, whereas the Call for action on GBV³ is as yet foremost adopted by specific ERA stakeholders.
- The urgent need for a data and monitoring framework on GBV at the ERA level is detected in the analysis, and suggestions for how to move forward on this important part of the ERA framework are required.
- Intersectionality is a cross-cutting priority in recent EU policy development on GBV in the ERA, but there are still several aspects to develop further. Especially, an intersectional understanding of multiple oppressive forms of discrimination is still missing. Policy development moving beyond a simplistic version of discrimination and an additive model is suggested.

Recommendations

The final part of the report develops a new agenda for policy development on GBV. Based on the previous analysis of research and policy, an infrastructure for systematic change is suggested, making it possible for ERA stakeholders to take on the collaborative responsibility for ending GBV in ERA. This is a new level of ambition for all ERA stakeholders, building on previous policy developments and past and current experiences from EU projects on GBV. The infrastructure will, in its full function, ensure the development and organisation of sustained structures for monitoring and evaluation, funding schemes on research, relevant support, and effective measures for accountability.

¹ Council of Europe 2014.

² Ljubljana Declaration 2021.

³ Call for action 2022.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. About the project

Building on the Horizon 2020 project GENDERACTION, the overall goal of GENDERACTIONplus is to contribute to the coordination of the gender equality and inclusiveness objectives of the new European Research Area (ERA) through the development of two communities of practice (CoPs), one consisting of representatives of national authorities and the second consisting of representatives of Research Funding Organisations. The network is made up of a total of 22 EU Member States (MS) and 3 Associated Countries (AC), as well as 26 project partners and 14 Associated partners.

Adding the plus sign to the title of the previous GENDERACTION project not only indicates that it is a follow-up project but also makes it explicit that this project also addresses diversity and intersectionality (the gender+ approach).

Specifically, the GENDERACTIONplus project aims to:

- Develop strategic policy advice on existing and emerging policy solutions;
- Enhance the policy-making process by engaging with stakeholders, civil society organisations, and citizens;
- Build capacities, competence, and expertise for gender equality and mainstreaming in Research & Innovation among the policy and RFO community members, with special attention to countries with less comprehensive policies;
- Create impact through communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

Thematically, the project focuses on:

- Intersectionality and inclusiveness
- Gender-based violence (GBV)
- The gender dimension in research and innovation
- Monitoring and evaluating gender equality actions in the European Research Area (ERA)
- Promoting institutional change through Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

GENDERACTIONplus aims to achieve the following impacts:

- Advance policy coordination among MS and AC countries through stakeholder and citizen engagement.
- Improve research careers and working conditions in European R&I, by developing policy dialogue and solutions on inclusion and intersectionality, combatting gender-based violence, and promoting institutional changes through GEPs.
- Improve research quality and the social responsibility of knowledge by integrating the gender dimension into research and innovation (R&I).
- Reduce geographic inequality by targeting less experienced/engaged countries and regions.

1.2. Objectives of the report

This benchmark report aims at collecting and analysing recent research and policy developments on combatting GBV in MS, AC and RFOs in ERA. Its main objectives are to:

- set a baseline understanding of current state of research on GBV in HEI
- give an overview of relevant policy developments on GBV in ERA, mainly targeting national authorities and RFOs
- give an overview of the overall policy framework on GBV concerning ERA stakeholders
- generate recommendations for policy development targeting the EC, MS, national authorities, RFOs, and future research

The current state of research on GBV in HE is collected through a systematic search procedure covering relevant peer-reviewed publications, during a period ranging from 2017-2022, including relevant databases. The research review in this part is mainly descriptive and gives an overview and baseline understanding of the current research on GBV in HE. Results are presented in different sections with a specific focus on existing research reviews, ERA countries representation of research output, research on funding infrastructure and praxis, as well as thematic areas covering several of the 7Ps⁴ and intersectionality. This work also adds important perspectives and knowledge to recent research reviews in the area of GBV in HE.⁵

Recent policy developments on GBV in the ERA are presented, building on the GENDERACTIONplus benchmark survey completed in the fall of 2022 by national authorities and RFOs represented in the project. In the survey, the focus is on national policies on GBV targeting RFOs and RPOs, as well as specific policies and targeted measures adopted by RFOs. Compared to the UniSAFE national mapping report,⁶ the GENDERACTIONplus benchmark survey does not cover the same extent of MS, AS and RFOs. As only about half of existing MS are included in the GENDERACTIONplus benchmark survey (and some AS), it is not possible to present a state-of-the-art analysis of the situation throughout the ERA. Despite this, the representation of EU14 and EU13 countries, as well as the differentiated representation of RFOs among respondents, gives an overall indication of the extent to which significant progress has been achieved or not in terms of policy developments on GBV in the ERA. Thus, the benchmark survey results aim primarily at identifying overall tendencies in progress on policy development on combatting GBV in the ERA, including best practices and challenges.

Further, the objective of giving an overview of the overall policy framework for ERA stakeholders builds on a collection and summary of existing relevant policies. This work also consists of an analysis of two specific themes relevant in this context: data and monitoring of GBV in the ERA and the use of an intersectional perspective in policy development. The issue of data and monitoring is discussed from the viewpoint of enhancing a common ERA framework, partly building on the work done in UniSAFE.⁷ Intersectionality is addressed from the viewpoint of contributing to the cross-cutting theme

⁴ The 7P framework is developed within the ongoing UniSAFE project (<https://unisafe-gbv.eu/>), where the individual Ps cover the measure of the Prevalence of GBV, with the aim to understand the roles of university and research organisations in Prevention, Protection, Prosecution, Provision of services, supported by Partnerships and Policies (<https://unisafe-gbv.eu/the-project/unisafe-7p-conceptual-framework/>).

⁵ Bondestam & Lundqvist 2020.

⁶ UniSAFE 2021b, 2021c.

⁷ UniSAFE 2023.

in GENDERACTIONplus, where the aim is to further the policy framework on GE in ERA through an intersectional lens.

Finally, the objective of contributing with recommendations for EU policy development is based on the results and analysis in this report. The recommendations in this part mainly cover suggestions for an ERA infrastructure on combatting GBV, which build on identified gaps and challenges in both research and policy analysis, and specific measures targeting different ERA stakeholders.

1.3. The relationship of this report to other tasks and work packages

This WP3 benchmark report on GBV is one of a set of benchmark reports to be delivered within the GENDERACTIONplus project, and thus contribute to the understanding of the current state of GE in ERA national authorities, RFOs and RPOs. The results of this report will further the understanding and development of a baseline document on preventive measures on GBV (WP3, task 3.2), set a standard for the development of a zero-tolerance policy template (WP3, task 3.3.) and will provide content in upcoming mutual learning, capacity building, and dissemination (WP3, task 3.4).

The current research knowledge on GBV and intersectionality presented in this benchmark report will foster the development of intersectionality as a cross-cutting principle in the project, foremost supporting the work done in WP2. Both the policy and research analysis enhance learning in the two CoPs in GENDERACTIONplus, especially relevant for WP4, task 4.4, but also as capacity building activities in WP7, task 7.3 and 7.4. Knowledge and results from the benchmark report also strengthen forthcoming EGET activities through WP7, task 7.5. Finally, the report is crucial for the work performed in WP8, task 8.4 and 8.5, by setting guiding principles, recommendations and a solid knowledge base for the development of NIPs and an European impact plan.

1.4. Structure of the report

This benchmark report on GBV in the ERA is divided into three main parts.

- In the first part, the methodology used to collect research data and perform the benchmark survey on policy development is presented.
- The second part presents results of a descriptive analysis in three sections: (1) research review of the current state of research on GBV in HE, (2) the existence and content of national and regional policies on GBV for RFOs and RPOs, and (3) the content and relevance of overall policies on GBV for ERA stakeholders. A short description of the content and rationale, and a brief summary of results, introduce each section.
- The third and final part summarizes the result sections overall and suggest recommendations for moving beyond the current policy and research knowledge on GBV in the ERA, aiming at an integrated infrastructure for change involving all ERA stakeholders.

The report concludes with acknowledgements, a list of references, and then several appendices describing the research review methodology used in detail, provides an overview of the analysed research publications, and presents the benchmark survey instruments used.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Research review

2.1.1. Systematic literature search

The aim of this research review is to examine the current state of knowledge on GBV in HE. This task can be addressed in several different ways since ‘the current state of knowledge’ is a question with a rather broad scope. Early in the assignment process, KvinnSam at the University of Gothenburg Library⁸ was contracted for the task of assisting the Swedish Secretariat for Gender Research with scientifically based search processes. A systematic literature search was conducted in the multi-disciplinary databases Scopus and Web of Science, on peer reviewed articles published in English since 2017 on GBV in HE. The timeframe 2017-2022 was set due to several reasons. 1) The assignment stating a focus on ‘current’ research, 2) The broad geographical scope requires a limitation in time to ensure a manageable number of posts in relation to the assignment, 3) A thorough international systematic research review was published in 2020 covering research published up to 2017/2018.⁹ The systematic literature search resulted in 2,264 posts, embedded and accessible to the authors in Rayyan,¹⁰ a research collaboration platform. Exclusion criteria “wrong topic” and “wrong language” applied on titles, abstract and keywords resulted in a main list of 1,866 peer reviewed articles (see Appendix A for details on the entire search process). Only publications published in English are included in the research review. This has a number of implications. Publication patterns and languages are different in different countries, and we do not know how much recent research we did not find in the search due to this language limitation. That criterion also advantages articles from English native-speaking countries.

2.1.2. Separate searches in a main list

Four separate search procedures within the main list were then conducted, as described below.

1. The search on systematic reviews had no geographical limitation, but rather a methodological limitation to include only systematic reviews in order to offer a scoping of the current focus in the international research field.
2. The search on research conducted in and/or about ERA had a geographical limitation, but no methodological one. Since the objective of this search was to offer a mapping of as much research as possible on GBV in HE, inclusion criteria were generous regarding the student sample and closeness to GBV and/or HE. Articles were thus included if they mentioned some form of GBV and had students as a sample.
3. To contribute with knowledge on the cross-cutting dimension of intersectionality in the GENDERACTIONplus project, a search was conducted in the main list on the term ‘intersectionality’.

⁸ KvinnSam – National Resource Library for Gender Studies, is a university-wide research infrastructure at University of Gothenburg, located at the Humanities Library.

⁹ Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020

¹⁰ <https://www.rayyan.ai/>.

4. To contribute to knowledge on the focus on RFOs in the GENDERACTIONplus project, a search was conducted in the main list on the terms 'RFO', 'research funding organizations/organisations' and 'research funding agencies'.

In the following figures, these four search strategies are described in more detail, also indicating the number of publications finally included. Each of the four reviews resulted in a list of articles, presented in appendices 2-5 respectively.

Systematic research reviews

Figure 1. Search procedure, systematic research reviews on GBV in HE.

The research reviews, including reference, DOI number, abstracts, and keywords, are presented in Appendix B.

Articles conducted in or about ERA

Figure 2. Search procedure, research on GBV in ERA.

The articles, including reference, DOI number, abstracts and keywords, are presented in Appendix C.

Articles on intersectionality

Figure 3. Search procedure, research on intersectionality and GBV in HE.

The articles, including reference, DOI number, abstract and keywords, are presented in Appendix D.

Articles on RFOs

Figure 4. Search procedure, research on GBV and RFOs.

The articles, including reference, DOI number, abstract and keywords are presented in Appendix E.

2.2. Benchmark survey

2.2.1. Target groups

The benchmark survey was intended for the beneficiaries and Associated Partners of the GENDERACTIONplus project, both policy-makers and representatives of RFOs). A request was made to submit only one answer per country or region for national authorities and RFOs respectively in GENDERACTIONplus. The benchmarking survey targeted national authorities (ministries, national agencies and organisations that support them) and RFOs. Overall, 113 representatives of national authorities, supporting organisations and RFOs within and outside the consortium were addressed with a request to (help to) provide answers to the questionnaires.

2.2.2. Data collection

The benchmarking survey was disseminated on 10.10.2022 with an initial deadline on 6.11.2022. In the case of some respondents, there was an agreement to postpone the deadline (often because of the need to coordinate the collection of information for the questionnaire across the organisation and/or because of the heavy workload in the autumn and as the end of the year approaches). The last inputs were received on 18.11.2022.

2.2.3. Mapping instruments

The benchmark survey questionnaire was developed through a co-creative process among partners involved in the GENDERACTIONplus project. Several versions were revised by partners during summer and early fall of 2022. Data were gathered through the LimeSurvey platform. To facilitate the work of coordinating inputs, a Word version of the questionnaires was sent to respondents along with

a link to the questionnaire in the outreach email. Most of the inputs were entered via online questionnaire, in two cases (SK, BE) the answers were sent in a Microsoft Word document.

2.2.4. Data clearing

All data with survey answers was downloaded from LimeSurvey as an excel file. Respondents were asked to upload or otherwise share relevant policy documents or links to them. There were overall 50 attached documents in the survey in the case of national policies benchmarking survey and 14 among responses from RFOs.

In the excel file collecting all answers, partial adjustments were made to the a few initial questions in respondents' inputs, e.g., changing or adding of country name to country code (Poland => PL, Spain=>ES), in one case the name of organisation was omitted by the respondent and was therefore added in the data cleaning phase. The two answers to the survey submitted in a Word file were manually added to the excel files.

In the next step, the answers that were complete were filtered. Duplicate inputs were deleted. As a result, there were 20 answers from RFOs (out of 29 addressed) and 15 questionnaires describing national and regional policies (out of 23 countries, whose representatives of national authorities or supporting organisations were asked for inputs).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Research review

3.1.1. An overview of the findings

This part of the benchmark report covers current research on GBV in HE. It includes identified systematic reviews at a global level (N=30), articles published in or about ERA (N=71), articles on intersectionality at a global level (N=33) and articles on Research Funding Organisations at a global level (N=1). Only peer reviewed articles published in English between 2017 and 2022 are included. The dominance of USA based research in the field is major. For example, not one identified systematic review was conducted in or about ERA countries, or the European context. The included material from ERA is limited as a whole, but also shows the difference between countries. A majority of the countries has 0-3 published articles within the scope of this overview, while a minority of the countries have a larger number of published articles. Spain stands out with 24 peer review articles published in English during the time frame of this overview. Below follows an overview of the main findings and identified gaps:

- The research described in the global section, heavily dominated by the USA, and the research described in the ERA, differ in terms of content and thematic focus. For instance, bystander initiatives are frequently examined in the included research reviews, but only represented in one of the included ERA articles. Another thematic difference is the focus on prevention and prevalence in the reviews, while the ERA articles to a higher degree focus on relationship violence between students.
- Another gap identified specifically in the ERA material is that between the strong focus on students' experiences of GBV and its weak relation to the development of HE infrastructure for prevention of GBV. Many of the articles focus on students in different ways, such as examining students' relations, experiences, behaviours, and predictors in relation to GBV. The generated knowledge in these studies is only, to a small extent, included in research on policy development. This results in a gap between students' lived experiences of GBV and the development of HE institutions' preventive work.
- A clear gap in the overall material related to the sample groups. An absolute majority of the included research focuses on students as a sample, and very few studies focus on staff in HE specifically, and not one identified article or review focused on doctoral students.
- Samples predominantly consist of majority group students. The lack of diversity and intersectional perspectives is a clear gap in the overall material, with the obvious exception of the specific search on intersectionality.
- The search on intersectionality can be categorised into two parts: Around half of the articles discuss individual experiences and the prevalence of GBV in HE from an intersectional perspective as a way of building more inclusive knowledge. The other half focus on intersectionality as a tool for change. The institutional and structural levels of HE is analysed through an intersectional lens in different ways.

- Research Funding Organisations are a central part of the HE infrastructure, yet there is a complete lack of research on RFOs in regard to GBV in HE.
- Findings regarding conceptual framework and methodology in this material confirm previous research results. Use of a wide range of scales, surveys and methodologies results in a variety of measures and numbers to describe GBV in HE. This in combination of the broad conceptual framework and varied definitions of GBV makes comparisons between studies and contexts challenging.

3.1.2. Systematic reviews on GBV in HE

3.1.2.1. General description of included articles

Research reviews give an overview of large numbers of articles and are of interest for this report because articles included in research reviews say something about the current state of knowledge, and research reviews in themselves also say something about which questions are in focus for much of the international research field on GBV in HE.

For a review to be included in this analysis, it had to be a systematic research review, meaning that the review describes the systematic search for and retrieval of the included articles, including search terms, databases and criteria for inclusion/exclusion. For further information on methodology see section 2.1. and Appendix A. All research reviews included in this part of the report are presented, including reference, DOI number, abstracts and keywords, with numbers 1-30 in Appendix B.

The included research reviews gather research from 1960 up until today and give a picture of the current state of research on GBV in HE in the international research field, which questions are in the foreground and which research make up our current knowledge and understanding of GBV in HE. The search was done without any geographical limitation, 29 reviews were conducted in the USA and one in Ethiopia. No systematic reviews conducted in ERA were found in the search. All but three focus on students and campus rather than academic staff. Several reviews highlight methodological difficulties with different measures and definitions of GBV (B8, B9, B23), which also affects the possibility to compare and replicate studies over time. These methodological challenges are also mirrored in the broad conceptual framework present in the reviews and reviewed articles.

Sexual harassment, sexual assault and sexual violence are some of the most used terms, but also intimate partner violence (IPV), dating violence, rape, sexual misconduct, unwanted sexual attention and several other terms are used and studied. Most of the reviewed articles lack an intersectional perspective, something that several of the reviews point out as problematic, asking for more nuanced, complex and diverse research in the future (B23, B24, B28, B29). Two of the included reviews focus on research on experiences of minority groups, trans students (B10) and LGBTQI+ students (B19). They conclude that there is a need for more research exploring minority groups' experiences of GBV in HE. This benchmark report contributes in part to this knowledge gap through including a sample of international research published since 2017, with an intersectional perspective at the centre.

In the following part of this benchmark report, findings from the included 30 systematic reviews are summarised, through four identified themes:

- Risk, protective factors and predictors
- Provision of services
- Prevention
- Prevalence

3.1.2.2. *Risk, protective factors and predictors*

Risk and protective factors are the focus in three of the reviews and are discussed both in relation to perpetration of sexual violence against women (B26), (re)victimization (B5), and dating violence perpetration and victimisation (B6).

History of perpetration is the strongest predictor of sexual violence perpetration at HEI (for men), while women who enter college with a history of sexual victimisation are at a substantially elevated risk for further victimisation in HE. Fraternity membership and peer approval of sexual violence are found to be more decisive predictors of sexual violence perpetration than alcohol consumption, hostile masculinity and/or men's rape myth acceptance (B26). Both alcohol/drug use, and peer and social risk factors are also discussed as risk factors for both dating violence perpetration and victimisation (B6). Yet another risk factor for sexual (re)victimisation is the limited knowledge and poor delivery of protective measures at HEI (B5).

All three reviews conclude that risk and protective factors are complex and highlight the need for theories and explanatory models which includes both individual, organisational and structural levels for understanding (for example an ecological model/theory, as elaborated on in B5 and B26).

3.1.2.3. *Provision of services*

Several of the reviews discuss HE at the institutional level, reviewing research on health service utilisation (B27), disclosure (B11), institutional characteristics (B28), sexual misconduct policies (B25), consequences (B18, B23), and underreporting (B2, B18).

In cases where a policy exists, the dissemination of its content and its availability may be inconsistent (B25). The importance of having a policy that is transparent and available in multiple different online areas, on which all key stakeholders continually collaborate, is highlighted (B25). Campus characteristics such as institution demographics, type, and climate are related to various forms of victimization, but the different campus characteristics did not show a direct correlation to victimisation, suggesting limitations of one-size-fits-all prevention approaches (B28).

Despite high rates of sexual violence victimisation, findings suggest a low use of campus health services and a low number of formal disclosure (B11, B27). Reviewed research also show that women victims tend to disclose to peers or informal personnel, suggesting that campus support service and education programmes regarding sexual victimization should be provided not only to survivors but also to individuals to whom disclosures are made (B11, B27). Finally, victims of sexual assault suffer negative academic outcomes, such as dropping out of university, having lower Grade Point Average, and experiencing self-regulated learning problems, among several other consequences (B23).

3.1.2.4. *Prevention*

Several systematic reviews examining prevention focus on bystander programmes. Bystanders are those who witness others being victims of GBV. Bystander intervention programmes, in various forms of training courses, aim at making bystanders intervene when witnessing GBV. Several of the reviews show that bystander programmes have significant effects, with desirable effects on bystander efficacy,

intentions, and intervention (B7, B13, B16, B17, B22). However, some of the reviews show that the examined bystander programmes only have short-term effects (B7, B13, B16, B17). It is suggested that campuses might tackle the observed decline by conceptualising bystander programming as an ongoing process and plan for follow-up strategies to reinforce programme content (B13). It is indicated that bystander programs have a desirable effect on bystander intervention, but not on GBV perpetration (B15).

In two reviews, the authors highlight the lack of global evidence and call for high quality research conducted across the world to enhance the understanding of bystander programmes' generalizability to non-US contexts (B17, B21). The issue with the dearth of diversity is highlighted, and some reviews (B7, B19) point out that most participants in the studies reviewed were female, white and cis gender. One review (B7) also highlights that the articles examined a variety of different programmes and utilised a variety of different instruments to measure bystander intervention efficacy. The authors call for more uniform measures to make programmes comparable.

One review (B30) focuses on other forms of prevention programmes than bystander ones, in this case a programme to prevent college dating violence. Findings suggest these programmes are effective at improving participants' knowledge and attitudes but are not effective at increasing bystander behaviours. The empirical evidence discussed in the reviewed articles suggests that dating violence prevention programmes may need to incorporate new techniques to effectively alter bystander behaviours.

3.1.2.5. Prevalence

A majority of the reviews regarding prevalence state that prevalence rates vary widely in the reviewed studies, in part due to how GBV is measured and defined and in part to other differences in study design, approaches and methodologies (B8, B9, B18).

Many of the articles reviewed use similar samples, which is a main limitation. One review (B2) concludes that the research often explores quantitative, juridical, and individual aspects of sexual harassment in higher education, but there is a continuous lack of qualitative and intersectional approaches and perspectives. Several of the reviews highlight the skewed samples as an issue (B2, B8, B18). In one review (B8), nearly all studies sampled white, heterosexual students attending 4-year colleges. Most studies sampled only female students. The prevalence findings are therefore limited. The few studies that explore ethnic and sexual minorities (B18, B19), students with disabilities (B23), or students with prior histories of sexual victimisation (B8), all found higher rates of sexual victimisation in these student populations. In another review (B18), results indicated that while white women respond more often that they had experienced sexual harassment, women of colour report more severe and prolonged consequences from their experiences of sexual harassment. The authors highlight the need for further prevalence research among at-risk populations and more inclusive measures (B8), as well as more examinations of how racism and other forms of oppression impact how students cope with sexual harassment (B18).

Most articles on GBV victimisation prevalence examine female students (B5, B27), while most articles on GBV perpetration prevalence sample male students (B1). While the vast majority of victimisation prevalence studies sample only female students, one review examines prevalence of sexual assault victimization among young college men. It concludes that men in college appear to be at higher risk for

sexual victimization than non-college men and are more likely to experience sexual violence when incapacitated.

The prevalence rates vary a lot, and the authors conclude that conceptualisation of sexual violence and wording attempting to assess prevalence rates likely lead to underestimation and suggest research should avoid definitions that include only intercourse or exclude women as potential perpetrators. The only review examining LGBTQ+ college and university students conclude that this group, and especially bisexual cisgender women and gender minority students, experience disproportionate sexual and relationship violence and negative outcomes are heightened by discrimination and minority stress. Despite experiencing disproportionate harm, LGBTQ+ students report feeling left out of campus sexual and relationship violence prevention and intervention efforts (B19).

The only review focusing on workplace harassment among higher education staff show that workplace harassment is prevalent in higher education at all levels and among all disciplines, gender is a major contributing factor, and sexual harassment was the most cited type of harassment in the reviewed literature (B12).

3.1.3. GBV in HE in ERA

3.1.3.1. General description of included material

Since the overall goal of GENDERACTIONplus is to contribute to the coordination of the gender equality and inclusiveness objectives of ERA, it is of interest for this part of the report to examine current research in the different EU countries. Since no systematic reviews conducted in ERA were found in section 3.1.2, a search was carried out to identify current research on GBV in HE in ERA. The search was done on country names and demonyms for all 27 MS, 16 AC, and the words 'EU' and 'Europe'.¹¹ 79 articles were identified in the search. Overall, 71 articles are included in this part of the research review, focusing on specific countries in ERA, associated countries and Europe as a whole. These 71 articles constitute a majority of the articles from European countries in the search, only eight articles were excluded due to wrong language or wrong topic. Countries not included in Table 1 had no results in the search (N=23).¹²

The articles, including reference, DOI number, abstracts and keywords are presented in Appendix C and also presented below in Table 1.

¹¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/updates-association-third-countries-horizon-europe-2021-12-21_en

¹² MS and AC with 0 results in the search: Albania, Armenia, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Faroe Islands, Finland, France, Georgia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Luxembourg, Malta, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Tunisia, Ukraine

Table 1: Articles included, divided in Europe, MS and AC, published 2017-2022.¹³

Europe, MS and AC	Number of included articles published 2017-2022
Europe	2
Austria	1
Bosnia and Herzegovina	1
Bulgaria	1
Cyprus	1
Denmark	1
Germany	3
Iceland	2
Ireland	1
Israel	1
Italy	6
Kosovo	1
Lithuania	2
Netherlands	2
Norway	3
Poland	3
Portugal	2
Romania	1
Spain	24
Sweden	2
Turkey	12

About one third of the included articles are from Spain (N=24). Turkey (N=12) and Italy (N=6) are the only countries with more than three published articles during the time period for this search (2017-2022). Around 70 percent of the included articles have students as a sample, while the remaining 30 percent mainly focus on HE at an institutional level, policies and protocols, and development of preventative measures. In a majority of the articles with student samples, students' experiences of

¹³ One article (C4) regards two MS, therefore the same article appears twice in this table, both for Lithuania and Cyprus.

GBV, mainly IPV or dating violence, are the main focus and consequences for HE institutions are only briefly mentioned (see for example C8, C14, C26, C70).

These articles are still of interest for working with GBV in HE, since knowledge about students' experiences of IPV and dating violence is important for developing preventive work in HEI. Some of the articles with student samples have a more direct relation to HE, where students' experiences of GBV are discussed in relation to HEI preventive work, provision of services, policies, education and training (see for example C31, C35, C44, C51). Six articles focus on staff or staff and students as samples (C4, C5, C34, C65, C66, C68) while doctoral students are invisible in the material (they might be included as part of staff or student population in some studies, but never pointed out as a specific sample).

Conceptually, the whole spectrum of GBV is present when the articles are examined as a coherent source of knowledge. Some concepts used are sexism (C5), psychological violence (C1), stalking (C43), sexual harassment (C17), sexual violence (C4), sexual aggression (C8), IPV (C14), dating violence (C60), cyber abuse (C36), rape (C32) and fear (C29)¹⁴. But when articles are examined separately, most of them uses a rather limited and specific understanding of GBV. This, in combination with the fact that in a majority of countries only 1-3 articles are published, the conceptual understanding and current state of knowledge in specific contexts are rather limited.

Since the aim for this part of the review is to give an overview of the current state of research on GBV in the ERA, the criteria for inclusion result in a collection of articles with a wide reach, not eligible for generalisations or statements about the overall situation in the ERA. Rather, the articles function as examples of research being carried out in the ERA to give an idea of different study objects, methodologies, theoretical frameworks and conceptual understandings of GBV in HE identified in the material. The material contains included articles which are presented below under different thematic rubrics:

- attitudes towards different forms of GBV in HE
- measures explicitly connected to preventing and handling GBV in HE
- studies implicitly connected to GBV, HE and vulnerability
- current state of knowledge on GBV in HE
- bystanders
- staff and doctoral students
- intersectionality
- research funding organisations

3.1.3.2. Attitudes towards GBV in HE

Numerous articles examine attitudes among students and staff towards different areas related to GBV, such as sexism (C5), gender equality (C33, C37), rape (C49), violence against women in the name of honour (C62, C65) and IPV (C39). One article develops and examines a scale to measure attitudes of university students and staff toward sexual harassment and assault (C66). Attitudes differ between age, gender, academic discipline, and social background, but several articles state that sexism and sexist and heteronormative attitudes obstruct the possibilities to tackle GBV. The articles result in recommendations and implications for the implementation of intervention such as:

¹⁴ The references are examples of some of the articles in the material which use these concepts.

- steps need to be taken to ensure that all employees understand that sexual harassment is an organisational, rather than an individual, problem (C5)
- leaders need to register all offences, including anonymous reports (C5)
- create more efficient mechanisms of sanctioning and reporting inappropriate behaviour (C33)
- promote attitudes in line with feminism (C37)
- design university curricula which enhance the development of egalitarian gender-role attitudes, with special focus on male students (C39)
- improve current efforts to develop educational and preventive programmes on sexual violence targeted to the general population, but particularly to men (C49)
- academics may try to change attitudes toward women by means of raising awareness among their students about honour crimes and killings (C65)

3.1.3.3. Measures explicitly linked to prevention and handling of GBV in HE

Several articles examine different levels of HEI infrastructure to prevent GBV. Two articles discuss national level legislation and initiatives (C6, C13), two articles explore policy implementation and development of protocol for handling GBV (C48, C56), one article evaluate a bystander training programme for university staff (C16), two articles discuss ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) as ways forward in preventative work for universities (C15, C38), and one article discusses a feminist approach to violence prevention (C69). The articles show for example that:

- practices related to corporate social responsibility can be used to discuss social responsibility of universities to fight against sexual harassment (C6)
- national authorities, HEI and individual levels need to work simultaneous to leverage change to the historically male dominated, masculinist criteria, procedures, processes and micropolitical practices that are 'normalised' in HEI (C13)
- relatively few training programmes based on the bystander approach to prevent GBV in HE have been performed in Europe (C16)
- there is a need for more systematic evaluation of training interventions that address cultural legitimization of GBV (C16)
- it is necessary to improve the knowledge and dissemination of mobile apps to make them a useful tool for prevention, education and support (C15)
- implementation of university policies against GBV is dependent on a combination of obstacles and opportunities, such as institutionalisation of gender equality, existing formal and informal institutions, and inertial resistances (C48)
- a feminist approach can be a useful framework for dating violence prevention efforts (C69)

3.1.3.4. Infrastructure implicitly linked to vulnerability

Some of the articles focus on the conditions and structure of HEI implicitly related to vulnerability and GBV. These articles examine power relations and HEI as gendered organisational structures (C1, C11, C12), gendered sites of resistance (C11), gendered financing system, institutional obstacles and researchers' vulnerability in relation to research topics (C3), neoliberal governing (C11), when practice does not align with values (C12), heterosexist environmental microaggressions (C19), and inequality, art and inclusive workspace (C23). The articles show for example:

- a need to change organisational culture, where lower positions pose a potential threat to experiencing harm (C1)
- a need for LGBTQ studies solidarity to overcome disadvantaged positions of LGBTQ scholars in post-socialist countries (C3)

- academics resist traditional neoliberal derivatives by for example exiting the institution and complaining through official channels (C11)
- how media and influencers can play part in preserving patriarchal power in academia (C12)
- heterosexist microaggressions within campus environment are negatively associated with students' perceptions of campus climate (C19)
- art(history) and philosophy can jointly analyse organisations as a basis for important conversations and to indicate institutional culture (C23)

3.1.3.5. Current state of knowledge on GBV in HE

Even though the 71 included articles differ by study object, methodology, theoretical framework and conceptual understanding of GBV in HE, some thematic strands of importance for knowledge on GBV in HE recurs in the material: prevalence, predictors, and consequences, as summarised below.

Some of the articles examine the prevalence of different forms of GBV in certain faculties, institutions, universities or student populations in a country (C24, C27, C28, C34). Other investigate prevalence of different forms of GBV perpetration and victimisation, often IPV or dating violence, in relation to different behaviours and experiences, as well as predictors of IPV and dating violence perpetration and victimization. Examples of results in these included articles are that:

- exposure to all forms of past-year sexual harassment was significantly more common among women and the youngest age cohorts. Fellow students committed the past-year sexual harassment in 18-29 percent of the instances, while a university staff member was reported to have committed the harassment in 0.6-4.6 percent of cases (C27)
- perpetrators of physical IPV are more likely to have been victims of physical, psychological and sexual IPV than non-perpetrators (C22)
- perpetrators and victims of IPV (physical, psychological, and sexual violence) showed higher rates of socialization of violence and tolerance toward IPV (C21)
- significant and positive correlations are established between emotional dependence, cyber-control and victimization of online aggression (C36)
- cyber dating victimisation and perpetration correlate with interpersonal and cognitive factors (C40)
- traditional gender roles were significantly associated with IPV indicators (C51)

Negative consequences of GBV have been studied and confirmed in previous research and in the included articles consequences of experiencing GBV are studied further and presented in six articles (C17, C18, C20, C26, C41, C44). These studies contribute to the overall knowledge on negative consequences of GBV at an individual level. Consequences at institutional or structural level are not specifically covered in any of the included articles.

Among other results, the articles show:

- experiencing sexual harassment is related to eating disorder symptoms for both genders with a regular gradient: the higher the harassment score, the more frequent the disordered eating behaviour symptoms (C17)
- a strong association between having experienced sexual harassment and several menstrual symptoms for female university students (C20)
- the risk of mental distress increases with sexual harassment exposure (C18)
- sexual harassment and assault, except for indecent exposure, is associated with insomnia,

with the odds of insomnia increasing as a function of the severity of harassment and assault (C26)

- all forms of violence are strongly associated with suicidal behaviour (C41)
- attempted coercion is associated with a higher risk of depression, while victims of attempted rape are at higher risk of substance use (C44)

3.1.3.6. *Bystanders*

Bystanders are those who witness others being victims of GBV. Bystander intervention programmes, in various forms of training courses, aim at making bystanders intervene when witnessing GBV, and are used to a various extent in HE internationally. Research on bystanders is a reoccurring theme and a rather extensive research topic in the international research field on GBV in HE. It was therefore somewhat surprising that recent research on bystanders is very limited in the ERA, with only one article focused on this theme (C16). If compared with the global research field in the section on research reviews, this is a gap that stands out particularly. Research on bystanders and bystander programmes is one of the main themes in that material.

3.1.3.7. *Staff and doctoral students*

The included articles on GBV and HE in an ERA context are heavily dominated by articles that use students as sample. Research focused on staff and doctoral students are much scarcer in the ERA. Six of the articles have both students and staff as sample (C1, C4, C34, C45, C66, C68), while only three of the articles (C5, C16, C65) focus on staff solely. Doctoral students are invisible in the material (although they might be included as part of staff or student population in some studies but never singled out as specific sample). This indicate that there is a lack of recent knowledge on university staff as well as doctoral students in relation to GBV in the ERA. This is in many ways in line with the international research field covered in our chapter on reviews, indicating a limited knowledge on university staff as well as doctoral students globally.

3.1.3.8. *Intersectionality*

A cross-cutting perspective in the GENDERACTIONplus project concerns enhancing the integration of intersectional perspectives in the policy discourse on GE in the ERA. The concept of intersectionality targets the interconnected, complex ways in which multiple inequalities (e.g., based on age, sex, gender, gender identity, sexuality, race/ethnicity, class, disability, nationality, religion, etc.) interact and position people. In research on GBV in HE in the ERA, research with intersectional perspectives is a clear knowledge gap. Only two of the included articles use an intersectional approach (C7, C64). One of them discusses the benefits of intersectional approaches for designing and implementing effective policies to tackle harassment and inequality in academia. It also shows that policy ineffectiveness was negatively related to women academics' inclination to pursue an academic career. Women academics that differed from the majority on multiple dimensions showed a stronger and more negative relationship between policy ineffectiveness and psychological safety. The other one investigates how young people make sense of dating violence from an intersectional perspective. Dating violence was interpreted and experienced differently by the participants depending on gender and the impact of traditional and egalitarian discourses on their accounts. The study showed nuanced differences in young people's meaning-making perspectives, needs, and vulnerabilities to dating violence and the authors call for diversity-informed, culturally tailored, and context-sensitive prevention practices (C64).

3.1.3.9. *Research funding organisations*

The results of the benchmark survey in this report focus on the existence and relevance of policies on GBV, especially targeting responses from national authorities and RFOs. In the research on GBV in HE in the ERA, studies on RFO are another clear knowledge gap. One article focuses on state policy developments and interventions, and research funding agency initiatives as one of them, in a national context (C13), but apart from this one article research on GBV and RFOs is absent in the ERA literature reviewed.

3.1.4. *Intersectional perspectives on GBV in HE*

3.1.4.1. *General description of included material*

Intersectionality is a concept stemming from different strands of feminist research, originally coined in 1989.¹⁵ Intersectional GBV is a direct consequence of the way different forms of discrimination and unequal power relations play out. For example, sexist and racist forms of violence and abuse often coexist and reinforce each other, with more severe consequences for racialised women than for other groups of women and minorities. As seen in a majority of the research reviews in this report, skewed samples and lack of diversity and intersectional perspectives on GBV in HE is often highlighted as a problem, and as something that affects both the validity and generalisability of the results. Hence, this part of the report aims at giving a broad picture of current international research using intersectionality (published 2017-2022) and what these studies can contribute to the overall field and understanding of GBV in HE.

There are also studies using other concepts than intersectionality doing intersectional work (for example diversity, inclusion, power, etc.), but due to time limitations for this specific assignment and an interest in the operationalisation of intersectionality, the concept intersectionality was used to limit the search, and hence the sample of the included publications. References are made with numbers 1-33 as listed in Appendix D.

Most of the articles included are conducted in the English-speaking part of North America, the majority are conducted in the US and some of them in Canada. One article examines the European context. Most of the articles (20 out of 33) use qualitative methods in their studies.

In this sample of articles (N=33) intersectionality is used in two different, but interconnected, ways: intersectionality as knowledge building, and intersectionality as tool for change. That is, first, intersectional perspectives are used to give a more inclusive and nuanced picture of the phenomenon GBV in HE, to contribute to knowledge building in the field. Second, intersectional perspectives are used to discuss the functioning and structures of HEI and of existing measures to prevent and handle GBV in HE.

3.1.4.2. *Intersectionality as knowledge building – individual level*

Around 50 percent of the included articles discuss individual experiences and prevalence of GBV in HE from an intersectional perspective as a way of building more inclusive knowledge. Both quantitative and qualitative methods are used to nuance and challenge the understanding of GBV in HE. Since this is a small sample, no generalisations can be drawn on prevalence numbers or experiences for specific groups at this stage, but overall, the included articles all show that analysing

¹⁵ Crenshaw 1989.

data and empirical material from an intersectional perspective gives new and important information on GBV in HE, for example:

- increased odds of victimisation among transgender students (D11)
- students with other ethnicity than white report less victimisation, but face greater extent of harassing behaviours (D28)
- intersecting systems of domination, specifically racism and sexism, influence experiences of campus sexual assault for women of colour (D13)
- students with disabilities have a statistically significant higher likelihood of sexual violence victimisation, both prior to and in HEI, and this student group is more likely to utilise formal sources of support than students without disabilities (D19)
- poverty, scarce resources and gender intersect to produce vulnerability for first year black female students (D1)
- LGBT students experience disproportionate rates of IPV compared with their heterosexual and cisgender counterparts (D27)
- one way of using intersectionality, to build a better knowledge, identified in the articles is exploring common concepts in the field of GBV in HE, like 'rape myth acceptance' (D22) and 'bystanders' (D5), from an intersectional perspective.

3.1.4.3. Intersectionality as tool for change

The above studies connect to an institutional level in HE through discussing the implications for preventive measures, reporting structures, and GBV education in HE. But there are also studies in the sample focusing on intersectional perspectives on reporting, education and policy. Differences of experiences, and perceived status, of reporting GBV, due to gender and sexual identity are explored in two articles (D16, D30). Four articles focus on education programmes, both through letting intersectional perspectives lead a critical examination of existing programmes (D30, D31) and by developing courses and curriculum through an intersectional lens (D4, D32). Two articles focus policy development, showing how a policy with ill-defined focus on gender can result in a colour-blind policy (D23, D26).

In eight of the included articles, HE is analysed through an intersectional lens in different ways, but with a focus on the institutional and structural level of HE. Three articles discuss academic culture, knowledge, and abuse of power from an intersectional perspective (D3, D6, D15). Three articles discuss how intersectionality can be used by the neoliberal HE system as a way of branding the university, focusing on the university reputation rather than taking intersectional claims seriously (D2, D7, D29). Two articles use intersectionality as ways of exploring methods to build transformative solutions and movements (D17, D20).

3.1.5. Research on RFOs and GBV in HE

In the research on GBV in HE in ERA, lack of studies on RFOs is another clear knowledge gap. Since this is a focus area in the report, a specific search procedure was performed screening for "RFOs" and other similar concepts. Only one publication examines RFOs.

The article (E1), which examines the Irish context, highlights several multi-level state interventions, and look at their gendered impact on HEI in Ireland, with RFOs as one of them. It mainly discusses the RFO's general GE initiatives and measures to include a gender dimension in research. GBV and

different multi-level institution initiatives to tackle GBV and sexual harassment specifically are discussed, but among these there are no measures taken by RFOs. The authors state that it is increasingly recognised that the structure and culture of HEI contributes to the likelihood of GBV. The article concludes that the case illustrates the importance of tackling gender inequality on several fronts. The best possibility of leveraging change arises when it is driven at a state (macro), institutional (meso), and situational (micro) level simultaneously, by gender competent leaders willing to tackle the historically male dominated, masculinist criteria, procedures, processes and micropolitical practices that are 'normalised' in HEI.

3.2. Benchmark survey

3.2.1. An overview of the findings

The results presented here focus on the existence and relevance of policies on GBV for RFOs and RPOs in 15 MS and a selected group of 20 RFOs engaged in the GENDERACTIONplus project. Benchmark survey questions, targeting national and regional policies on GBV for RFOs and RPOs, specifically address if and how targeted measures are included or not.¹⁶ This benchmark survey report is a follow-up of the extensive national mapping of policies performed in the UniSAFE project.¹⁷

Overall, **the results in this part of the report show that policies on GBV for RFOs do not exist, and that policies on GBV for RPOs are rare.** There are but two exceptions to these results among the 15 countries and regions included in the benchmark survey – Belgium-FWB and Ireland – in which recent developments have put in place a targeted and coherent framework for combatting some forms of GBV in RPOs. Among the 20 RFOs responding to the benchmark survey questions on GBV, only a few of them have targeted policies on GBV in place.

3.2.1.1. Results in sum: National and regional policies

- None out of the 15 countries or regions participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey has a national or regional policy against GBV in RFOs in place
- None out of the 15 countries or regions participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey has a policy against GBV in RPOs in place which includes measures for RFOs
- Only two out of 15 responding partners (Belgium-FWB, Ireland) in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have a national or regional policy against GBV in place for RPOs
- Concepts used in policies are often left undefined and mainly cover either some forms of GBV or only SH and discrimination
- An intersectional approach is missing throughout the analysed policy documents, with the single exception of Ireland where especially the national framework policy takes important steps towards making visible and using an intersectional lens in its aims and strategies.

3.2.1.2. Results in sum: Research funding organisations

- Five out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have developed policies on GBV since 1 May 2021
- One out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have measures targeting applicants

¹⁶ See Appendix F and G.

¹⁷ UniSAFE 2021b, 2021c.

- Three out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey indicate funding priorities in GBV
- Two out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey respond there has been recent policy developments targeting the safety of researchers
- Two out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey respond there are procedures for information on GBV misconduct by PIs or researchers and procedures for sanctions

3.2.2. National and regional policies – results

Policy development on national and regional level in the ERA is a key factor enabling RPOs, RFOs and other relevant stakeholders to adopt concepts, strategies and targeted measures combatting GBV on an institutional level. As is described in the UniSAFE report on national mapping of legal frameworks,¹⁸ all countries participating in the benchmark survey in GENDERACTIONplus have national laws on GBV in some sense. There are some differences concerning conceptual clarity and differentiation in these legal frameworks, but GBV is first and foremost included in laws on equal treatment or anti-discrimination as well as laws on labour and criminal offences. Further, some countries developed national action plans and strategies targeting GBV. A discrepancy between EU-14 and EU-13 countries is observed, both in terms of the existence of laws and targeted activities engaged in by national authorities.¹⁹

3.2.2.1. Participating countries and regions

Participating countries in the GENDERACTIONplus benchmark survey are listed in Table 2, indicating the responding national or regional authority and contact person.

Table 2. Participating national or regional authorities and contact persons responsible for answering the benchmark survey questions on GBV.

Country/region	National or regional authority	Contact person
EU-14		
Austria	Ministry of Education, Science and Research	Raffaella Ebersteiner
Belgium – F	Department of Economy, Science and Innovation	Liesbet Schruers
Belgium – FWB	Ministry of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation	Martin Degand
Denmark	University of Southern Denmark	Eva Sophia Myers
Greece	National Documentation Centre	Maria Malagkoniari

¹⁸ UniSAFE, 2021b, p. 24f.

¹⁹ Please cf the UniSAFE interactive map on legal and policy frameworks on GBV: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/map/>

Ireland	Higher Education Authority	Ross Woods
Portugal	Ministry of Science and Technology and Higher Education	Maria João Sequeira
Spain	Ministry of Science and Innovation	Zulema Altamirano
Sweden	Swedish Secretariat for Gender Research, University of Gothenburg	Fredrik Bondestam
EU-13		
Czech Republic	Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences	Hana Tenglerová
Lithuania	Vilnius University Šiauliai Academy	Virginija Šidlauskienė
Poland	National Information Processing Institute	Magdalena Chrobak-Tatara and Anna Knapinska
Republic of Croatia	Ministry of Science and Education	Doris Jozic
Associated Countries		
Norway	Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research	Heidi Holt Zachariassen
Israel	Ministry of Innovation, Science & Technology	Yael Proaktor

Most participating countries and regions are EU-14 MS. Belgium is represented by two regional authorities, whereas all other participating countries are represented by national entities. The representation of authorities differs between countries and regions, ranging from ministries of higher education to authorities to national institutes with an appointment to represent the national authority in the GENDERACTIONplus project.

3.2.2.2. Overall responses from participating MS and AC

In Table 3, the existence of national and regional policies on GBV in RFOs and RPOs are described per country and region, following the responses²⁰ given to three specific questions on to what extent RFOs and RPOs are targeted in policies, and if specific measures are included or not.²¹

²⁰ Responses from 15 MS and AC are presented. Two MS have not left complete answers to the benchmark survey as yet, and especially not on the questions regarding GBV. Therefore, these MS are excluded in this presentation.

²¹ Cf Appendix F for survey questions 7.1, 7.2 and 7.3 in detail.

Table 3: National or regional policies on GBV targeting RFOs and RPOs, overall answers to Q7.1-Q7.3, by 15 MS and AC.

Answers: Questions:	Yes	It is planned	No, and it is not planned	I don't know
National or regional policies for RFOs adopted (Q7.1)	Belgium-F, Greece, Lithuania, Poland	Austria	Belgium-FWB, Czech Republic, Denmark, Israel, Republic of Croatia, Spain, Sweden	Ireland, Norway, Portugal
National or regional policies for RPOs with actions for RFOs (Q7.2)	Belgium-F, Greece, Portugal	Austria, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Republic of Croatia	Belgium-FWB, Czech Republic, Denmark, Israel, Norway, Spain, Sweden	
National or regional policies for RPOs with actions (Q7.3)	Austria, Belgium-FWB, Greece, Ireland, Israel, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain		Czech Republic, Denmark, Sweden	Belgium-F, Republic of Croatia

Four out of 15 countries or regions responding to the benchmark survey indicated the existence of national policies on GBV for RFOs (Belgium-F, Greece, Lithuania and Poland). In Austria, a policy is planned, whereas most countries and regions (Belgium-FWB, Republic of Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Israel, Spain, Sweden) do not have a policy in place for RFOs and are not planning to develop it either. Three respondents lack knowledge on the existence of a policy on GBV for RFOs (Ireland, Norway, Portugal).

Much the same distribution of responses can be noted on the question related to the existence of a policy for RPOs on GBV, including targeted measures or actions to be taken by RFOs. Three out of 15 countries and regions (Belgium-F, Greece, Portugal) claim to have such policies in place. Several countries are planning policy development in this regard (Austria, Republic of Croatia, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland), whereas most countries and regions do not have a policy in place and are not planning to develop it either (Belgium-FWB, Czech Republic, Denmark, Israel, Norway, Spain, Sweden).

Finally, answers to the question on the existence of policies concerning GBV in RPOs, including targeted measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves, are somewhat different. A majority of responding countries and regions indicate the existence of such policies (Austria, Belgium-FWB, Greece, Spain, Ireland, Israel, Lithuania, Norway, Portugal, Poland). Three countries respond there is

a lack of policies and no plans to develop these (Czech Republic, Denmark, Sweden), and one country and one region indicate a lack of knowledge on the existence of a policy on GBV for RPOs (Belgium-F, Republic of Croatia).

In sum, the current situation, according to the MS and AC responding to the GENDERACTIONplus benchmark survey on the existence of policies on GBV, shows much the same distribution as the earlier national mapping of countries done within the UniSAFE project²² as well as the ERAC SWG GRI report on GBV and SH in ERA.²³ Few countries and regions report having policies on GBV targeting RFOs, although some indicate an upcoming process to develop policies mainly for RPOs. On the other hand, most countries and regions respond that policies on GBV targeting RPOs are in place.

3.2.2.3. Overall results in more detail

When looking in detail into the answers given to the different benchmark survey questions on the existence of policies on GBV, it is obvious these first results building on MS and AC responses must be discussed further. Although the questions were framed using clear distinctions between *laws*, *policies* and *policy measures*, some respondents did not distinguish between these definitions and dimensions.²⁴ For example, the responses from some countries and regions (Belgium-F, Greece, Lithuania) do not describe actual targeted policies on GBV for RFOs as requested, but rather refer to legislation, overarching National Action Plans (NAPs) on violence in society, protocols adopted by specific HEIs, or other similar frameworks not clearly using the definitions provided.

A few other countries report policies are in place for RPOs and/or RFOs, but these are more strictly to be categorised as gender equality policies targeting several different phenomena and not specifically addressing GBV (Poland, Portugal). The same holds true for a vast majority of answers on targeted policies on GBV for RPOs, where these responses tend to indicate the existence of laws, other legal entities, the inclusion of GBV to some extent in GEPs in RPOs, and other similar frameworks (Austria, Greece, Israel, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain). The only exception to this pattern is Belgium-FWB and Ireland. In Belgium-FWB a targeted circular²⁵ on combatting harassment and sexual violence is in place since 2021, and in Ireland a recently developed national framework²⁶ and an implementation plan²⁷ were adopted. This clearly demonstrates, in sum, that *targeted policies on GBV for RFOs do not seem to exist at all*, and that *targeted policies on GBV for RPOs are rare*.

²² According to the UniSAFE 2021b report, p. 103f, the following countries were described as having a coherent national or regional policy on GBV for RPOs: Czech Republic, Finland, France, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, Republic of Cyprus and Spain. Ireland and Portugal thus still report policies in place, according to the responses given to the benchmark survey questions in this GENDERACTION plus report, but not the Czech Republic. Though, the definition of policies in the UniSAFE report were not as narrow as is the case in the benchmark survey questions in the GENDERACTION plus benchmarking survey. Also, the UniSAFE mapping covered a period of six years, during which some adopted policies had lost their status for different reasons.

²³ SWG GRI 2018.

²⁴ This was clearly stated as important differences in definition in both benchmark surveys, as can be found in the first paragraphs in Appendix F and G.

²⁵ Circular of 13/09/2021. Prevention and fight against harassment and sexual violence within establishments of higher education: https://www.gallilex.cfwb.be/document/pdf/48826_000.pdf

²⁶ Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions: <https://assets.gov.ie/24925/57c394e5439149d087ab589d0ff39c92.pdf>

²⁷ Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Higher Education Institutions Implementation Plan, 2022-2024: https://hea.ie/assets/uploads/2021/04/HEA_ESVH_Implementation_Plan_FINAL.pdf

In terms of planned policy development indicated by several countries and regions, these include ideas on developing a Code of Conduct following from an updated NAP (Austria), sharpening of procedures for tackling discrimination and harassment (Poland), and examples of integrating aims and measures on GBV in specific GEPs (Republic of Croatia). The main reasons given for the lack of targeted policies in several countries and regions address the argument of current legislation on GBV more broadly also covering combatting GBV in RPOs and RFOs (Denmark, Israel, Spain, Sweden). There are also arguments given on the current lack of interest or political incentives (Republic of Croatia, Czech Republic). Further issues on the content, scope, relevance, use of intersectionality etc. are described and discussed in more detail in a section below turning more directly to the actual content of the national policies.

3.2.2.4. Widening participation or not?

Table 4 illustrates the same results as Table 3, but instead displayed per country and region and divided between advanced countries/regions, less advanced countries/regions,²⁸ and associated countries, and only depicting the “Yes”-answers.

Table 4: National or regional policies on GBV targeting RFOs and RPOs, “Yes”-answers to Q7.1-Q7.3, divided into EU-14, EU-13 and AC.

Country/region	National or regional policies for RFOs adopted (Q7.1)	National or regional policies for RPOs with actions for RFOs (Q7.2)	National or regional policies for RPOs with actions (Q7.3)
EU-14			
Austria	---	---	✓
Belgium – F	✓	✓	---
Belgium – FWB	---	---	✓
Denmark	---	---	---
Greece	✓	✓	✓
Ireland	---	---	✓
Portugal	---	✓	✓
Spain	---	---	✓
Sweden	---	---	---
EU-13			
Czech Republic	---	---	---

²⁸ As defined in the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2021-2022: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf

Lithuania	✓	---	✓
Poland	✓	---	✓
Republic of Croatia	---	---	---
Ass. Countries			
Israel	---	---	✓
Norway	---	---	✓

The summary in Table 4, on the overall responses to questions on policy development in MS and AC, indicates some important aspects. There is no clear difference between EU14 and EU13 countries and regions in terms of responses on the existence of policies on GBV for RFOs. Although only half of EU-27 MS participated in this benchmark survey, the results indicate a situation partly in contrast to the national mapping of policies in the UniSAFE project, where it was concluded that more advanced countries had policies in place on GBV to a larger degree.²⁹

The latter holds true, though, when depicting the answers on whether policies on GBV for RPOs with measures targeting RFOs are in place; only EU14 countries respond “Yes” in this regard. The overall distribution on the reported existence of policies on GBV for RPOs also confirms the identified differences between EU14 and EU13 countries and regions. Included AC display the current existence of policies on GBV for RPOs, but a lack of such policies targeting RFOs.

Importantly though, as discussed previously in relation to the overall responses to questions on national or regional policies on GBV for RFOs and RPOs in Table 3, it is evident that these answers do not illustrate the actual existence of policies targeting RFO and RPOs directly.

3.2.2.5. Conceptual clarity, scope and relevance?

The use of an inclusive, conceptual understanding of GBV in policy development is crucial to be able to eradicate all forms of violence and abuse prevalent in ERA RPOs and RFOs. In the benchmark survey responses targeting MS and AC on policy development, there are several responses claiming the existence of national or regional policies for both RPOs and RFOs, as displayed above in Table 4. The analysis so far illustrated this is not the case, as responses more often than not refer to legislation and other frameworks instead, with the sole exception of Belgium-FWB and Ireland. It is still interesting to analyse to what extent and how these current legislative and other frameworks use the concept of GBV, and how the conceptual understanding is displayed, defined, and eventually discussed. This is not the least important as legal and other frameworks are instrumental for potential future development of targeted policies on GBV for RFOs and RPOs.

The definition of GBV used in this context – also specified as an entry point for respondents to the benchmark survey questions – is *all forms of violations and abuse*, including but not limited to, physical violence, psychological violence, economic and financial violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender harassment, stalking, organisational violence, and harassment – in both online and offline contexts, including emerging forms of violence. The concept of GBV includes a continuum

²⁹ UniSAFE 2021b, p. 103f.

of violence and violations, violent behaviours and attitudes based on sex and gender, which also intersects with and shapes other dimensions of inequalities, such as inequalities based on age, class, ethnicity, disability and sexuality.³⁰ With this definition in mind, where for example, sexual harassment is seen as one of several forms of GBV, it is relevant to discuss the conceptual state-of-the-art in the benchmark survey responses as presented in sum in Table 5.

Table 5: National or regional policies on GBV targeting RFOs and RPOs, definition of used concepts by those answering “Yes” to one or more questions.

<i>Answers:</i>	Covering and defining all forms of GBV	Covering and defining two or more forms of GBV	Covering and defining SH and discrimination
<i>Questions:</i>			
National or regional policies for RFOs adopted (Q7.1)	---	Belgium-F ³¹ , Greece ³²	Lithuania ³³ , Poland ³⁴
National or regional policies for RPOs with actions for RFOs (Q7.2)	---	Belgium-F ³⁵ , Greece ³⁶ , Portugal ³⁷	
National or regional policies for RPOs with actions (Q7.3)	---	Belgium-FWB ³⁸ , Ireland ³⁹ , Portugal ⁴⁰	Austria ⁴¹ , Greece ⁴² , Israel ⁴³ , Lithuania ⁴⁴ , Norway ⁴⁵ , Poland ⁴⁶ , Spain ⁴⁷

³⁰ UniSAFE 2021a.

³¹ NAP for society at large and not a specific policy addressing RFOs.

³² NAP for society at large and not a specific policy addressing RFOs.

³³ General legislative framework in terms of amendments to the Labour Code (Article 30 (2)).

³⁴ The Men and Women Equality Plan (MWE) of the National Centre for Research and Development (NCBR).

³⁵ NAP for society at large and not a specific policy addressing RPOs.

³⁶ NAP for society at large and not a specific policy addressing RPOs.

³⁷ General legislative framework and specific studies performed.

³⁸ Women’s Rights Plan 2020-2024; Circular of 13/09/2021 Prevention and fight against harassment and sexual violence within establishments of higher education

³⁹ Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions.

⁴⁰ Individual GEPs, a project on gender inclusion in STEM as well as legal framework.

⁴¹ BMBWF and public universities GEPs as well as The Austrian Academy of Sciences guideline for dealing with sexual harassment and mobbing.

⁴² No policy is referred, the analysis builds on response given only.

⁴³ The Law for the Prevention of Sexual Harassment.

⁴⁴ The Conference of Rectors of Lithuanian Universities "Guidelines for the prevention and investigation of cases of sexual harassment".

⁴⁵ Proposition 89 L (2018–2019) Proposal on Amendments to the Universities and Colleges Act and the Vocational Schools Act (student representative, harassment and facilitation).

⁴⁶ Survey among supervised public universities regarding their anti-mobbing and antidiscrimination procedures.

⁴⁷ Law 17/2022 of Science, Technology and Innovation.

Analysing the policies, being foremost legal documents, NAPs and other general frameworks, it is evident that there is a lack of definitions in many of the policies stated by respondents to be inclusive of GBV. Although several forms of GBV are mentioned in some countries and regions, there are often no clear definitions put forward, based on for example research-based knowledge or other sources as validation of perspectives. It is more often the case, as in, for example, the policy referred to by Poland through NCBR (National Center for Research and Development), that an overarching ambition with gender equality is “counteracting violence in the workplace (mobbing, harassment)” and the need to ensure “the elimination of prejudices, customs and traditions based on stereotypical sex roles, discrimination and sex-based violence including sexual harassment”.⁴⁸ There are no further definitions given, and although the response on Q7.3 indicates targeted aims and measures for RFOs in this particular case, there are no examples in the existing policies referred to.

It is commonplace to use sexual harassment and discrimination as concepts targeting the issues at stake, usually by referring to existing laws, propositions and other legal instruments targeting working life in general or society. Mobbing, violence, or in some instances, sexual violence, are often added on to sexual harassment and discrimination, but without further definitions or clear demarcations between the different concepts used. Further, although sometimes referring to conventions and broader frameworks outside national contexts, in which GBV is more clearly adopted and defined (such as The Istanbul Convention or The ILO Convention No 190 on Eliminating violence and harassment in the world of work), this has no visible impact on the scope and content of analysed policies in this regard.

In sum, GBV as a concept in this context, with its inclusive and far-reaching ambition to capture multiple forms of violations and abuse, is as yet not used as a baseline for national and regional policies targeting RFOs and RPOs in ERA.

3.2.2.6. Intersectionality on the rise in policy discourse on GBV in ERA?

A cross-cutting perspective in the GENDERACTIONplus project concerns enhancing the integration of intersectional perspectives in the policy discourse on GE in ERA. Intersectionality is defined in this context as overlapping or intersecting categories such as gender, sex, ethnicity, age, socioeconomic status, sexual orientation, and geographical location that combine to inform individuals’ identities and experiences. The term was coined by legal scholar Kimberlé Crenshaw in 1989 to describe how multiple forms of discrimination, power and privilege intersect in Black women’s lives, in ways that are erased when sexism and racism are treated separately.⁴⁹ Since then, the term has been expanded to describe intersecting forms of oppression and inequality emerging from structural advantages and disadvantages that shape a person’s or a group’s experience and social opportunities.

Responses to the question on the existence of a policy on GBV targeting RFOs had a follow-up option: “If yes, does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (an intersectional perspective)?”.⁵⁰ All four countries and regions (Belgium-F, Greece, Lithuania, Poland) responding positively on the existence of a policy, also answered “yes” on the question on an intersectional perspective. In one case, there is a clear and defined and used intersectional perspective (Belgium-F), as the NAP both has integrated an intersectional perspective throughout, but also displays several strategies and measures following from an intersectional analysis. In the words of the respondent:

⁴⁸ NCBR. 2021. *Men and Women Equality Plan for the National Center for Research and Development*, p. 29: <https://www.gov.pl/attachment/36f5ee48-54d4-4666-a449-890569cfbcca>

⁴⁹ Crenshaw 1989.

⁵⁰ Q7.1, cf Appendix F.

“The NAP 2021-2025 integrates an intersectional approach that allows taking into account the complex situations in which some people are at the same time at the crossroads of different forms of oppression”. The other responding countries have referred to policies which to some extent include other dimensions, such as sexuality/LGBTQ and functional diversity, but there are nothing indicating the use of an intersectional perspective.

In sum, there are some important developments on a policy level in the responding MS and AC on including other dimensions of power, discrimination, and oppression beyond gender, which is visible when taking part in the total responses of the benchmark survey in GENDERACTIONplus. The use of an intersectional lens or perspective in developing policies on GBV for RFOs and RPOs is in its early stages, and consequently there are only a few examples in this report. In all these instances, though, as was mentioned in relation to the analysis of overall results from table 3 above, these are policies not directly targeting GBV and RFOs and RPOs.

3.2.3. RFO policies and measures – results

RPOs of all sorts – private, public, regional, national – are key actors in promoting GE in ERA and beyond.⁵¹ Funding organisations can be instrumental as stakeholders setting the agenda and also working towards eradicating GBV in ERA RPOs. Although differences between and within national and regional contexts make it difficult to achieve a common policy discourse on GE for RFOs, the impact of RFOs targeted measures on combatting GBV in RPOs is crucial. Funding mechanisms are vital as governing mechanisms and can be instrumental preventive measures if used with care and in dialogue with RPOs, researchers, and other relevant stakeholders.

3.2.3.1. Participating Research Funding Organisations

This is exactly why GENDERACTIONplus prioritises building capacity and knowledge together with RFOs on GE and GBV. A total of 20 RFOs participate in the GENDERACTIONplus CoP, which also serves as the basis for responding to the benchmark survey on GBV policies.⁵² The results in this part cover answers on the benchmark survey from the RPOs participating in the CoP in GENDERACTIONplus as listed below in table 6.

Table 6. National and regional RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus CoP and contact persons answering the benchmark survey questions on GBV.

Country/region	RFO	Contact person
EU-14		
Belgium – F	Research Foundation of Flanders (FWO)	Tim Thijs

⁵¹ de Cheveigné et al 2010; Young Håkansson & Sand 2021.

⁵² Cf Appendix G.

Belgium – FWB	National Fund for Scientific Research (NFSR)	Nadège Ricaud
Denmark	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Maria Mortensen
Ireland	Irish Research Council (IRC)	Emer Cahill
Italy	Regional Foundation for Biomedical Research (FRRB)	Paola Bello
Portugal	The Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Maria João Sequeira
Spain	The Spanish State Research Agency (AEI)	Lucía Ramírez and Lourdes Armesto
Sweden	Forte (FOR)	Inger Jonsson
Sweden	Vinnova (VIN)	Sophia Ivarsson
EU-13		
Bulgaria	Bulgarian National Science Fund (BNSF)	Milena Aleksandrova
Czech Republic	Technology Agency of the Czech Republic (TACR)	Jana Dvořáčková
Estonia	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Merili Tamson
Lithuania	Research Council of Lithuania (LMT)	Reda Cimperman
Malta	Malta Council for Science and Technology (MCST)	Jennifer Cassingena Harper
Poland	The National Centre for Research and Development (NCRD)	Monika Wąsowska
Poland	National Science Centre (NCN)	Aleksandra Sienkowiec
Republic of Cyprus	Research and Innovation Foundation (RIF)	Kalypso Sepou
Romania	The Executive Unit for the Financing of Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation (UEFISCDI)	Alexandru Mihai Dinu

Associated Countries		
Norway	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Ingeborg W. Ovesen
Turkey	The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TÜBİTAK)	Duygu Çelik

The representation of national and regional RFOs is important, as is the differentiated participation of both state-funded and private key stakeholders for research funding. Further, there is a diverse participation of RFOs with different profiles, ranging from main national research funding agencies to RFOs particularly funding research in STEM, innovation, biomedical research or health and working life. Also, the representation from both EU14 and EU13 is a strength when analysing issues on widening participation and the importance of fostering policy development on GE and GBV. The RFO CoP in GENDERACTIONplus comprise a selection of RFOs, and therefore the results in this part are not representative for ERA.

3.2.3.2. RFO policies and intersectionality

The GENDERACTIONplus project does not map all policies on GBV among different stakeholders, as this has been done within the UniSAFE project.⁵³ Instead, recent important policy developments are sought for, with a particular interest in preventive measures, intersectional perspectives, and other issues.

In Table 7 below, the existence of new and recent RFO policies on GBV is summarised. The results are clustered with the question on whether the existing policy has an intersectional perspective or not.

Table 7. New or revised RFO policies on GBV since 1 May 2021, with an intersectional perspective.

Answers:	Yes, with an intersectional perspective	Yes, but no intersectional perspective is planned	No
Questions:			
New or revised RFO policy to address GBV in relation to the applicants (Q6.1)	IRC (Ireland) LMT (Lithuania)	MCST (Malta) NFSR (Belgium FWB) UEFISCDI (Romania)	AEI (Spain) BNSF (Bulgaria) DFF (Denmark) ETAG (Estonia) FCT (Portugal) FOR (Sweden) FRRB (Italy) FWO (Belgium F) NCN (Poland)
RFO policy on GBV with an intersectional perspective (Q6.3)			

⁵³ UniSAFE 2021b.

			<p>NCRD (Poland)</p> <p>RCN (Norway)</p> <p>RIF (Republic of Cyprus)</p> <p>TACR (Czech Republic)</p> <p>TÜBİTAK (Turkey)</p> <p>VIN (Sweden)</p>
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Five out of 20 RFOs have developed policies on GBV since 1 May 2021 (IRC, LMT, MCST, NFSR, UEFISCDI). Two out of those five RFOs have indicated an intersectional perspective is included (IRC, LMT). This is a somewhat promising result, as the recent UniSAFE report mapping policy development among RFOs on GBV up until 2020 concluded by stating no RFO in ERA had a policy in place combatting GBV.⁵⁴

The LMT policy,⁵⁵ which in fact is not an RFO-specific policy but a law on labour and discrimination, covers all forms of discrimination asked on in the survey (cf. Appendix G), except ethnicity. There are no indications of the use of a more advanced intersectional perspective. A strong focus is on combatting psychological violence and sexual harassment, and there are no signs of expanding the scope towards a more inclusive understanding of GBV. The IRC policy⁵⁶ covers all forms of discrimination (including civil status and family status) but does not advocate an intersectional approach.

At the same time, the different forms of violations described in the law on labour and discrimination are nuanced and detailed, and to some extent this implies an understanding of qualitatively different consequences of GBV depending on survivors' status. The IRC policy concentrates on three different forms of violations and abuse (bullying, harassment, sexual harassment) and use inclusive definitions of these, but does not expand to the concept of violence or the more inclusive aspects of GBV. The other three RFOs responding positively on the question on policy development, but without an intersectional dimension, are examples of RFO policies being a GEP with descriptions of overall legislative demands on combatting GBV (MCST)⁵⁷, as well as guidelines to recognise and prevent sexual and moral harassment (UEFISCDI).⁵⁸

3.2.3.3. RFO targeted measures combatting GBV

In Tables 8-10 below, questions on new or recent policy developments on GBV – i.e., measures targeting applicants, funding schemes, and the safety of researchers – are described. All questions ask for developments since 1 May 2021. This is due to being the end date for collection of data using the same questions in the UniSAFE report national mapping policy in ERA.⁵⁹ It is also relevant to use

⁵⁴ UniSAFE 2021b, p. 106.

⁵⁵ <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/a1effc70f87e11ecbfe9c72e552dd5bd> (only in Lithuanian).

⁵⁶ Bullying, Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy: https://research.ie/assets/uploads/2021/06/IRC-Bullying-Harassment-and-Sexual-Harassment-Policy_June-2021.pdf

⁵⁷ Also highlighting different inequalities in line with current legislation. <https://mcst.gov.mt/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Gender-Equality-Plan-002.pdf>

⁵⁸ https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/resource-866289-uefiscdi_ghid-pentru-prevenirea-hartuirii-sexuale.pdf. Only in Romanian.

⁵⁹ UniSAFE 2021b.

this short deadline in order to find out to which extent the GEP requirement on gender equality, in which GBV is one of several recommended priority areas, has triggered any actions in terms of planning for or actually developing and adopting new or revised policies including measures on GBV.

Table 8. New or recent RFO policy development on measures against GBV for applicants since 1 May 2021.

<i>Answers:</i>	Yes	No but it is planned	No and it is not planned	I don't know
<i>Questions:</i>				
RFO measures against GBV for the applicants (Q6.4)	IRC (Ireland)	FCT (Portugal)	AEI (Spain) DFF (Denmark) ETAG (Estonia) FOR (Sweden) FRRB (Italy) FWO (Belgium F) MCST (Malta) NFSR (Belgium FWB) RIF (Republic of Cyprus) TACR (Czech Republic) TÜBİTAK (Turkey) VIN (Sweden)	BNSF (Bulgaria) LMT (Lithuania) UEFISCDI (Romania) NCN (Poland) NCRD (Poland) RCN (Norway)

Only one out of 20 responding RFOs (IRC) has measures targeting applicants. The IRC have a developed measure described as follows: “Applicants must self-certify at the application stage that they do not hold an active sanction against them for matters of bullying, harassment or sexual harassment. If they do, then a risk assessment must be carried out by the host institution to ensure it is safe and appropriate for the applicant to be leading junior members of the team and/or taking on a supervisor/mentorship role.”

FCT is planning to develop measures targeting applicants and also describe the importance of legal mechanisms: “A Working Group to elaborate a new Integrity Code/Code of Conduct, addressing the integrity culture in the institution, in all aspects, which is expected to deliver in the short run. In spite of the lack of specific dispositions in FCT regulations in this regard, good practices are safeguarded

through legal mechanisms, such as the institution’s replies to complaints filed with the Deputy Ombudsman for Research. FCT is also explicitly committed with these procedures whenever considered in the regulations of international calls.”

Several RFOs comment on the lack of a policy with measures targeting applicants. Some describe the lack of interest in the organisation, whereas others describe GBV as an upcoming issue to discuss and further develop in relation to GEPs and the development of a code of conduct. Other RFOs describe the lack of competence on GBV as a reason or question to some extent whether measures targeting applicants is within the scope of an RFO.

One of the RFOs (FWO) also comments on this issue, at least in an indirect way, as already being part of their GEP, and states why it is necessary to take steps as an RFO concerning the safety of researchers (and thus also applicants): “The FWO requires the supervisors of its PhD fellows or postdoctoral researchers to create and maintain a safe environment for the proper functioning of the researchers. Attention to psychosocial well-being is an essential element of such a safe environment. Fellowship holders can raise psychosocial problems with their supervisors. All Flemish host institutions also have a network of ombudsman services and confidential advisers to whom FWO researchers can turn with psychosocial problems they cannot discuss with their supervisor. When a PhD fellow or postdoctoral researcher has used all facilities in their own host institution to find a solution to a psychosocial problem, in particular in the event of conflicts between the researcher and the supervisor, the FWO can, as a last resort, attempt to mediate.” This final comment touches on several other RFO responses. There is a general difficulty to draw a clear line between targeted measures on GBV and other measures securing equal terms, safety or access to funding in different ways.

In Table 9, funding schemes on GBV as a priority topic are in focus. As for the previous Table 8, questions pertain to a limited timeframe set to policy developments since 1 May 2021.

Table 9. New or recent RFO policy development on GBV as a priority topic in funding since 1 May 2021.⁶⁰

<i>Answers:</i>	Yes	No and it is not planned	I don't know
<i>Questions:</i>			
GBV as a priority topic in funding (Q6.5)	FCT (Portugal) IRC (Ireland) RCN (Norway)	AEI (Spain) DFF (Denmark) ETAG (Estonia) FOR (Sweden) FRRB (Italy) FWO (Belgium F) MCST (Malta) NFSR (Belgium FWB)	BNSF (Bulgaria) LMT (Lithuania) NCN (Poland) NCRD (Poland)

⁶⁰ None of the RFOs responding to the GENDERACTIONplus survey used the alternative “No, but it is planned”, therefore this column is omitted in table 9.

		<p>RIF (Republic of Cyprus)</p> <p>TACR (Czech Republic)</p> <p>TÜBİTAK (Turkey)</p> <p>UEFISCDI (Romania)</p> <p>VIN (Sweden)</p>	
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Three (FCT, IRC, RCN) out of 20 RFOs have indicated funding priorities in GBV. There have been several different funding initiatives among these, including one project on GBV in academia co-funded within the GENDER-NET Plus project (RCN). The IRC has funded more than 350 partnerships among researchers and NGOs, whereas the FCT has funded a broad range of projects on hate crime and consequences on Covid-19. It is unclear whether some or any of these projects actually targets the content of the question (support research on GBV *in* universities and research organisations). Several comments describe the lack of funding initiatives as a consequence of (the lack of) political priorities, funding schemes not set up for specific areas of interest, the bottom-up approaches governing funding systems, etc. Further comments also pinpoint the issue of GBV not being considered a “real” problem, and there are also comments claiming the RFO only funds excellence. In sum, it seems reasonable to conclude there is a continuing lack of directed funding schemes targeting the issue of GBV in RPOs.

In Table 10, an important aspect of targeted measures combatting GBV in RPOs is asked for; that is to what extent RFOs have taken any actions for the safety of researchers. As for the previous Tables 8 and 9, the question has a limited timeframe set to policy developments since 1 May 2021.

Table 10. New or recent RFO policy development on actions for the safety of researchers since 1 May 2021.

<i>Answers:</i>	Yes	No and it is not planned	I don't know
<i>Questions:</i>			
Actions or measures regarding GBV for the safety of researchers in projects (Q6.6)	<p>FCT (Portugal)</p> <p>IRC (Ireland)</p>	<p>AEI (Spain)</p> <p>DFF (Denmark)</p> <p>ETAG (Estonia)</p> <p>FOR (Sweden)</p> <p>FRRB (Italy)</p> <p>FWO (Belgium F)</p> <p>MCST (Malta)</p> <p>NFSR (Belgium FWB)</p> <p>RCN (Norway)</p> <p>RIF (Republic of Cyprus)</p>	<p>BNSF (Bulgaria)</p> <p>LMT (Lithuania)</p> <p>NCN (Poland)</p> <p>NCRD (Poland)</p> <p>UEFISCDI (Romania)</p>

		TACR (Czech Republic) TÜBİTAK (Turkey) VIN (Sweden)	
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Two out of 20 RFOs (FCT, IRC) have responded that there have been recent policy developments targeting the safety of researchers. The IRC response is of a more general character: “As IRC awards are made on an individual basis we allow for freedom of mobility. This means awardees are allowed to change institution during the lifetime of the award without penalty. Likewise for early career researchers they are allowed to change institution and/or supervisor or mentor during the award.” This is in line with the response from the FCT, pointing at safety measures being in place for a long time and not directly aimed (only) at tackling consequences of GBV: these “procedures occur just when there is a complaint, and clear impacts on the execution of the project are expected. If this is the case, FCT promotes the confrontation of the involved parties, including the complainant, the hosting institutions and the prevaricator (principal investigator, thesis supervisor, other). When projects are developed under a consortium, ethical / integrity issues must be addressed in a Protocol. If divergencies are not likely to be solved, the minimum basic conditions of the funding support have to be reassessed and, at the limit, the suspension/cancellation of funding may be considered.”

All in all, these latter responses demonstrate procedures and practices which have long been well known among the RFO community at large, and existing in several other RFOs both in ERA and beyond. A majority of comments on why the safety of researchers has not been targeted by RFOs in this respect, point at the issue being the responsibility of RPOs (or difficult to address as funders do not always fund individual researchers, but consortia and infrastructure, etc.). There are also some responses indicating resistance to GBV measures.

In the overall responses on this question, there are no indications as to whether or to what extent the consequences of GBV, especially for minorities, mobile researchers or other vulnerable groups, are considered when commenting, planning for or adopting these procedures. It would be an interesting development, i.e., to apply an intersectional lens to different aspects of safety procedures, to be able to develop more directed and relevant measures. It is also important to stress the need for collaborative efforts between RFOs and RPOs on the safety of researchers, instead of claiming the responsibility to solely be elsewhere.

In Table 11 below, results from two questions are merged: if RFOs have procedures for (a) receiving information on misconduct of researchers and (b) on possible sanctions targeting perpetrators. As all RFOs have answered identically on both questions, these are presented in the same table. Please observe, in contrast to the tables above on recent and new policy development, the questions in Table 11 are not limited in time.

Table 11. RFO procedures for receiving information on misconduct of researchers and possible sanctions targeting perpetrators.

Answers:	Yes	No and it is not planned	I don't know
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Questions:			
<p>Procedures for information from RPOs on GBV misconduct by PIs or researchers applying for funding (Q6.7)</p>	<p>FCT (Portugal) FOR (Sweden) IRC (Ireland)</p>	<p>AEI (Spain) DFF (Denmark) ETAG (Estonia) FRRB (Italy) NFSR (Belgium FWB) RIF (Republic of Cyprus) TACR (Czech Republic) TÜBITAK (Turkey) VIN (Sweden) UEFISCDI (Romania)</p>	<p>BNSF (Bulgaria) FWO (Belgium F) LMT (Lithuania) MCST (Malta) NCN (Poland) NCRD (Poland) RCN (Norway)</p>
<p>Procedures for sanctioning perpetrators when informed on GBV misconduct by an RPO (Q6.8)</p>			

Three out of 20 RFOs (FCT, FOR, IRC) have responded that there are procedures for information on GBV misconduct by PIs or researchers and procedures for sanctions. FCT responds the same way as on the previous question presented in Table 10. The IRC has a procedure in place, where: “Applicants are asked to self-certify if they have any active sanctions against them for matters of bullying, harassment or sexual harassment as part of their applicant declarations. On each application, the RFO is asked to endorse the applicant and their application, verifying to the best of their ability that all information provided is correct.”

FOR reports having indirect procedures in place, i.e., not targeting GBV specifically, although they have not been used as yet for the purpose of sanctioning perpetrators: “The contract does not specify anything concerning GBV, but there is a clausula listing grounds for decision to terminate payment of funds. One reads: “the project leader, through other actions, is clearly shown to be an inappropriate recipient of funding from Forte”. In theory GBV could be a deviation from the contract that should be reported to Forte, but there are no indications that it has been done.”

Most comments from RFOs on the lack of procedures for information and sanctions, describe being in lack of information as such and also stress the problems of not being able to take action on an incident. This is perceived by many as the responsibility of RPOs. FNRS comments on their response also in the following way: “FNRS adopted a case-by-case approach for sanctioning perpetrators, when informed on misconduct in terms of GBV by an RPO. It is discussed in the frame of its Board of Directors.” In another comment from TACR, the recurrent theme of resistance to gender equality and GBV is being described more in detail: “These kinds of measures are, in general, still very rare among RFOs. Therefore, such measures would entail high resistances in the organization and would probably complicate the introduction of other “gender measures”. Promoting gender equality in research is still a relatively new activity in the Czech research ecosystem, especially among RFOs. More awareness-raising is needed before it is possible to introduce such a measure.”

In sum, it seems as if the issues of collecting information on general misconduct are being developed among RFOs, although not specifically addressing misconduct in terms of GBV. The same goes for systems and procedures for withdrawing funding, or by other means sanctioning different forms of research misconduct. Yet, sanctions on perpetrators of GBV, to be used by RFOs, seems still to be an issue to tackle, both in terms of creating the incentives to pursue new forms and procedures for holding perpetrators accountable as well as ensuring the capability and resources for developing relevant procedures per se.

3.2.3.4. Current ideas on RFO policy developments

In Table 12 below, the existence of ideas on future measures and strategies to combat GBV among RFOs are presented.⁶¹

Table 12. Current ideas on prevention of GBV by RFOs.

Answers:	Yes	No	I don't know
Questions:			
Current ideas on prevention of GBV by RFOs (Q6.9)	FCT (Portugal) IRC (Ireland)	DFF (Denmark) ETAG (Estonia) FWO (Belgium F) MCST (Malta) NCN (Poland) NFSR (Belgium FWB) TACR (Czech Republic) VIN (Sweden) UEFISCDI (Romania)	AEI (Spain) BNSF (Bulgaria) FOR (Sweden) FRRB (Italy) LMT (Lithuania) NCRD (Poland) RCN (Norway) RIF (Republic of Cyprus) TÜBİTAK (Turkey)

Two (FCT, IRC) out of 20 RFOs have responded that there are current ideas on prevention of GBV being discussed. FCT highlights an existing policy⁶² from another stakeholder and argues on the importance of developing “specific policies and codes, with clear principles, and adopt procedures similar to those of the Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian – FCG, including them systematically in all contracts, by adapting the following clause: All contracts for scholarships, internships, volunteering, acquisition of goods, provision of services or allocation of subsidies, must include a clause establishing the right to terminate the agreement based on the breach of the FCG’s general principles

⁶¹ These measures and strategies will be commented on only briefly in this context, as the benchmark report mainly targets the state-of-the-art on policy development in ERA. Though, these results will be part of the work done in task 3.2 in GENDERACTIONplus, on developing a baseline document with measures and strategies for RFOs. This work is presented in deliverable D3.2 which is due in December 2023.

⁶² https://cdn.gulbenkian.pt/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Codigo_boa_conduta_prevencao_combate_assedio_trabalho_EN.pdf

regarding this subject matter”. The IRC mentions the importance of a follow-up on the recommendations given in the report from the national Irish HEI survey on sexual violence.

3.2.3.5. Concluding comments

It is important to acknowledge recent policy developments in some countries and regions (as in Belgium-FWB and Ireland, but also Portugal and Poland), as well as promising recent adoption of RFO policies on GBV (IRC, MCST, NFSR, UEFISCDI), but still there are no indications of a common approach throughout ERA on concepts, scope, relevance, use of GEPs, intersectional perspectives, or other possible synergies. Some countries and regions comment, in the benchmark survey responses in GENDERACTIONplus, on the possibilities to use the recent and upcoming developments on GEPs, where GBV currently is one out of five recommended thematic areas, as an important factor for policy development. A more holistic and inclusive notion on defining and combatting GBV will very likely depend on a coherent conceptual framework adopted in ERA and would also benefit from a decision to set eradicating GBV as a mandatory building block in GEPs.

This is all the more relevant to pinpoint in relation to the analysis of the use of a 7P-framework in UniSAFE, which illustrates several differences in how and which preventive mechanisms are emphasised in different countries and regions, and also that there is a lack of a systematically coherent policy discourse in ERA as such.⁶³ This is also why the UniSAFE project delivers assessment frameworks and indicators at both ERA- and RPO- levels, to support RPOs to take further steps and enable monitoring and evaluation.⁶⁴ In much the same spirit, upcoming work in the GENDERACTIONplus project will develop a baseline document on preventive strategies used, and planned to be used, by RFOs (WP3, task 3.2), and also a template on a zero-tolerance policy on GBV for RFOs and national authorities will be made available (WP3, task 3.3).

3.3. Policies targeting GBV in ERA

3.3.1. An overview of the findings

In this third part of the benchmark report results section, an analysis of the current *overall policy framework* on GBV in ERA is presented. It covers the general EU policy framework on GBV as well as certain policies targeting RFOs and RPOs more specifically. The inclusion of GBV in ERA priorities dates back several years, albeit as late as 2015 the Council Conclusions on Advancing Gender Equality in the European Research Area did not actively address the issue.⁶⁵ There are several important developments since then, but what is still lacking is a coherent analysis of the complete overall policy framework on ERA level targeting GBV.

Recent analyses of the policy development within national contexts have been undertaken in several projects. The national and institutional mapping of policy development on GBV in the UniSAFE project,⁶⁶ already referred to above, has to a great detail described and analysed the existence and

⁶³ UniSAFE 2021b,

⁶⁴ UniSAFE 2023.

⁶⁵ Also, cf the Council of the European Union 2015.

⁶⁶ UniSAFE 2021b, 2021c; cf Wroblewski 2018 for the broader GE framework.

content of different national and institutional policy frameworks. There are also several useful tools developed to enhance an overview of policy developments in this regard.⁶⁷

The results in this part of the benchmark report describe the following situation and challenges for the future:

- The ERA policy framework on GBV builds to a large extent on the principles and suggested strategies and measures developed in the Istanbul Convention.⁶⁸
- The ERA policy framework lacks a consistent overall structure. Instead, it is composed of divergent policies targeting different stakeholders with measures and strategies not always clearly aligned.
- The Ljubljana declaration on GE⁶⁹ has been widely endorsed by MS, whereas the Call for action on GBV⁷⁰ is as yet foremost adopted by specific ERA stakeholders.
- The urgent need for a data and monitoring framework on GBV on the ERA level is detected in the analysis, and suggestions for how to move forward on this important part of the ERA framework is suggested.
- Intersectionality is a cross-cutting priority in recent policy development on GBV in ERA, but there are still several aspects to develop further. Especially, an intersectional understanding of multiple oppressive forms of discrimination is still missing. Policy development moving beyond a simplistic version of discrimination and an additive model is suggested.

3.3.2. Policy framework on GBV for ERA

It can be difficult to find information on and keep track of the overall policy framework concerning GBV for national authorities, RFOs and RPOs in ERA. Therefore, a first short and descriptive overview is presented in table 13 on the main policies targeting GBV of relevance for ERA stakeholders. This will give insights on different policies from the viewpoint of main conceptual coverage, the level of endorsement, scope and relevance for national authorities, RPOs and RFOs, including also examples of core strategies and measures suggested. In particular sections below, a more nuanced discussion and analysis on specific themes of interest will follow.

Table 13. Overall policies on GBV relevant for ERA stakeholders, with an overview of content.

Policy	Content	Endorsement, scope and relevance for national authorities, RFOs, and RPOs in ERA	Strategies and measures of relevance for national authorities, RFOs, and RPOs in ERA
	Coverage of GBV and other forms of violence, harassment and discrimination, including intersectional perspectives on GBV		

⁶⁷ Please of the UniSAFE interactive map on legal and policy frameworks on GBV: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/map/>.

⁶⁸ Council of Europe 2014.

⁶⁹ Ljubljana Declaration 2021.

⁷⁰ Call for action 2022.

<p>Council of Europe. (2014). <i>Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence</i> (Council of Europe Treaty Series No 210). Istanbul: Council of Europe</p>	<p>Applies to all forms of violence against women, defined as violation of human rights and a form of discrimination against women and shall mean all acts of gender-based violence that result in, or are likely to result in, physical, sexual, psychological or economic harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life.</p> <p>Broad definition of GBV included covering most forms of violence hitherto defined in research.⁷¹</p> <p>Protective rights for victims must address discrimination on all grounds.</p> <p>Intersectionality is not used as a concept to define GBV.</p>	<p>Endorsed by all MS, ratified by 21 MS.⁷²</p> <p>Covering all areas of public and private life, in peace as in situations of armed conflict.</p> <p>Policy framework for national authorities and all public and private RFOs and RPOs in MS and beyond, but no specific mentioning of ERA stakeholders.</p>	<p>Implement gender-sensitive policies.</p> <p>Allocate appropriate financial and human resources for implementation.</p> <p>Support research in the field of all forms of violence.</p> <p>Prevent through changing social and cultural patterns, awareness-raising, education, training of professionals, intervention and treatment programmes</p> <p>Provide protection and support.</p> <p>Enable reporting.</p> <p>Adopt effective, proportionate and dissuasive sanctions against perpetrators.</p>
<p>EC. (2020). <i>A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025</i></p>	<p>Covering all forms of GBV as defined in co-existing policies.⁷³</p> <p>Intersectionality is used as a concept to define GE, but not directly linked to GBV. Mainly advocating an additive approach to gender and different grounds of discrimination.</p>	<p>Targeting all MS, and AC when relevant and covering all areas of public and private life.</p> <p>The policy framework also targets research and education in several ways. Describes foremost different GE initiatives concerning Horizon Europe, including Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).</p>	<p>GEPs to include measures combatting GBV as a suggested priority area.</p> <p>Funding for gender and intersectional research will be made available.</p>

⁷¹ Cf UniSAFE 2021a for an extensive discussion on the concept of GBV for ERA stakeholders.

⁷² As documented per Dec 2022: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-area-of-justice-and-fundamental-rights/file-eu-accession-to-the-istanbul-convention>.

⁷³ Cf Council of Europe 2014; ILO 2019.

<p>EC. (2022). <i>Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence</i></p>	<p>Covering all forms of GBV as defined in co-existing policies.⁷⁴</p> <p>Focus on sexual and other forms of harassment at work is pronounced.</p> <p>Mainly advocating an additive approach to gender and different grounds of discrimination, coined as intersecting discrimination.</p>	<p>Targeting all MS, and AC when relevant.</p> <p>Covering all areas of public and private life.</p> <p>Policy framework set to enhance already agreed upon statutes, mainly addressing the need to sharpen legislative and preventive mechanisms.</p> <p>No specific concern targeting ERA RFOs and RPOs directly.</p>	<p>Preventive measures shall include awareness-raising campaigns, research and education programmes, incentives for early detection of violence and abuse, where appropriate developed in cooperation with relevant civil society organisations, social partners, impacted communities and other stakeholders</p> <p>Cyberviolence and sexual harassment at work are priority areas for national legislation</p> <p>System to be put in place for the collection, development, production, and dissemination of statistics on violence against women or domestic violence on MS level. Coordination body set up by EIGE 2025-2026.</p> <p>Support research on root causes, effects, incidences, and conviction rates of the forms of violence mentioned in the directive.</p>
<p>Council of Europe. (2018). <i>Gender Equality Strategy 2018-2023</i></p>	<p>Covering all forms of GBV as defined in co-existing policies.⁷⁵</p> <p>Intersectional discrimination as main concept used, but also intersectionality addressed as a transversal issue across the priority</p>	<p>Adopted by the Committee of Ministers and valid for all of the 47 Member States of the Council of Europe.⁷⁶</p> <p>No specific concern targeting ERA RFOs and RPOs directly.</p>	<p>Similar objectives and strategies as Council of Europe (2014).</p> <p>Support MS to actively implement the CEDAW,⁷⁷ including rec no. 35 on GBV, updating rec no. 19, as well as Agenda 2030 SDGs 5 and 16.</p>

⁷⁴ Cf Council of Europe 2014; ILO 2019.

⁷⁵ Cf Council of Europe 2018; ILO 2019.

⁷⁶ As documented per 7th of March 2018: <https://epws.org/gender-equality-strategy-2018-2023/>.

⁷⁷ UN 1979.

	objectives, including combatting GBV.		
ILO. (2019). <i>Violence and Harassment Convention, 2019 (No. 190)</i>	<p>Using the combined concept of GBV and sexual harassment as causing physical, psychological, sexual or economic harm.</p> <p>Advocating an additive approach to gender and different grounds of discrimination.</p> <p>Risks of GBV seen as part of intersecting discrimination and unequal gender-based power relations.</p>	<p>Ratified by 25 countries globally and within ERA so far by Greece, Ireland, Italy and Spain.⁷⁸</p> <p>Including all workers and other persons in the world of work, but without mentioning of ERA RFOs and RPOs directly.</p>	<p>Similar objectives and strategies as Council of Europe (2014).</p> <p>Demands policies ensuring the right to equality and non-discrimination in employment and occupation, including for women workers, as well as for workers and other persons belonging to one or more vulnerable groups or groups in situations of vulnerability that are disproportionately affected by violence and harassment in the world of work.</p>
EC. (2021). <i>European Research Area Policy Agenda</i>	<p>Using the combined concept of GBV and sexual harassment, but without further definition.</p> <p>Target inclusiveness and intersections with other diversity categories and potential grounds for discrimination, such as ethnicity, disability, or sexual orientation.</p>	<p>Includes all ERA member states.</p> <p>Priority 5 especially concern GE, and in some parts also GBV.</p> <p>Builds almost exclusively on the Ljubljana Declaration. (2021).</p> <p>Targets ERA RFOs and RPOs directly with perceived outcomes.</p>	<p>GEPs to include measures combatting GBV as a suggested priority area.</p> <p>An outcome will be a strategy to counteract GBV including sexual harassment in the European R&I system and to assure gender equal and inclusive working environments through institutional change in any RPO or RFO.</p>
Ljubljana Declaration. (2021). <i>Gender Equality in</i>	Uses GBV and sexual harassment, without further definition.	Endorsed by 38 MS & AC and the EC. ⁷⁹	GBV to be included as part of data collection practices for She Figures.

⁷⁸ As displayed online by ILO Normlex per March 2023:

https://www.ilo.org/dyn/normlex/en/f?p=1000:11300:14910219869805:::P11300_INSTRUMENT_SORT:1

⁷⁹ As detailed in the call for action document per Nov 26th 2021:

https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MIZS/Dokumenti/PSEU/Ljubljana-Declaration-on-Gender-Equality-in-Research-and-Innovation- endorsed_final.pdf.

<p><i>Research and Innovation.</i></p>	<p>Intersectionality is not used as a concept to define GBV.</p>	<p>Targets ERA RFOs and RPOs directly with perceived outcomes.</p>	<p>GBV as a thematic area to be addressed in GEPs. A request for additional policy coordination and action from RFOs, RPOs and other relevant stakeholders in ERA.</p>
<p><i>Call for Action (2022). Working towards Safe and Respectful Higher Education and Research for All. Call for Action to End Gender Based Violence.</i></p>	<p>GBV used and defined in line with an inclusive research-based understanding as developed in UniSAFE.⁸⁰ Strong declaration on intersecting inequalities as paramount for all actions.</p>	<p>Endorsed by two MS and 49 ERA stakeholders.⁸¹ Targets ERA RFOs and RPOs directly with perceived outcomes.</p>	<p>Detailed description of several directed targets and measures, on both institutional and structural level, targeting RFOs, RPOs, MS and the EC respectively.⁸²</p>

Reading through the overall policies on GBV in Table 13, with relevance for ERA national authorities, RFOs and RPOs, it is clear this framework consists of a web of both overlapping and specific demands on combatting GBV. Several policies address concepts, aims, strategies and outputs from other policies, yet sometimes the opposite is true as some policies instead develop their own measures not addressed beforehand. Further, the uses of concepts on GBV are diverse, not aligned throughout the policy framework, nor defined to the extent it is possible to use a coherent understanding of what is at stake. This holds true also for the diverse degrees to which different policies are endorsed, adopted and ratified by MS and other groups of countries and/or stakeholders.

The analysis of the proposed measures and strategies in detail renders it obvious that many of them are identical all the way through the overall policy framework – as, for example, with the use of gender-sensitive approaches, adopting preventive measures protecting victims of GBV, and fostering legal requirements to be set or adopted in different ways – whereas other such interventions are unique for single policies, often embedded in detailed paragraphs. It can of course make it all too complex, and almost impenetrable, for single national authorities, RFOs or RPOs to keep track of what is demanded, at least without strong commitment and enough expert knowledge and other dedicated resources. Thus, **the urgent need for a coherent overview and accessible overall policy framework for ERA stakeholders is obvious**, which describes compulsory strategies and outcomes as well as voluntary measures. Table 13 can serve as a starting point for further development of both

⁸⁰ UniSAFE 2021a.

⁸¹ As documented per Feb 23rd 2023: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1h-lqghs9tNyTwXSOHS-DeM9jKGUnMVjG8kZpiAp4jf4/edit#gid=0>.

⁸² The actions proposed are not described at length, please cf the call itself for more details. In section 4.2 below, the content of the call is discussed further as a stepping stone for an infrastructure for change.

a coherent ERA framework (as outlined as an outcome from EC 2021), and a forthcoming tool that is applicable for ERA stakeholders.

A final overall remark concerns the analytical perspectives adopted in several policies, describing the reasons why GBV persists, also detailing different risk factors, structural conditions, unequal power relations, and other important aspects. This is a crucial part of understanding the reach and impact of GBV on individual, institutional and societal levels, not the least pertaining to ERA stakeholder responsibilities, as: “asymmetric power relations, hierarchies, ageism, nepotism, and secondary victimisation (such as victim blaming or discounting of experiences of violence) often make it impossible for people, mostly women, who are experiencing gender-based violence to speak up or take action against the perpetrator of the violence.”⁸³

In the following paragraphs, two important aspects are analysed in more detail – data and monitoring on GBV, and the use of different notions of intersectionality – with comments on best practice and recommended ways forward.

3.3.3. Data and monitoring

As formulated by the EC, data and monitoring on the prevalence and consequences of GBV will have to be developed by all MS.⁸⁴ EU-wide policy analysis⁸⁵ clearly demonstrate a general lack of a coherent monitoring framework, regular data collection and measures to prevent GBV in ERA. The most common indicators on GBV already in place in ERA RPOs target the number of reported cases of GBV. However, these indicators on prevalence are likely to underestimate prevalence due to severe underreporting, as described in both policy analysis and research.⁸⁶ Further, national survey data on prevalence of GBV in RPOs in MS is scarce. Only Ireland⁸⁷ and Sweden⁸⁸ benefit from survey data on a national level, albeit not covering all forms of GBV.

The to date most reliable survey data compilation on GBV in all its forms in ERA RPOs is the UniSAFE survey, covering 15 MS and 46 RPOs in total. The results from this cross-context survey – despite a low response rate and not covering all forms of RPOs and countries – clearly demonstrate the current levels of GBV. Two out of three respondents have experienced some form of GBV during their time as students or staff. Psychological violence (57 percent) and sexual harassment (31 percent) are the main experiences reported.⁸⁹

More general policy frameworks outside of ERA are under development at the moment. Both indicators and monitoring devices on GBV for the EU are already put in place through the 2007 initiative taken by the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) to UN Women, the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) and Eurostat. Currently, EU GBV indicators are being refined⁹⁰ and will establish new data on prevalence in the EU27 by the end of 2023. The EC will also

⁸³ Ljubljana Declaration 2021, p. 1.

⁸⁴ EC 2022.

⁸⁵ SWG GRI 2020; UniSAFE 2021b, 2021c.

⁸⁶ UN 2017; UniSAFE 2021a; Walby et al. 2017.

⁸⁷ McNeela et al. 2022.

⁸⁸ KI 2022.

⁸⁹ Lipinsky et al 2022.

⁹⁰ Eurostat 2021.

set a standard for data and monitoring to be upheld by MS, and a coordinating function run by EIGE starting from 2025-2026.⁹¹ An initiative of corresponding scope and relevance is lacking in the ERA.

In sum, the importance of collecting and monitoring data on prevalence of GBV in ERA is crucial to enable prevention on institutional levels. Overall, though, analysing the existing policy framework in detail as listed in Table 13, there is no clear commitment on the *institutional level* to pursue survey or administrative data collection on GBV, nor setting up systems on *ERA level* for monitoring and evaluation of progress in combatting GBV. This further confirms the analysis already undertaken in the UniSAFE project on this issue,⁹² in which an assessment framework on GBV for RPOs is under way.⁹³

3.3.4. Intersectionality

Analysing the overall policy framework on GBV in ERA, several relevant aspects are worth mentioning in relation to the use of intersectionality. What is evident is a reluctance to take a clear stance of both the definition and importance of integrating an intersectional perspective in policies targeting GBV. There are also several different concepts used, without clear definitions and alignment to research or co-existing policies. For instance, “intersecting discrimination” is used in parallel to “discrimination on several grounds” (EC 2021), but without clarifying the baseline understanding of in what way these concepts actually target identified inequalities and in what way this enables progress in combatting specific minorities experiences of injustices and different forms of GBV. A more elaborate example can shed some light on what is at stake.

The EC Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 claims intersectionality to be a cross-cutting principle in all its measures. At the same time, when reading more closely, it advocates an ambivalent understanding of the concept of intersectionality. That is, on the one hand it is claiming a research-based understanding of intersecting inequalities (by quoting EIGE), but at the same time primarily uses only an additive approach. This latter approach means mentioning a list of grounds for discrimination, counting the various forms, and then arguing for the way they can add up to more severe consequences. This is not an example of applying an intersectional approach, which would mean to describe and analyse *how* and *for whom* different inequalities and power regimes reinforce each other and *when* they are especially relevant for combatting GBV.

This additive approach is also evident in other concepts used by the EC, for example in the way the policy defines the inclusion of other categories beyond gender. The policy aims at inclusion of people “in all their diversity”, as a main point of departure for how to interpret intersectionality: “The expression ‘in all their diversity’ is used in this strategy to express that, where women or men are mentioned, these are a heterogeneous categories including in relation to their sex, gender identity, gender expression or sex characteristics. It affirms the commitment to leave no one behind and achieve a gender equal Europe for everyone, regardless of their sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation.”⁹⁴

⁹¹ EC 2021.

⁹² UniSAFE 2021b, 2021c.

⁹³ UniSAFE 2023.

⁹⁴ EC 2020, p 2, note 9.

The EU gender equality policy paradigm of “inclusiveness”, emanating from an additive approach to the idea of intersectionality, is also clearly manifested in other policies, as presented in Table 13 above. This can be set in contrast to some of the policies moving further on defining and identifying the intersectional consequences of GBV in several ways, such as defining “multiple and intersecting forms of discrimination, and unequal gender-based power relations” and arguing for an understanding of it being “essential to ending violence and harassment in the world of work”.⁹⁵ Further, the importance of pinpointing specific vulnerable groups in this respect is also evident in a few of the analysed policies: “the urgent needs of disadvantaged and marginalised groups of women such as women migrants, refugees and asylum seekers, women drug users, women with diverse sexual orientations and gender identities, Roma women, require targeted policies and activities to address the violence they are confronted with.”⁹⁶

The same aspect is important to recognise in the context of R&I, where it is clearly stated that the persistence of GBV: “drives women, including women in vulnerable situations affected by other inequalities (age, sexism in the workplace, disabilities, marginalised backgrounds, instability, non-normative gender identities and sexual orientations etc.) and persons with non-normative gender identities and sexual orientations – out of academia and research.”⁹⁷

In sum, the ambition to be inclusive, to set forth an agenda where discrimination on several different grounds is identified and included, is an important step forward in terms of policy development on GE, especially in the context of ERA. But there are still further steps to take, mainly adopting an intersectional approach as defined in research, meaning **not to let go of the way multiple inequalities and power regimes create complex challenges and unique consequences of GBV for specific vulnerable groups**. This development is clearly under way, as pronounced in both calls for action on GBV in ERA (Ljubljana Declaration 2021; Call for Action 2022), but it has not made an impact on the broader overall policy framework for ERA yet.

⁹⁵ ILO 2019, preamble.

⁹⁶ Council of Europe 2018, p. 21.

⁹⁷ Ljubljana Declaration 2021, p. 1.

4. Summary and recommendations

4.1. Overall summary of results

A complete summary of the main results from the benchmark report analysis is described below.

4.1.1. Research review on GBV in HE

- The research described in the global section, heavily dominated by the USA, and the research described in the ERA, differ in terms of content and thematic focus. For instance, bystander initiatives are frequently examined in the included research reviews, but only represented in one of the included ERA articles. Another thematic difference is the focus on prevention and prevalence in the reviews, while the ERA articles to a higher degree focus on relationship violence between students.
- Another gap identified specifically in the ERA material is that between the strong focus on students' experiences of GBV and its weak relation to development of HE infrastructures for prevention of GBV. Many of the articles focus on students in different ways, such as examining students' relations, experiences, behaviours, and predictors in relation to GBV. The generated knowledge in these studies is only to a small extent included in research on policy development. This results in a gap between students' lived experiences of GBV and the development of HE institutions' preventive work.
- A clear gap in the overall material regards sample. An absolute majority of the included research focus on students as a sample, and very few studies focus on staff in HE specifically, and not one identified article or review focus on doctoral students.
- Samples predominantly consist of majority group students. The lack of diversity and intersectional perspectives is a clear gap in the overall material, with the obvious exception of the specific search on intersectionality.
- The search on intersectionality can be categorised into two parts: Around half of the articles discuss individual experiences and prevalence of GBV in HE from an intersectional perspective as a way of building more inclusive knowledge. The other half focus on intersectionality as a tool for change. The institutional and structural levels of HE are analysed through an intersectional lens in different ways.
- Research Funding Organisations are a central part of the HE infrastructure, yet there is a complete lack of research on RFOs in regard to GBV in HE.
- Findings regarding the conceptual framework and methodology in this material confirm previous research results. Use of a wide range of scales, surveys and methodologies results in a variety of measures and numbers to describe GBV in HE. This in combination of the broad conceptual framework and varied definitions of GBV makes comparisons between studies and contexts challenging.

4.1.2. Policy analysis – national and regional level

- None out of the 15 countries or regions participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey has a national or regional policy against GBV in RFOs in place.
- None out of the 15 countries or regions participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey has a policy against GBV in RFOs in place which includes measures for RFOs.
- Only two out of 15 responding partners (Belgium-FWB, Ireland) in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have a national or regional policy against GBV in place for RFOs.
- Concepts used in policies are left undefined and mainly cover either some forms of GBV or only SH and discrimination.
- An intersectional approach is missing throughout the analysed policy documents, with the single exception of Ireland where especially the national framework policy takes important steps towards making visible and using an intersectional lens in its aims and strategies.

4.1.3. Policy analysis – research funding organisations

- Five out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have developed policies on GBV since 1 May 2021.
- One out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have measures targeting applicants.
- Three out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have indicated funding priorities in GBV.
- Two out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have responded there has been recent policy developments targeting the safety of researchers.
- Two out of 20 RFOs participating in the GENDERACTIONplus survey have responded there are procedures for information on GBV misconduct by PIs or researchers and procedures for sanctions.

4.1.4. Policy analysis – overall ERA framework on GBV

- The ERA policy framework on GBV builds to a large extent on the principles and suggested strategies and measures developed in the Istanbul Convention.⁹⁸
- The ERA policy framework lacks a consistent overall structure. Instead, it is composed of divergent policies targeting different stakeholders with measures and strategies not always clearly aligned.

⁹⁸ Council of Europe 2014.

- The Ljubljana Declaration on GE⁹⁹ has been widely endorsed by MS, whereas the Call for action on GBV¹⁰⁰ is as yet foremost adopted by specific ERA stakeholders.
- The urgent need for a data and monitoring framework on GBV on the ERA level is detected in the analysis, and suggestions for how to move forward on this important part of the ERA framework is suggested.
- Intersectionality is a cross-cutting priority in recent EU policy development on GBV in the ERA, but there are still several aspects to develop further. Especially, an intersectional understanding of multiple oppressive forms of discrimination is still missing. Policy development moving beyond a simplistic version of discrimination and an additive model is suggested.

4.2. Recommendations

This benchmark report concludes by setting a new level of ambition in combatting GBV in the ERA. The reason for this is quite simple. Ending GBV has long been pronounced as an important issue in the overall ERA policy framework. It is a key area of the EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025. Since 1979, targeted measures and strategies to eradicate all forms of violence against women are set as core principles for almost all MS through the Istanbul Convention. The systematic mission to eradicate GBV more broadly dates back, at least, to the first and second wave of women's liberation movements globally. Still, actual change has barely begun, if at all, especially not in the ERA.

As researchers and analysts writing this report, we have reflected continuously on the various policies, research results, aims and measures produced and proposed in EU27 and beyond, being aware of what is suggested is mainly concepts, strategies and practices already tried out in the Nordic context for decades – without any measurable results. Still, this is what is being sought for by MS both in EU14 and EU13 countries; to imitate the notion of “best practices”, which have not proven to be best at all.¹⁰¹ #Metoo did occur, in some respect, due to a change being under way, but it was and still is a poignant example of the inability of our age to foster structural, institutional and cultural change.

Overall, what is in place is a few ambitious and productive EU-funded projects, a handful but important national or regional developments of laws and policies, an overall ERA policy framework with the recent GEP requirement promoting GBV as one of several possible priority areas for ERA stakeholders, some pioneering research studies on GBV and HE lately, as well as other developments described in this as well as other similar reports – all running the risk of ending up repeating old strategies already tested and failed. Despite good intentions and strong advocates for change on all levels, working tirelessly to make things happen, the *current lack of a systemic infrastructure for change* allows the fight against GBV in the ERA to remain a minor, marginal, underfinanced, unknowledgeable issue.

⁹⁹ Ljubljana Declaration 2021.

¹⁰⁰ Call for action 2022.

¹⁰¹ This conclusion has strong support from an immense research review on global research on SH in HEI concluding the lack of any international research evidence on the function of the hitherto used preventive measures (Bondestam & Lundqvist 2019). Although it might feel negative to claim the failure of the up until now used strategies and measures, it is actually, on the contrary, what is the most hopeful and positive – to acknowledge failure is a crucial way to mobilize the will to enable new ways of thinking and acting.

This is what is at stake, no less, as the current status quo prevails at the expense of the lives and bodies of a majority of women, minorities and some men, and with severe consequences for the quality of research and education throughout the ERA.¹⁰² The definition of the situation must change. Existing forms of financing education and research need to be fundamentally re-evaluated and reorganised. At this point it is necessary to imagine the unthinkable as the only possible way forward: RPOs in ERA completely free from GBV, the much longed-for code of conduct setting zero-tolerance not just as a goal but a fact, imply new and bold ways of thinking and doing.

The most recent “Call for action”, adopted by the Czech Presidency of the Council of the EU in November 2022, sets ambitious aims and measures for ERA stakeholders on all levels. It suggests several important developments to actually enable a code of conduct on, or zero-tolerance of, GBV in all its forms throughout the ERA. It argues for a new momentum, with an intersectional perspective, defining ending GBV as “a crucial aspect of reclaiming core academic principles of scientific quality, meritocracy, research integrity and academic freedom”.¹⁰³ Although not adopted by more than four MS, though by a fairly large group of different ERA stakeholders, it points towards a *collaborative responsibility* among all relevant partners.

This is an important development, as it does not claim the sole and full responsibility of RPOs for academic cultures. It does not point at RFOs to possess some unforeseen, magic ability to foster bold strategies for change through financial incentives. It also avoids the classic mistake of only calling out for more, better (or any at all) legal structures put in place, so as to guarantee formal justice (but as if often the case, without any real impact on the institutional level). Finally, a collaborative responsibility avoids the tendency to define the problem of GBV as an individual, situational, single event to be dealt with when it already has occurred (indeed, it is important to deal with such events as well, claiming accountability of perpetrators and supporting victims), instead claiming the need for systematic, institutional change so these events do not take place at all.

For some MS it is of course almost impossible to even imagine being critical of the long hoped for development of a law or policy on GBV of any kind, due to the lack of such measures in the first place. Likewise, MS with a long history of GE policies, and seemingly highly developed strategies and measures for combatting GBV, are more often than not reluctant to acknowledge GBV is ongoing¹⁰⁴ The need to overcome these lock-in effects is urgent.

All this being said, what is proposed here is *an infrastructure for systematic change making it possible for ERA stakeholders to take on the collaborative responsibility asked for in recent policies on GBV in ERA.* In Figure 5 below, a summary of a coherent infrastructure is described, presenting key components of an overall engagement and responsibilities for different stakeholders, enabling zero-tolerance of GBV in ERA¹⁰⁵ in all dimensions. It is a new level of ambition for all ERA stakeholders ensuring the development and organisation of sustained structures for monitoring and evaluation, funding schemes on research, relevant support, and effective measures for accountability.

¹⁰² Cf Anitha & Lewis 2018 for a more elaborate discussion.

¹⁰³ Call for Action 2022.

¹⁰⁴ Research on a “Nordic paradox” is still under way, though often pointing at men’s violence against women being more, or at least as, prevalent in Nordic countries as in other regions, even after controlling for different relevant factors (cf for example Gracia et al 2019; Humbert et al 2021).

¹⁰⁵ As suggested in the Call for Action 2022.

Figure 5. ERA infrastructure for systematic change through collaborative responsibility.

ERA INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SYSTEMATIC CHANGE THROUGH COLLABORATIVE RESPONSIBILITY				
Stakeholder engagement	EU RESPONSIBILITY Financing, developing and organising preventive, ERA-common nodes supporting zero-tolerance to GBV in RPOs	NATIONAL RESPONSIBILITY Organising sustainable systems for monitoring and evaluation, funding, support and sanctions on a national level	RFO RESPONSIBILITY Organising sustainable systems for data collection, funding, support and sanctions targeting national RPOs	RPO RESPONSIBILITY Organising sustainable systems for data collection, funding, support and sanctions at the institutional level
Data & statistics	Monitoring and evaluation of national GEP commitment to eradicate GBV, ensuring full 7P coverage and progress, and implementing new ERA indicators	Monitoring and evaluation of institutional GEP commitment to eradicate GBV, ensuring full 7P coverage and progress, using new ERA indicators.	Collecting & analysing data on GBV, ensuring full 7P coverage and progress, especially targeting conditions for and consequences of research funding schemes	Collecting & analysing data on GBV, ensuring full 7P coverage and progress, building sustainable structures for internal monitoring in line with new ERA indicators
Research & innovation	Funding knowledge production & dissemination through research on GBV, RPOs, organisational change, and the implementation of the 7Ps	Funding knowledge production & dissemination through research on GBV, RPOs, organisational change, and the implementation of the 7Ps	Funding knowledge production & dissemination through research on GBV, RPOs, organisational change, and the implementation of the 7Ps	2. Funding knowledge production & dissemination through research on GBV, RPOs, organisational change, and the implementation of the 7Ps
Support structures	Provision of services acknowledging a survivor-centered approach, independent of ERA RPOs, enhancing national and institutional responsibilities	Provision of services acknowledging a survivor-centered approach, independent of RFOs and RPOs, enhancing institutional responsibilities	Provision of services acknowledging a survivor-centered approach, independent of RPOs, targeting applicants and recipients of research funding	Provision of services acknowledging a survivor-centered approach, targeting staff and students with ongoing primary, secondary and tertiary measures
Systematic liability	Incentives & sanctions using both academic and financial measures targeting national authorities, RFOs and RPOs in line with an ERA code of conduct	Incentives & sanctions using both academic and financial measures targeting RFOs and RPOs in line with an ERA code of conduct	Incentives & sanctions using both academic and financial measures targeting RPOs and individual researchers in line with an ERA code of conduct	Incentives & sanctions using both academic and financial measures targeting staff and students in line with an ERA code of conduct

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The infrastructure displayed in Figure 5 is a vital step towards transforming ERA stakeholder engagement on implementing relevant practices ending GBV.

We suggest an overall responsibility of the EU to develop, finance and implement four different ERA common nodes – on *data and statistics*, *research and innovation*, *support structures*, and *systematic liability*. These nodes are to be run by the EU and preferably organised as independent mechanisms with sufficient long-term funding and a strong commitment and representation from MS experts. The ERA common nodes are to be aligned with a development of corresponding elements by engaged stakeholders on the national level in MS (national authorities), as well as by individual RFOs and RPOs. The commitment in national contexts will differ, partly depending on the level of advancement in terms of GE and experiences of striving towards ending GBV. The ERA common nodes are, on the EU level, mainly suggested here as *supportive structures* in a common quest for managing systemic change throughout ERA, but on this level, it will also be important to take on the responsibility for *monitoring and evaluation* of progress in ending GBV in RPOs.

The four ERA common nodes are chosen based on knowledge emanating from the analysis in this benchmark report, from the experiences of the UniSAFE project, output from other EU-funded as well as other projects, and finally (and mainly) building on the experiences of a long-term commitment within the Nordic context of developing targeted measures ending GBV in RPOs since at least the early 1980s. Further, these specific nodes are as such interlinked throughout all stakeholder levels – that is they are interconnected between the EU, national contexts, RFOs and RPOs. Set up only on one level will not be sufficient, as it underestimates the continuous lack of engagement, support, funding, and structures needed for sustained change. Finally, the four suggested nodes are also interconnected with each other. *Data and statistics* are fundamental parts of making empirical *research and innovation* possible, without which targeted *support structures* will be ineffective (or even counterproductive), and finally none of these nodes are implemented successfully without a clearly defined and *systematic liability* for stakeholders on all levels.

Each ERA common node is described in more detail in the following sections.

- (a) *Data and statistics*. The lack of coherent data and systems for monitoring and evaluation on GBV in ERA is evident, without which measuring progress in ending GBV in RPOs will not be possible and research and innovation initiatives will run short. The collection of administrative and survey data has to be set in relation to the relevance of monitoring especially. This implies a corresponding set of practices connecting all stakeholder levels, starting out with EU developing new ERA indicators on GBV. Then national authorities, RFOs and RPOs will have to align with these indicators when developing systems for collecting specific data, targeting their respective purpose, scope and responsibility. A first set of relevant indicators on GBV, possible to use for ERA overall monitoring, and throughout the chain of stakeholders, are already being developed as part of the output from the ongoing UniSAFE project.¹⁰⁶
- (b) *Research and innovation*. As displayed in this benchmark report research review, there are significant gaps in research on GBV in ERA. This is confirmed more generally by previous research reviews as referred beforehand. Without relevant, research-based knowledge perspectives, ideas, measures and strategies on combatting GBV, it will be difficult to transform the current situation in ERA RPOs. Therefore, a common responsibility on all

¹⁰⁶ EUROSTAT are developing new indicators on IPV for the EU in collaboration with EIGE, and these are of course relevant to incorporate when relevant.

stakeholder levels is to define, fund, and disseminate research results. The EU is obliged to enlarge the commitment of research funding through Horizon Europe and an upcoming revision of the ERA framework for research funding as such. On the national level, funding initiatives targeting generic challenges identified in national R&I is necessary. RFOs are foremost responsible for funding schemes developed in dialogue with national stakeholders, identifying relevant knowledge gaps and challenges to be addressed. Finally, RPOs have a responsibility to secure the independent development of research on GBV, mainly through internal mechanisms in place (targeted areas for institutional development, internal funding mechanisms, supporting the development of networks and collaboration on different relevant topics, etc).

- (c) *Support structures.* There is strong research evidence on the low number of formal reports of abuse and violations in RPOs, in contrast to the actual reported incidence of GBV. Provision of services within a specific RPO in ERA is generally underestimated, underfinanced, and also lacking other relevant resources and funding. Long-term research knowledge on the experienced lack of reparation among survivors of GBV clearly shows the general lack of knowledge, resources, measures and perspectives necessary. Supporting survivors is one of the main aspects of tertiary prevention, which also need to include bystanders and even perpetrators, but this is seldom the case.¹⁰⁷ By developing support structures on all stakeholder levels, it will be possible to ensure a more thorough and inclusive process of provision of services for survivors, bystanders and perpetrators. Foremost, generic knowledge, strategies, measures, and relevant resources can be developed on the EU level as well as on the national level, ensuring adequate support independent of both RFOs and RPOs. In turn, the latter stakeholders can implement relevant resources as needed to complement and enrich institutional measures.
- (d) *Systematic liability.* Developing an ERA common code of conduct will be necessary to ensure necessary incentives and sanctions to deploy throughout the different levels of stakeholder engagement. Legal sanctions will of course be mainly developed within national contexts, due to the existence of different legal amendments in MS. What is suggested here, though, is a code of conduct comprised of a *common academic protocol defining relevant, sufficient and necessary sanctions and incentives* on eradicating GBV, to be used in an equivalent manner throughout ERA. Imagine a Bologna charter or even a Magna Charta on eradicating GBV, thus. This code of conduct is the natural output from the ongoing policy discourse in ERA on a so called zero-tolerance approach, which will only be realised in its full potential when set as an ERA common code of conduct *developed by and for RPOs*. This will no doubt need to entail strong commitment by different stakeholders, but especially by RPO representatives from all fields of research (and education), so as to also enable a code of conduct *which in itself will strengthen academic and institutional freedom* (rather than run the risk of counteracting such freedoms).

In sum then, the suggested infrastructure in Figure 5 demands extensive funding in all its parts, and a considerable amount of time and resources invested on all stakeholder levels. However, the current

¹⁰⁷ Bondestam & Lundqvist 2019.

estimated cost of GBV against women in the EU is set to approximately 290 billion EUR per year.¹⁰⁸ The suggested infrastructure will barely entail a discernible fraction of this cost. The amount of engagement, time, expertise and professional development ensuring the full functioning of the infrastructure is still immense. It is necessary to ensure the development and sustained functioning of several different structures for monitoring, evaluation, funding, support and incentives for holding national, institutional and individual actors accountable for GBV. Establishing a monitoring and evaluation framework for ERA as such – with indicators on GBV used and analysed on all stakeholder levels, as well as functional survey and administration data collecting procedures on institutional and national levels – is of course challenging. But without statistics it will be fruitless to try to ensure progress in eliminating GBV in the ERA.

What is all the more important to recognise is the strength of the EU level incentives and structural measures for setting a code of conduct with common demands on liability and accountability for stakeholders on all levels – developed by and for academics. This will be decisive for moving the policy agenda fast forward in EU13 MS, on their own terms, as the responsibilities for developing structures and measures are a joint responsibility which implies acceptance of national and regional differences. It will also be crucial for EU14 MS, as yet not delivering incentives ending GBV in their national R&I systems, although the level of investments in GE is higher.

All in all, the suggested infrastructure is not an issue of if and how – it merely suggests a minimum level of decency and commitment needed to eradicate GBV in ERA.

¹⁰⁸ EIGE 2021, p. 22, table 12.

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ANNEXES

Appendix A – Systematic research review, search process in detail

General

The assignment was to conduct a research review on the current research, hence a time period of 2017-2022 was established. No geographical limitations were used for the search, but only peer reviewed articles published in English were included.

All posts were embedded and made accessible for the authors of the report in Rayyan, an online research collaboration platform.

Delimitations of search terms

At an early stage in the search process, a multitude of different search terms were identified to capture gender-based violence and Higher Education. The search terms were organized in three blocks to make sure to include relevant articles focusing on both GBV and HE, but to exclude irrelevant articles on for example 'gun violence in HE' or 'gender related violence in the fishing industry'. The search string also included 'NOT (child* OR school*)' to exclude the big research field focusing on children and primary education.

Databases used as sources for the assignment

The multi-disciplinary databases Web of Science and Scopus.

Search string

(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Gender based" OR "Gender coded" OR "Gender related" OR sexual* OR gender* OR intersect* OR minorit* OR diversity OR diverse OR inclusion* OR inclusiv* OR rape OR "violence against women") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (violence OR violent OR harass* OR abuse OR abusive OR assault* OR offence OR rape OR stalking OR stalker) AND (TITLE (universit* OR college* OR campus OR academ* OR "Higher education" OR rpo OR "research performing organi*" OR rfo OR "research funding organi*" OR "European research area") OR KEY (universit* OR college* OR campus OR academ* OR "Higher education" OR rpo OR "research performing organi*" OR rfo OR "research funding organi*" OR "European research area")) AND NOT (child*)) AND PUBYEAR > 2016 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")

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Appendix B – Research review publications, 2017-2022

No.	References	Scope Number of included articles (=N) Country The frame of reviewed articles	Abstract	Keywords
1	<p>Anderson, R.A.E. <i>et al.</i> (2021) "The Frequency of Sexual Perpetration in College Men: A Systematic Review of Reported Prevalence Rates From 2000 to 2017," <i>Trauma, Violence, & Abuse</i>, 22(3), pp. 481–495.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838019860619</p>	<p>N=77 US and Canada 2000-2017</p>	<p>Background: The prevalence of sexual perpetration in college men is unknown. Prior reviews of sexual violence prevalence rates have produced wide-ranging estimates, likely due to wide variation in measurement strategies.</p> <p>Objectives: This article systematically reviewed research findings (from 2000 to 2017) regarding prevalence rates of sexual perpetration in college men and measurement strategies.</p> <p>Data Sources: PsycINFO and Web of Science databases.</p> <p>Eligibility Criteria: Empirical reports published between 2000 and 2017 that included male participants, available in English, and reported lifetime prevalence findings in Canadian or American college students.</p> <p>Participants: Data from 78 independent samples including 25,524 college men.</p> <p>Results: The average prevalence rate of any sexual perpetration was 29.3% (SD%46.8), and the average rate of rape was 6.5%(SD%6.3). Studies that used non-Sexual Experiences Survey (SES)–based questionnaires recorded higher prevalence rates (41.5%) than SES-using studies (26.2%). At least 16 different sexual perpetration questionnaires were identified. Modifying standardized questionnaires was extremely common; this was reported in over half of the studies. Studies using modified standardized questionnaires found higher prevalence rates of sexual perpetration than studies using nonmodified standardized questionnaires.</p> <p>Limitations: This report focused exclusively on college men in the United States and Canada. Conclusions and Implications: On average, 29% of college males report engaging in behaviors defined as sexual perpetration; however, there was a strong influence of measurement strategy on reported rates.</p>	<p><i>Sexual perpetration; sexual aggression; sexual coercion; campus sexual assault; measurement; assessment; prevalence; rape</i></p>
2	<p>Bondestam, F. and Lundqvist, M. (2020) "Sexual harassment in higher education - a systematic review," <i>European journal of higher education</i>, 10(4), pp. 397–419.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/21568235.2020.1729833</p>	<p>N= 802 Global search, mainly results from the US 1966-2017</p>	<p>Sexual harassment is an epidemic throughout global higher education systems and impact individuals, groups and entire organizations in profound ways. Precarious working conditions, hierarchical organizations, a normalization of gender-based violence, toxic academic masculinities, a culture of silence and a lack of active leadership are all key features enabling sexual harassment. The aim of this study is to review scientific knowledge on sexual harassment in higher education. A thematic focus is on (a) knowledge derived from top-ranked peer-reviewed articles in the research field, (b) the prevalence of sexual harassment among students and staff, (c) reported consequences of sexual harassment, (d) examples of primary, secondary and tertiary preventive measures, and (e) core challenges to research on sexual harassment in higher education. The published research evidence suggests several findings of importance, mainly: (a) prevalence of sexual harassment among students is reported by on average one out of four female students; (b) severe consequences of sexual harassment impacts individuals but the effects on the quality in research and education is unknown; (c) there is almost no evidence</p>	<p><i>sexual harassment; higher education; systematic review; prevalence; consequences; prevention; research</i></p>

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			supporting the supposed effects of major preventive measures; and (d) research on sexual harassment in higher education lacks theoretical, longitudinal, qualitative and intersectional approaches and perspectives.	
3	<p>Bovill, H. and Podpadec, T. (2022) "What is Currently Understood About the Impact of Sexual Violence Activism for Higher Education Student Sexual Violence Survivors?," <i>Trauma, violence & abuse</i>, pp. n/a.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/15248380221093691</p>	<p>N=28</p> <p>Global search, mainly results from the US</p> <p>2010-2020</p>	<p>Objective: This systematic literature review maps the landscape of higher education and student sexual violence survivors who become involved in sexual violence activism. It was undertaken to understand what drives student sexual violence survivors to become activists, the negative and positive impacts of this activism on the students, how higher education institutions might work with sexual violence activists to foster effective prevention and response, and how activism has been negotiated by and within practice, policy and research.</p> <p>Method: A qualitative evidence synthesis methodology was used to identify research which examines drivers to and consequences of sexual violence activism for student activists. Searches across seven databases were conducted using six keywords combined in various ways, with further inclusion criteria of published in English between 2010 and 2020. Searches of grey literature were also carried out.</p> <p>Results: 28 sources met the inclusion criteria. Thematic analysis, conducted in NVivo, resulted in identification of four themes: survival from harm, community, labour in the personal made public and power between activists and institutions.</p> <p>Conclusions/Recommendations/Limitations: Inadequate institutional response was a key driver of student sexual violence activism. Activism had positive and negative impacts on the activists. Recommendations are that activists, institutions, researchers and policy makers work as coalitions to bring about enduring cultural change. Review limitations were the small number of studies in this field; additionally, they were dominated by US and UK perspectives.</p>	<p><i>Harm; community; labour; coalition, power; sexual violence</i></p>
4	<p>Carlson, J. <i>et al.</i> (2020) "What can Campuses Learn From Community Sexual Assault Response Teams? Literature Review of Teams' Purpose, Activities, Membership, and Challenges," <i>Trauma, violence & abuse</i>, 21(4), pp. 678–690.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838018789157</p>	<p>N=14</p> <p>USA</p> <p>1999-2017</p>	<p>Sexual assault is a public health issue, with college-age students reporting high levels of victimization. Following an increase in national attention and federal initiatives, college and universities' sexual assault response efforts are being examined. The practice of community sexual assault response teams (SARTs) may provide campuses with a model strategy to coordinate campus and community service delivery and planning, still underdeveloped or missing at many institutions. This literature review summarizes in side-by-side fashion the most current empirical literature about community SARTs and campus team approaches (CTAs) in four domains: (1) defined purpose, (2) activities to achieve purpose, (3) membership, and (4) challenges to functioning. Two searches were conducted. The community SART inclusion criteria were (a) an empirical study focusing on community SARTs as the level of analysis, (b) located in the United States, (c) published between 2010 and 2017, and (d) written in English. The inclusion criteria for the CTA were (a) an empirical study on CTAs to sexual assault and/or intimate partner violence as the level of analysis and (b) written in English. Eight articles met the criteria for community SARTs, and six articles met the criteria for CTAs. Differences between community SARTs and CTAs included community SARTs shared and more discretely defined purpose and subsequent activities. Further directions offered for the conceptual and practical development of a CTA to address sexual assault include the need for clearer definition of a team's purpose leading to response-focused coordination of activities.</p>	<p><i>sexual assault; campuses; sexual assault response teams; campus team approaches; purpose; membership; challenges</i></p>
5	<p>Decker, M. and Littleton, H.L. (2018) "Sexual Revictimization Among College Women: A Review Through an Ecological Lens," <i>Victims & offenders</i>, 13(4), pp. 558–588.</p> <p>Available at:</p>	<p>N= 55</p> <p>Global search, mainly results from the US</p> <p>2000-2017</p>	<p>This paper reviews factors at the individual, microsystem, meso/exo-system, and macrosystem levels that contribute to sexual revictimization among college women. Potential implications for reducing sexual revictimization on campuses via multilevel targeting of interventions is then discussed. This review reveals that despite a need for additional work examining the influence of multiple interacting factors contributing to revictimization, extant work offers insights as to how colleges can develop comprehensive programs to reduce sexual revictimization. Such programming would not only improve institutional responses to sexual violence, but also serve as a model for reducing general cultural acceptance of the perpetration of sexual assault.</p>	<p><i>Rape; sexual assault; risk factors; prevention</i></p>

	https://doi.org/10.1080/15564886.2017.1390514			
6	Duval, A., Lanning, B.A. and Patterson, M.S. (2020) "A Systematic Review of Dating Violence Risk Factors Among Undergraduate College Students," <i>Trauma, Violence, & Abuse</i> , 21(3), pp. 567–585. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838018782207 .	N=23 USA 2006-2016	College students are a vulnerable population for dating violence (DV) because of the social environment in which they live and interact with other students. Campus climate surveys are considered best practice for gathering information about the severity and cause of college DV; however, there are still unanswered questions as to why DV remains an alarming public health concern among college students. The aim of this systematic literature review was to examine DV risk factors specific to college students with a special focus on methodological factors and gaps in the literature. Databases EBSCO, Scopus, PsycINFO, MEDLINE, ERIC, and PubMed were searched for articles published between 2006 and 2016, resulting in 23 articles that met inclusion criteria for this review. Very few studies were conducted at private universities (n ¼ 4). Most researchers used descriptive cross-sectional surveys (n ¼ 22), while only one utilized a mixed-methods approach. Measurement scales used to collect DV rates were similar across studies, yet the definition of DV was inconsistent. Types and severity of DV varied across studies, but overall, females were more likely to perpetrate and/or experience DV than males. Individual risk factors (e.g., substance use, risky sexual behaviors) were identified more often than family risk factors (e.g., intergenerational violence) and peer and social risk factors (e.g., Greeklife or athletic team membership, relationship type). A better understanding of new college relationships is critical to identify modifiable risk factors for DV. Recommendations for future practice and research are also discussed.	<i>dating violence, domestic violence, cultural contexts, intervention/treatment, situational factors, sexual assault, adult victims</i>
7	Evans, J.L., Burroughs, M.E. and Knowlden, A.P. (2019) "Examining the efficacy of bystander sexual violence interventions for first- year college students: A systematic review," <i>Aggression and violent behavior</i> , 48, pp. 72–82. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2019.08.016 .	N=11 USA 2010-2017	Objective: The purpose of the following systematic review was to determine the efficacy of bystander sexual violence, school-based educational interventions, aimed at first-year college students to reduce the occurrence of sexual violence on college campuses. Methods: A literature search was conducted using MEDLINE, CENTRAL, ERIC, and CINAHL Plus and Boolean search logic to extract articles from the databases. Only peer-reviewed journal articles published from 2010 to 2017 were considered. After applying inclusion criteria based on the study purpose, only seven articles remained in the review. Results: Bystander intervention education is effective in increasing student's bystander confidence; however, these results were mixed. Studies in this review employed different educational programs and durations, and instrumentation to assess bystander behavior and confidence. Conclusion: Bystander intervention education is effective in increasing bystander confidence among college students; however, confidence gained during bystander intervention education needs to be assessed.	<i>health education, sexual violence, bystander intervention, literature review</i>
8	Fedina, L., Holmes, J.L. and Backes, B.L. (2016) "Campus sexual assault: A systematic review of prevalence research from 2000 to 2015," <i>Trauma, Violence, & Abuse</i> , 19(1), pp. 76–93. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838016631129 .	N=34 USA 2000-2015	Sexual assault is a pervasive problem on university and college campuses in the United States that has garnered growing national attention, particularly in the past year. This is the first study to systematically review and synthesize prevalence findings from studies on campus sexual assault (CSA) published since 2000 (n¼34). The range of prevalence findings for specific forms of sexual victimization on college campuses (i.e., forcible rape, unwanted sexual contact, incapacitated rape, sexual coercion, and studies' broad definitions of CSA/rape) is provided, and methodological strengths and limitations in the empirical body of research on CSA are discussed. Prevalence findings, research design, methodology, sampling techniques, and measures, including the forms of sexual victimization measured, are presented and evaluated across studies. Findings suggest that unwanted sexual contact appears to be most prevalent on college campuses, including sexual coercion, followed by incapacitated rape, and completed or attempted forcible rape. Additionally, several studies measured broad constructs of sexual assault that typically include combined forms of college-based sexual victimization (i.e., forcible completed or attempted rape, unwanted	<i>campus sexual assault, rape, sexual victimization, unwanted sexual contact, prevalence, college students</i>

			sexual contact, and/or sexual coercion). Extensive variability exists within findings for each type of sexual victimization measured, including those that broadly measure sexual assault, which is largely explained by differences in sampling strategies and overall study designs as well as measures of sexual assault used in studies. Implications for findings and recommendations for future research on the prevalence of college-based sexual victimization are provided.	
9	<p>Forsman, R.L. (2017) "Prevalence of Sexual Assault Victimization Among College Men, Aged 18-24: A Review," <i>Journal of evidence-based social work</i>, 14(6), pp. 421–432.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/23761407.2017.1369204.</p>	<p>N=5</p> <p>Global search, but all included studies have the US as empirical base.</p> <p>1999-2016</p>	<p>Purpose: The current review provides summary and evaluation of prevalence data for the sexual victimization of college men ages 18 – 24.</p> <p>Methods: Potential studies were selected by searching electronic bibliographic databases. Studies were initially selected for inclusion if they (1) assessed prevalence rates of sexual victimization on college campuses and (2) were published in a scholarly journal (3) in the English language. Utilizing this strategy, 3,973 studies were initially identified, of which 5 underwent complete review.</p> <p>Results: All 5 studies returned results for sexual victimization of men on college campuses. However, identified prevalence data varies widely from 3.2% – 28.7% of the males surveyed.</p> <p>When incapacitation as a form of victimization was included in the study, college men as a whole appear to be most vulnerable to this form of sexual violence, though sexual minority males may have more heterogeneous experiences of victimization.</p> <p>Conclusions: Conceptualization of sexual victimization and wording of items attempting to assess prevalence rates likely lead to underestimation of true prevalence. Even with an incomplete understanding of prevalence, results suggest that continuing to assess prevalence may not be the most pressing need at this time. Research into the kinds of victimization college men face as well as education, prevention, and intervention within these areas may likely do more to positively advance the knowledge base.</p>	<p><i>Campus sexual assault; male sexual victimization; sexual assault</i></p>
10	<p>Hafford-Letchfield, T. et al. (2017) "Transgender students in post-compulsory education: A systematic review," <i>International Journal of Educational Research</i>, 86, pp. 1–12.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2017.08.004</p>	<p>N=20</p> <p>2005-2016</p> <p>Global search, results mainly from the US</p>	<p>Students identifying on the transgender spectrum are significantly under-researched and underreported in the education literature. Long term detrimental effects of gender-identity based discrimination and violence requires us to find more inclusive ways of supporting students with transgender identities. We report findings from a systematic review of the international research on transgender students in post-compulsory education. A standardised review protocol was used to synthesise findings from twenty empirical studies to: 1) describe the complexities of gender identities within education; 2) situate the importance of targeting equality issues for transgender students, and; 3) highlight emerging innovations and the need for further research. We recommend more critical engagement and dialogue with transgender issues to challenge institutional policies, processes in education with those involved</p>	<p><i>Transgender; gender non-conforming; education; students; universities; college; equality; inclusion</i></p>
11	<p>Halstead, V., Williams, J.R. and Gonzalez-Guarda, R. (2017) "Sexual violence in the college population: a systematic review of disclosure and campus resources and services," <i>Journal of clinical nursing</i>, 26(15-16), pp. 2137–2153.</p> <p>Available at:</p>	<p>N=16</p> <p>USA</p> <p>2010-2015</p>	<p>Aims and objectives: To synthesise research examining college student sexual violence disclosure and campus sexual violence resources and services.</p> <p>Background: Recently, the issue of sexual violence within the college population has garnered attention worldwide. The prevalence of sexual violence within college students is alarmingly high. Survivors often experience negative outcomes (e.g. health-related consequences, impact on education). Efforts have been made to address this significant public health concern.</p> <p>Design: Systematic review of published literature.</p> <p>Methods: Studies were identified through systematic searches of PubMed, CINAHL and PsycInfo of articles published between January 2010–February 2015. A total of 672 articles were identified. After screening, 16 articles were included in this review.</p>	<p><i>College; disclosure; sexual violence; sexual violence resources; sexual violence services; student health</i></p>

	http://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.13735		<p>Results: A lack of consistency in how sexual violence was referred to and measured was identified. Research on college student sexual violence disclosure has primarily been conducted in six areas: (1) informal disclosure, (2) formal disclosure, (3) friends' perceptions of disclosure, (4) process/effects of disclosure on the survivor, (5) barriers to disclosure and (6) social support in the disclosure process. Research related to campus sexual violence resources and services has primarily focused on: (1) students' knowledge, (2) students' utilization and (3) students' suggestions. Synthesised findings are presented.</p> <p>Conclusions: Sexual violence impacts college student survivors and the campus community as a whole. To appropriately assist/address sexual violence, a thorough understanding of college student sexual violence disclosure and campus sexual violence resources/services is necessary. Suggestions for researchers, colleges and nurses are provided.</p> <p>Relevance to clinical practice: Nurses who serve students, especially those at on campus student health centres, are opportunely placed to address sexual violence. Findings highlight the need for nurses to use consistent definitions of sexual violence when identifying survivors. Nurses should take measures to increase disclosure and promote sexual violence resources/services provided by their facility. Additional suggestions for nurses are provided.</p>	
12	<p>Henning, M.A. <i>et al.</i> (2017) "Workplace harassment among staff in higher education: a systematic review," <i>Asia Pacific education review</i>, 18(4), pp. 521–539.</p> <p>Available at: http://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-017-9499-0</p>	<p>N= 51</p> <p>Global search, results mainly from US, UK, Canada and Turkey</p> <p>1994-2013</p>	<p>Workplace harassment in higher education adversely impacts workforce productivity and has deleterious health effects on victims. The aim of this study was to review the literature pertaining to workplace harassment in higher education. This systematic literature search was conducted in December 2013 and completed in January 2014. Refereed journal publications from 1994 to 2013 inclusive were identified. The strategy was conducted on seven major databases. A total of 3278 articles were initially screened, and after review 51 refereed journal articles were included in the final analysis. A thematic analysis identified six themes: causation, types, employee roles, measurement, consequences and interventions. The published evidence, mainly from North America, suggests that workplace harassment is prevalent in higher education, such as gender harassment, workplace bullying, and mobbing. This review highlighted issues associated with: (1) confirming direct causation of harassment due to the high prevalence of correlational research in this area; (2) establishing and standardising measures of harassment that would have cross-cultural applicability and validity; (3) the demand for more comparative research to cater for the globally mobile workforce; (4) the requirement for greater monitoring and evaluation of the efficacy of policies and programmes purporting to be effective in dealing with harassment in the higher education workplace; and (5) the need for more contextually laden research to examine the unique nuances operating in countries, such as those in the Asia Pacific region, not well represented in the literature.</p>	<p><i>Workplace harassment; higher education; systematic review; staff</i></p>
13	<p>Jouriles, E.N. <i>et al.</i> (2018) "Bystander programs addressing sexual violence on college campuses: A systematic review and meta-analysis of program outcomes and delivery methods," <i>Journal of American college health</i>, 66(6), pp. 457–466.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/07448481.2018.1431906.</p>	<p>N=24</p> <p>USA</p> <p>-> 2017</p>	<p>Objectives: This systematic review and meta-analysis evaluates the effectiveness of bystander programs that address sexual violence on college campuses. Program effects on student attitudes/beliefs and bystander behavior were examined. Durability of program outcomes and the influence of program-delivery methods (e.g., facilitator-led programs vs. video, online or poster campaign programs) and program-parameters (e.g., program length) were also evaluated. Methods: Twenty-four studies met criteria for inclusion in the meta-analysis, and 207 separate results from these studies were coded.</p> <p>Results: Students who participated in a bystander program, compared to those who had not, had more pro-social attitudes/beliefs about sexual violence and intervening to prevent it, and engaged in more bystander behavior. Program effects diminished over time, but meaningful changes persisted for at least three months following program delivery. Longer programs had greater effects than shorter programs on attitudes/beliefs.</p> <p>Conclusions: Bystander programs can be a valuable addition to colleges' violence prevention efforts.</p>	<p><i>Bystander; sexual violence; meta-analysis</i></p>

14	<p>Kefale, B. <i>et al.</i> (2021) "Predictors of sexual violence among female students in higher education institutions in Ethiopia: A systematic review and meta-analysis," <i>PloS one</i>, 16(2), p. n/a.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0247386.</p>	<p>N=10 Ethiopia 2000-2020</p>	<p>Background: Sexual violence is a profound social and public health problem in Ethiopia. Female students in institutions of higher education are highly vulnerable to sexual violence. Different studies conducted on sexual violence at higher education institutions lack consistency and inclusiveness. Thus, this systematic review and meta-analysis were conducted to estimate the lifetime and twelve-month prevalence, and predictors of sexual violence among female students in institutions of higher education in Ethiopia.</p> <p>Methods: This study used a systematic review and meta-analysis of studies conducted from January 1, 2000, to June 1, 2020, in Ethiopia. This review followed Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. Electronic databases including PubMed, Cochrane Library, Hinari, Google Scholar, CINAHL, and Global Health were searched using relevant search terms. Meta-analysis was performed using STATA 14 software.</p> <p>The I2 statistics and Egger's test were used to assess heterogeneity and publication bias, respectively. Forest plots were used to present the prevalence and odds ratio (OR) with a 95% confidence interval (CI).</p> <p>Results: This systematic review and meta-analysis included 10 studies, 5790 study participants. The pooled lifetime and twelve-month prevalence of sexual violence among female students in Ethiopia was 49.4% (95%CI: 37.87, 60.96) and 36.02% (95%CI: 26.42, 45.62) respectively. Rural residence (OR = 2.13;95%CI: 1.33, 3.42), alcohol drinking (OR = 2.03; 95%CI: 1.44, 2.87), and ever had a boyfriend (OR = 2.07; 95%CI: 1.32, 3.62) were factors associated with sexual violence.</p> <p>Conclusions: The lifetime prevalence of sexual violence among female students in institutions of higher education in Ethiopia was high. Place of residence, alcohol drinking, and ever had a boyfriend were statistically significant factors of sexual violence. Life skill training and law enforcement are needed to control alcohol consumption. Additionally, more focused interventions should be done in rural settings.</p>	<p>No keywords</p>
15	<p>Kettrey, H.H. and Marx, R.A. (2019) "Does the Gendered Approach of Bystander Programs Matter in the Prevention of Sexual Assault Among Adolescents and College Students? A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis," <i>Archives of sexual behavior</i>, 48(7), pp. 2037–2053.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-019-01503-1.</p>	<p>N=21 USA 2000-2017</p>	<p>Sexual assault is a significant problem among adolescents and college students in the U.S. One promising strategy for preventing sexual assault is the implementation of bystander programs, which encourage young people to intervene when witnessing incidents or warning signs of sexual assault. The evidence base for the effectiveness of bystander programs appears to be promising, but we know little about which programs are most effective in preventing sexual assault. This is a significant oversight, as bystander programs vary in content, particularly in their gendered framing of sexual assault. In this systematic review and meta-analysis, we synthesized high-quality research examining the effects of bystander programs on (1) bystander intervention and (2) self-reported perpetration of sexual assault. Paying special attention to a gendered approach as a moderator of program effects, we synthesized data from 14 independent studies (N = 7881). Twelve studies were randomized controlled trials and two used high-quality quasi-experimental designs. Findings indicated that bystander programs have a significant, desirable effect on bystander intervention, but no significant effect on sexual assault perpetration. Despite calls for sex-segregated implementation of sexual assault programs, we found no evidence that method of implementation (i.e., individual, single-sex group, mixed-sex group) moderated the effect of bystander programs on bystander intervention. Additionally, we found no evidence that gendered framing of sexual assault (i.e., portraying sexual assault as a gender-neutral problem or a gendered problem overwhelmingly affecting young women) moderated the effect of bystander programs.</p>	<p>sexual assault, bystander, meta-analysis, adolescence, prevention</p>
16	<p>Kettrey, H.H. and Marx, R.A. (2019) "The Effects of Bystander Programs on</p>	<p>N=15</p>	<p>Research on sexual assault prevention programs implemented with young people has largely failed to examine program effects between age groups. This systematic review and meta-analysis synthesizes data from 15 high quality studies (N=6104) examining the effects of sexual</p>	<p>Sexual assault; bystander; meta-</p>

	the Prevention of Sexual Assault across the College Years: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis," <i>Journal of youth and adolescence</i> , 48(2), pp. 212–227. Available at: http://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-018-0927-1	USA 2007-2016	assault prevention bystander programs on bystander efficacy, intentions, and intervention across the college years. Findings indicate bystander programs have a significant, desirable effect on all three outcomes. Effects on bystander intentions were significantly stronger among students in their first two years compared to those in their later years of college. There was no evidence of a significant difference in effects on bystander efficacy or intervention between these two groups. Implications and directions for future research are discussed.	<i>analysis; adolescence; college; prevention</i>
17	Kettrey, H.H., Marx, R.A. and Tanner-Smith, E.E. (2019) "Effects of bystander programs on the prevention of sexual assault among adolescents and college students: A systematic review," <i>Campbell systematic review</i> , 15(1-2), p. n/a. Available at: https://doi.org/10.4073/csr.2019.1	N=27 USA 1997-2017	<i>No abstract, but parts of 'plain language summary' shown:</i> This Campbell systematic review examines the effects of bystander programs on knowledge and attitudes concerning sexual assault and bystander intervention, bystander intervention when witnessing sexual assault or its warning signs, and the perpetration of sexual assault. The review summarizes evidence from 27 high-quality studies, including 21 randomized controlled trials. Bystander programs have a significant effect on bystander intervention. But there is no evidence that these programs have an effect on rates of sexual assault perpetration. This suggests that bystander programs may be appropriate for targeting the behavior of potential bystanders but may not be appropriate for targeting the behavior of potential perpetrators. Beneficial effects of bystander programs on bystander intervention were diminished by 6 months post-intervention. Thus, booster sessions may be needed to yield any sustained effects. There are still important questions worth further exploration. Namely, more research is needed to investigate the underlying causal mechanisms of program effects on bystander behavior (e.g., to model relationships between specific knowledge/attitude effects and bystander intervention effects), and to identify the most effective types of bystander programs (e.g., using randomized controlled trials to compare the effects of two alternate program models). Additionally, more research is needed in contexts outside of the USA so that researchers can better understand the role of bystander programs across the world.	<i>No keywords</i>
18	Klein, L.B. and Martin, S.L. (2021) "Sexual Harassment of College and University Students: A Systematic Review," <i>Trauma, Violence, & Abuse</i> , 22(4), pp. 777–792. Available at: http://doi.org/10.1177/1524838019881731	N= 24 USA 2000-2018	Increased attention to Title IX and the #MeToo movement has led to more interest in developing strategies to prevent forms of gender-based violence beyond acquaintance rape, including sexual harassment (SH). This study reviewed the extant literature published since 2000 on SH of college/university students (n=24) to determine (a) study methods, (b) sample socio demographic characteristics, (c) prevalence, (d) risk and protective factors, and (e) consequences of campus SH. These studies shared the view that overall SH rates are high, but their findings were difficult to cross-evaluate due to variations in their study designs. Generally, unwanted sexual attention and gender harassment were more commonly experienced in campus SH occurrences than sexual coercion. Findings indicated that being White, a woman, or a sexual minority increased a student's likelihood of experiencing SH while at a college/university. Student SH survivors rarely filed official reports but often faced a variety of mental and physical health consequences. Women of color experienced lower rates of SH but more severe consequences in the aftermath. This review concludes by detailing several implications for future research, as well as possible campus SH prevention, intervention, and policy protocols.	<i>sexual harassment; campus sexual assault; sexual victimization; prevalence; college students; risk and protective factors; consequences</i>
19	Klein, L.B. <i>et al.</i> (2022) "Sexual and Relationship Violence Among LGBTQ	N=60	Although there has been increased attention to campus sexual and relationship violence (SRV) because of Title IX and the #MeToo movement, much of that attention has focused on victimization of cisgender heterosexual women. This scoping review uncovers information	<i>sexual assault; intimate partner</i>

	College Students: A Scoping Review," <i>Trauma, violence & abuse</i> Available at: http://doi.org/10.1177/15248380221089981	USA 2011-2022	from empirical studies on what is known about LGBTQ+ (e.g., lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, and nonbinary) students' experiences of campus SRV. Using rigorous scoping review methods (i.e., searches of 15 databases, searches of expert websites, hand searching, reference harvesting, and forward citation chaining), we identified 60 documents published since 2000 that contained findings from empirical studies related to LGBTQ+ students and SRV on U.S. college and university campuses. Through content analysis, we summarized findings around five key themes: (1) extent and types of victimization, (2) negative outcomes, (3) knowledge of and attitudes about SRV, (4) perspectives on SRV services and prevention education programs, and (5) recommendations from study authors based on their findings. Implications for research, practice, and policy based on these findings are discussed.	<i>violence; college; LGBTQ+; sexual minority; gender minority</i>
20	Kovalenko, A.G. <i>et al.</i> (2022) "What Works in Violence Prevention Among Young People?: A Systematic Review of Reviews," <i>Trauma, Violence, & Abuse</i> , 23(5), pp. 1388–1404. Available at: http://doi.org/10.1177/1524838020939130	N= 40 Global search, results mainly from North America, Europe and Australia 1999-2018	Violence prevention programs aim to raise awareness, change attitudes, normative beliefs, motivation, and behavioral responses. Many programs have been developed and evaluated, and optimistic claims about effectiveness made. Yet comprehensive guidance on program design, implementation, and evaluation is limited. The aim of this study was to provide an up-to-date review of evidence on what works for whom. A systematic search of PsycINFO, MEDLINE, ERIC, and Sociology Collection ProQuest identified 40 reviews and meta-analyses reporting on the effectiveness of violence prevention programs among young people (age 15–30) in educational institutions, published before October 2018. These included reviews of programs designed to reduce (i)bullying, (ii) dating and relationship violence, (iii) sexual assault, and (iv) antisocial behavior. Only evaluations that reported on behavioral outcomes such as perpetration, victimization, and bystander behavior were included. The reviewed evaluations reported on programs that were mainly implemented in high-income countries in Europe and North America. The majority found small effects on violence reduction and victimization and increases in self-reported bystander behavior. Our findings expose critical gaps in evaluation research in this area and provide recommendations on how to optimize the effectiveness of future programs.	<i>Review of reviews; narrative reviews; meta-analyses; young people; campus violence prevention</i>
21	Labhardt, D. <i>et al.</i> (2017) "You see but you do not observe: A review of bystander intervention and sexual assault on university campuses," <i>Aggression and violent behavior</i> , 35, pp. 13–25. Available at: http://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2017.05.005	N= 28 USA 1980-2015	Sexual assault on university campuses has garnered increased attention in recent years. A systematic review was conducted to identify the factors associated with bystander intervention regarding sexual assault on university campuses. Currently, no published systematic reviews exist within this area. Twenty-eight studies were reviewed according to four major bystander factors: rape myth and date rape attitudes; bystander efficacy; bystander intent; and bystander behavior. There was a heavy emphasis on bystander intent and behavior throughout. Three important limitations were identified: (1) all empirical research has been conducted in the USA, yet bystander intervention programs exist outside of the USA, in countries such as the UK, (2) a majority of the studies employed quantitative methodologies and so failed to capture important details such as bystanders' perceptions of sexual assault or what other factors influence the likelihood of intervening, and (3) there were limited attempts to control for factors such as social desirability. This area of research is still in its infancy. Future research should examine in greater detail the factors inhibiting and facilitating bystander intervention. Finally, research outside of the USA is important in developing the literature in this area to effectively inform bystander intervention programs.	<i>Bystander behavior; bystander intervention; sexual assault; university campus; systematic review</i>
22	Mahoney, P. <i>et al.</i> (2020) "Applying the Haddon Matrix to evaluate sexual assault interventions on college campuses," <i>Journal of American college health</i> , 68(6), pp. 579–586.	N=31 USA 2001-2017	Objective: A Haddon Matrix analysis was used to systematically review literature evaluating college campus sexual assault prevention programs to identify research gaps and intervention opportunities. Methods: Articles included were published from January 1, 2001 to December 31, 2017; indexed in PubMed, PsycInfo, or Scopus; involving English-speaking undergraduate students in the US; with experimental or quasi-experimental design. Results: All 31 eligible studies evaluated educational programming; all relied on self-report measures; and three-quarters had follow-up periods ≤ 6months. Significant positive effects were reported by 6 of 10 studies that measured bystander behavior, 6 of 10 that educated	<i>Haddon Matrix; intervention research; sexual assault; sexual violence</i>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/07448481.2019.1583658 .		potential victims and assessed victimization, and one of four that educated potential perpetrators and measured perpetration. Conclusion: The Haddon Matrix analysis identified the need for interventions that address perpetrators and the post-assault period, as well as studies of the impact of enforcing existing policies and new environmental and situational approaches to sexual assault prevention.	
23	Molstad, T.D., Weinhardt, J.M. and Jones, R. (2021) "Sexual Assault as a Contributor to Academic Outcomes in University: A Systematic Review," <i>Trauma, violence & abuse</i> , pp. n/a Available at: http://doi.org/10.1177/15248380211030247	N=13 Global search, 12 studies use samples in North America, 1 in Nigeria 2007-2021	Sexual assault continues to be a prevalent and consequential experience for university students. The aim of this systematic review was to synthesize the literature on the academic consequences of the sexual assault for university students. There is currently no comprehensive review of the literature focusing on the academic consequences for university students who experienced sexual assault. This review was conducted based on searches from five databases including Academic Search Complete, Education Search Complete, Education Resources Information Center (ERIC), PsycINFO, and Google Scholar. We identified 13 articles that examined academic consequences of sexual assault during university. Across all studies, sexual assault was associated with more academic problems including lower grade point average, dropping out of university, and self-regulated learning problems. Although the number of articles is small, the results are consistent. Practically, this means that universities, those providing psychological services, and victims themselves need to understand that the consequences are not just physical and psychological but can also negatively impact academic achievement. Our review also identifies limitations in the literature regarding this topic such as methodological concerns, diversity and inclusion concerns, and the need for future work to investigate mediators of the relationship between sexual assault and academic outcomes. We offer recommendations for future research to combat the concerns identified. Development of interventions to support those who experience sexual assault during university necessitates overcoming the limitations identified.	<i>sexual assault; sexual harassment; PTSD; violence exposure</i>
24	O'Connor, J. et al. (2021) "Predictors of campus sexual violence perpetration: A systematic review of research, sampling, and study design," <i>Aggression and violent behavior</i> , 58, p. 101607. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2021.101607 .	N=28 USA 2000-2019	Understanding the research on predictors of campus sexual violence perpetration is critical for primary prevention efforts directed at preventing perpetrators from offending. This study systematically reviewed 28 research articles to understand common predictors of campus sexual violence perpetration as well as the research and study design of these articles. Personality factors, attitudes, and negative life experiences were the most investigated predictors of campus perpetration, while other factors, such as sexual behavior and past perpetration, received less empirical attention. Most of the studies in this review used cross-sectional, observational data with participants at large, public universities. The samples were largely White, undergraduate students. These findings indicate that more research is needed to understand predictors of campus sexual violence perpetration with increased attention to understudied risk factors. Future research should be conducted at more diverse institutions with more diverse samples.	<i>campus, sexual violence, perpetration predictors, review, research methods</i>
25	McNair, K. et al. (2018). "Sexual Misconduct Policies at Institutes of Higher Education: An Integrative Review". <i>Journal of forensic nursing</i> . 14. 238-247. Available at: http://doi.org/10.1097/JFN.0000000000000216	N=8 USA 1990-2018	Although federal legislation designed to advance sexual misconduct policies at institutes of higher education (IHEs) has been in effect for decades, recent national attention has put more pressure on IHEs to combat sexual violence on their campuses. Thus, the past few years have yielded significant research that examines federal compliance, dissemination, and perception of IHE sexual misconduct policies. This integrative review was conducted to assess sexual misconduct policies in the United States and the potential to prevent and combat sexual violence at IHEs through these policies. Following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses guidelines and using a quality assessment tool to ensure rigor, eight studies were synthesized. Findings indicate that IHE sexual misconduct policies vary widely and that most IHEs lack transparent, legislation-compliant policies. There remains a need for research examining the association between sexual misconduct policy, campus climate, and students' behavior, so as to better inform future sexual misconduct interventions and IHE policies. Forensic nurses may be key stakeholders in policy development that is currently missing from the literature.	<i>Campus violence; institutes of higher education; sexual misconduct policy</i>

26	Steele, B. et al. (2022) "Risk and Protective Factors for Men's Sexual Violence Against Women at Higher Education Institutions: A Systematic and Meta-Analytic Review of the Longitudinal Evidence," <i>Trauma, Violence, & Abuse</i> , 23(3), pp. 716–732. Available at: http://doi.org/10.1177/1524838020970900	N= 16 Global search, but all included studies have the US as empirical base. 2003-2019	Sexual violence among higher education institution (HEI) students is a growing public health concern. To date, there is little evidence on how to effectively prevent sexual violence among this demographic. This study is the first systematic review to meta-analyze all available evidence for risk and protective factors of sexual violence perpetrated by men at HEIs. We searched four electronic databases and multiple gray literature sources. We screened studies using prespecified selection criteria for the sample (HEI students who identify as men), outcome (sexual violence perpetration against peers), and study design (quantitative and longitudinal). Longitudinal studies provide the most rigorous available evidence on risk and protective factors. We identified 16 studies and meta-analyzed eight different risk factors: alcohol consumption, hostility toward women, delinquency, fraternity membership, history of sexual violence perpetration, rape myth acceptance, age at first sex, and peer approval of sexual violence. We deemed included studies to have a varied risk of bias and the overall quality of evidence to range from moderate to high. History of sexual violence perpetration (perpetration prior to entering an HEI) emerged as the strongest predictor of sexual violence perpetration at HEIs, complicating the notion that HEI environments themselves foster a culture of sexual violence. Peer support for sexual violence predicted perpetration while individual rape-supporting beliefs did not. Our findings suggest that interventions targeting peer norms (e.g., bystander interventions) and early sexual violence prevention and consent interventions for high school and elementary school students could be effective in reducing and preventing sexual violence at HEIs.	<i>sexual assault; dating violence; domestic violence; offenders; sexual assault</i>
27	Stoner, J.E. and Cramer, R.J. (2019) "Sexual Violence Victimization Among College Females: A Systematic Review of Rates, Barriers, and Facilitators of Health Service Utilization on Campus," <i>Trauma, Violence, & Abuse</i> , 20(4), pp. 520–533. Available at: http://doi.org/10.1177/1524838017721245	N=22 USA 1990-2016	To date, little work specifically addresses empirical studies concerning barriers and facilitators to health service use among college female sexual violence victims. The following objectives were addressed: (1) analyze studies of college-aged women who have been victims of sexual violence to examine the frequency and moderating characteristics of utilization of university-based resources available, (2) identify inconsistencies and gaps in the literature concerning sexual victimization and service utilization, and (3) provide next steps for researchers and clinical care coordinators. Six electronic databases were searched from 1990 to May 2016. Inclusion criteria for the review were (1) university or college setting or sample, (2) empirical design, and (3) inclusion of some discussion or measurement of health service use. Following preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) procedures, 22 articles were identified for the review. Although prevalence rates of sexual victimization were high (4.7–58%), rates of service utilization were lower (0–42%). There were significant discrepancies between hypothetical use of services and actual rates of service use. Identified barriers included feelings of shame, guilt and embarrassment, not wanting friends and family to find out, and thinking the victimization was not serious enough to report. Identified facilitators included acknowledging the sexual violence victimization as a crime, receiving encouragement from friends and family to utilize health services, and receiving a positive response during the initial informal disclosure. Finally, measurement of victimization was inconsistent across studies. Recommendations are offered for college campus prevention programming and future research.	<i>sexual victimization; college student; systematic review</i>
28	Tashkandi, Y. et al. (2022) "A Systematic Review of Campus Characteristics Associated With Sexual Violence and Other Forms of Victimization," <i>Trauma, violence & abuse</i> , p. n/a	N=43 USA 1978->	Violence researchers have highlighted a need to understand connections between campus characteristics and violent victimization among students. Responding to those calls, we systematically reviewed research examining the characteristics of secondary and post-secondary educational settings associated with sexual violence and related victimization experiences, including dating/intimate partner violence, stalking, bullying, hate crimes, and crime more broadly. We screened 1124 quantitative and qualitative records, 43 of which met the inclusion criteria for this systematic review. Evidence emerged for institution demographics, institution type, institution climate, institution financial characteristics, and educational characteristics being related to various forms of victimization; institution setting (urban vs. rural) was not associated with victimization. Additionally, evidence was observed for institution location and size/density. Some factors, including institution	<i>sexual assault, intimate partner violence, bullying, crime, campus characteristics</i>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/15248380221078893 .		type and campus demographics, operated differently for different forms of victimization. We highlight limitations of existing data, including variability in the measurement of victimization outcomes, lack of power to detect differences at the campus level, and challenges of creating a database on victimization that contains campus identifiers. We also reinforce calls for more intersectional research, both in terms of the types of victimization experienced by students as well as in the disproportionate impact victimization may have on students with marginalized identities.	
29	Voth Schrag, R.J. (2016) "Campus Based Sexual Assault and Dating Violence," <i>Affilia</i> , 32(1), pp. 67–80. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886109916644644 .	N=196 USA 2010-2015	Colleges are working to study and address sexual assault (SA) and dating violence (DV) on campus. This quantitative systematic review assessed 196 studies of SA and DV to evaluate if the literature fully reflects the demographics of American higher education. Results show disproportionate representation in the populations and settings in which research is occurring. No studies occurred at associates/2-year institutions, and participants are substantially younger and whiter than American college students overall. Education and prevention efforts that do not take into account the bias in these studies may exacerbate intersectional barriers for students.	<i>domestic violence, feminist theories and research, intimate partner violence, research categories, sexual abuse</i>
30	Wong, J.S., Bouchard, J. and Lee, C. (2021) "The Effectiveness of College Dating Violence Prevention Programs: A Meta-Analysis," <i>Trauma, violence & abuse</i> , pp. n/a Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/15248380211036058	N= 29 Global search, mainly results from the US 2000-2020	Due in part to their involvement with social activities on campus, college students experience an increased risk of dating violence. Recent legislation such as the Campus SaVE Act (which requires U.S. colleges to offer training on sexual assault, domestic violence, stalking, and sexual harassment to all incoming students) has contributed to the increase in prevention programming offered across postsecondary campuses, as well as subsequent research examining the effectiveness of these prevention efforts. The current study provides a systematic review and meta-analysis of college dating violence prevention programs. A systematic search of 28 databases and numerous gray literature sources identified an initial 14,540 articles of which 315 were deemed potentially eligible for inclusion. Studies were selected if they (1) evaluated a college dating prevention program/campaign, (2) reported one of five outcomes (knowledge, attitudes, or bystander efficacy, intentions, or behavior), (3) had a minimum sample size of 20 in the treatment group, (4) used a pre/post and/or comparison group design, and (5) were published in English or French between January 2000 and October 2020. We calculated 53 effect sizes from 31 studies and conducted separate meta-analyses on various categories of outcome measures. Findings suggest that college dating violence prevention programs are effective at increasing knowledge and attitudes toward dating violence, as well as bystander skills, but are not effective at increasing bystander behaviors. Findings from moderator analyses suggest that several program components influence the strength of treatment effects. Implications for improving the effectiveness of college dating violence prevention programs are discussed.	<i>dating violence; domestic violence; intervention/treatment; domestic violence: date rape; sexual assault</i>

Appendix C – European research publications, 2017-2022

No.	Reference	Country	Method <i>Qualitative/quantitative</i> <i>N = sample size</i>	Abstract	Keywords
1	<p>Siller, D.H. et al. (2021) “Not a Woman-Question, But a Power-Question’: A Qualitative Study of Third Parties on Psychological Violence in Academic Medicine,” <i>Workplace health & safety</i>, 69(1), pp. 41–49.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/2165079920938001</p>	Austria	Qualitative	<p>Background: Psychological violence is a persistent issue in academic medicine and affects the health and safety of health care workers. This violence is also debated as part of medical culture. Third parties, persons learning about violations after it happened, may provide an understanding of the interplay between gender and psychological violence. Perspectives on research on psychological violence in academic medicine are currently lacking.</p> <p>Methods: In this qualitative exploratory study, interviews were conducted with women from a working group on equal treatment at one medical university in Austria. This group monitors discrimination and harassment and consists of medical doctors, natural scientists, administrative staff, and students. To recruit participants, an email invitation was sent to members of the working group. Of 20 eligible persons, 12 women participated. After written consent from participants, individual interviews were conducted face-to-face, audiorecorded, and transcribed verbatim. Data were analyzed with grounded theory.</p> <p>Findings: Participants described a firm organizational culture with persistent, historically grown gendered structures. Potential threat of psychological violence affected mostly “weaker,” less powerful persons, and often women. Descriptions of violence indicated harm to those affected, but intent to harm was doubted. Interventions strengthened the individual, but some participants demanded collective responsibility.</p> <p>Conclusion/application to practice: Few descriptions could be classified as psychological violence. Findings indicated a need to change organizational cultures where lower positions pose a potential threat to experiencing harm. Occupational health practice should include training in sensitization to psychological violence, protection of those targeted, deconstructing power accumulation, and promoting diversity in career patterns and working styles.</p>	<p><i>Psychological violence in the workplace; power; gender; academic medicine</i></p>

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2	<p>Dodaj, A., Sesar, K. and Šimić, N. (2020) "Impulsivity and empathy in dating violence among a sample of college females," Behavioral Sciences, 10(7), p. 117.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.3390/bs10070117.</p>	Bosnia and Herzegovina	<p>Quantitative</p> <p>N = 474</p>	<p>The predictive factors of violence between married couples or adolescents are well-known. However, less is known about the factors relating to intimate violence among college students. This study examined sociodemographic variables (age, duration of relationship, and relationship satisfaction), impulsivity, and empathy as predictors of dating violence, using data from 474 female college students from the University of Mostar, Bosnia and Herzegovina. The sample completed online the Conflict Tactics Scale 2 Short Form, the Interpersonal Reactivity Index, and the Short Impulsive Behavior Scale. The results indicated a higher prevalence of victimization than perpetration for psychological aggression. The obtained data showed that younger women and those in longer relationships, as well as those unsatisfied with their relationship, are more prone to experience psychological victimization or perpetration. Relationship satisfaction was also shown to be a predictor of physical perpetration causing injury. Impulsivity facets were found to have a differential weight in explaining dating violence. Empathy was shown to be a significant predictor of dating victimization, specifically "perspective taking" for psychological victimization and empathic concern for sexual victimization. These results suggest the need to develop specific interventions and prevention programs focused on relationship satisfaction, impulsivity, and empathy.</p>	<p><i>Dating violence; college females; impulsivity; empathy</i></p>
3	<p>Darakchi, S. (2020) "Emergence and development of LGBTQ studies in post-socialist Bulgaria," Journal of Homosexuality, 67(3), pp. 325–334.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2018.1534413</p>	Bulgaria	Qualitative	<p>This article explores the development of LGBTQ studies and scholarship in Bulgaria. In part, it brings to the forefront the personal experiences of some of the first Bulgarian scholars working on LGBTQ studies. The personal is interpreted in part through explorations of Bourdieu's concept of "symbolic violence." Elaborating on the challenges regarding the emergence and the development of LGBTQ studies on an institutional and personal level, I discuss three main topics: (1) the emergence and the development of LGBTQ scholarship and university courses in Bulgaria; (2) the main institutional obstacles and the "symbolic violence" within the academia against scholars dealing with LGBTQ subjects, including issues of funding, evaluation, and discrimination; and (3) the future development of the subject in Bulgaria, with a particular attention to the need for "LGBTQ studies solidarity" to overcome the disadvantaged position of LGBTQ scholars in post-socialist countries.</p>	<p><i>LGBTQ Studies; LGBTQ scholars; academia; Eastern Europe</i></p>
4	<p>Šidlauskienė, V. and Pocevičienė, R. (2021) "The comparative analysis of sexual violence and harassment at the piloting universities of Cyprus and Lithuania," Information & Media, 92, pp. 90–117.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.15388/im.2021.92.</p>	Cyprus, Lithuania	Qualitative	<p>The sociocultural contexts of higher education institutions form the background for gender-based violence in professional structures and environment of academia. The article presents a comparative analysis of sexual violence and the reasons for its (non-)disclosure at the piloting universities in Lithuania and Cyprus. The findings of focus group interviews conducted within the framework of the Ending Sexual Harassment and Violence in Third Level Education (ESHTE) project, co-funded by the European Union, have been summarized in the present research. The focus group participants from each partner university involved university teachers, administrative staff, counselors and university students. The research was conducted during a 3-month period between 2017 and 2018. The main aim was to investigate university staffs' and students' experiences in the disclosures of the cases of sexual violence and harassment (SVH) in university environment and campus, as well as their awareness of</p>	<p><i>Sexual violence and harassment (SVH); academic and administrative staff; students; Cyprus; Lithuania.</i></p>

	53.			existing procedures and policies in handling the cases of SVH. The results of this study discovered both universities' academic and administrative staff and students' personal experiences, attitudes and beliefs of SVH, as well as any of their suggestions towards the improvement of disclosures of SVH are discussed in the article.	
5	Skewes, L., Skewes, J.C. and Ryan, M.K. (2021) "Attitudes to sexism and the #MeToo movement at a Danish University," NORA - Nordic Journal of Feminist and Gender Research, 29(2), pp. 124–139. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/08038740.2021.1884598 .	Denmark	Quantitative and qualitative N = 1128	We explore the relationship between academic employees' attitudes to modern sexism and the #MeToo movement to better understand how interventions designed to address sexual harassment might be received in Danish academia. Using a survey of employees at a large Danish university (N = 1128), we categorized employees' open answers about their attitudes to the #MeToo Movement as (a) positive, (b) ambivalent, or (c) negative. These categories were associated with employees' modern sexism scores, such that those higher in modern sexism were more likely to be negative about the movement, while those with lower scores were more likely to be positive. To better understand possible sources of resistance to policy interventions, we used an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design to analyse the open comments for themes related to employee's negative attitudes towards #MeToo. The two most prominent themes were: (1) delegitimisation of the purposes of the movement, and (2) perception that the rights of potential sexual perpetrators were more important than those of potential victims. We discuss the implications for the implementation of interventions targeting sexual harassment.	<i>Sexism; gender equality; harassment; discrimination; #MeToo</i>
6	Bosco Damous, L. and Guillopé, C. (2021) "Gender-based violence in Higher Education and research: A European perspective," Pure and Applied Chemistry, 93(8), pp. 899–905. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1515/pac-2021-0401 .	Europe	Qualitative	The gender gap in science is intrinsically linked to gender-based violence in academia. Gender-based violence is a form of discrimination against women that occurs in an academic environment, and it often takes the form of sexual harassment. Some European countries, such as France, Italy, and Ireland, have solid legal systems in place to address sexual harassment in academia. However, as the report of the European Research Area and Innovation Committee Standing Working Group on sexual harassment points out, not all European countries have legislation in this area, or if they do, it is often ineffective. While national surveys generally show that it is difficult to prevent or combat sexual harassment in universities, practices related to corporate social responsibility could be used to start the conversation about the social responsibility of universities to fight against sexual harassment, which is reflected in this article.	<i>Compliance; gender-based violence; gender gap; gender gap in science; higher education and research; science; sexual harassment; STEM</i>

7	<p>Täuber, S. (2022) "Women Academics' Intersectional Experiences of Policy Ineffectiveness in the European Context," <i>Frontiers in psychology</i>, 13, p. 810569.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.810569</p>	Europe	Quantitative	<p>Despite policy efforts targeted at making universities more inclusive and equitable, academia is still rife with harassment and bullying, and opportunities are far from equal for everyone. The present preregistered survey research (N=91) aimed to explore whether an intersectional approach can be useful to examine the tangible effects of policy ineffectiveness, even when legislative and ideologic constraints limit the possibility to conduct a full-fledged intersectional analysis. Policy ineffectiveness was operationalized as experiences of harassment, discrimination, institutional resistance to gender equality, and retaliation against reporters of misconduct in universities. Policy ineffectiveness was negatively related to women academics' inclination to pursue an academic career. This relationship was mediated by lower levels of psychological safety associated with policy ineffectiveness. Importantly, women academics who differ from the majority on multiple dimensions show a stronger and more negative relationship between policy ineffectiveness and psychological safety. The study further shows that self-report measures are useful to uncover intersectional privilege afforded to overrepresented groups in academia. The study discusses the benefits of intersectional approaches for designing and implementing effective policies to tackle harassment and inequality in academia, even when the available methodologies are constrained by legislation and ideology. Overall, self-report measurement can have an important function for signalling areas that warrant further intersectional inquiry to ensure that policies serve everyone.</p>	<p><i>academia, policy ineffectiveness, psychological safety, voice, intersectional inequality, intersectional privilege</i></p>
8	<p>Schuster, I., Tomaszewska, P. and Krahe, B. (2020) "Changing cognitive risk factors for sexual aggression: Risky sexual scripts, low sexual self-esteem, perception of pornography, and acceptance of sexual coercion," <i>Journal of Interpersonal Violence</i>, 37(3-4).</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260520922341.</p>	Germany	Quantitative N = 324	<p>Sexual aggression is a problem among college students worldwide, and a growing body of research has identified variables associated with an increased risk of victimization and perpetration. Among these, sexuality-related cognitions, such as sexual scripts, sexual self-esteem, perceived realism of pornography, and acceptance of sexual coercion, play a major role. The current experimental study aimed to show that these cognitive risk factors of sexual aggression victimization and perpetration are amenable to change, which is a critical condition for evidence-based intervention efforts. College students in Germany (N= 324) were randomly assigned to one of three groups: a treatment group designed to change participants' sexual scripts for consensual sex with regard to the role of alcohol consumption, casual sex, and ambiguous communication of sexual intentions as risk factors for sexual aggression (EG1), a treatment group designed to promote sexual self-esteem, challenge the perceived realism of pornography, and reduce the acceptance of sexual coercion (EG2), and a non-treatment control group (CG). Baseline (T1), post-experimental (T2), and follow-up (T3) measures were taken across an eight-week period. Sexual scripts contained fewer risk factors for sexual aggression in EG1 than in EG2 and CG at T3. Sexual self-esteem was enhanced in EG2 at T2 relative to the other two groups. Acceptance of sexual coercion was lower in EG2 than in EG1 and CG at T2 and T3. No effect was found for perceived realism of pornography. The findings are discussed in terms of targeting cognitive risk factors as a basis for</p>	<p><i>sexual aggression; sexual scripts; sexual self-esteem; sexual coercion; college students</i></p>

				intervention programs.	
9	<p>Krahé, B., Schuster, I. and Tomaszewska, P. (2021) "Prevalence of sexual aggression victimization and perpetration in a German university student sample," Archives of Sexual Behavior, 50(5), pp. 2109–2121.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-021-01963-4.</p>	Germany	<p>Quantitative</p> <p>N = 1172</p>	<p>This study examined the prevalence of sexual aggression perpetration and victimization in a sample of 1,172 students (755 female, 417 male) from four universities in Germany. All participants were asked about both victimization by, and perpetration of, sexual aggression since the age of 14 years, using the Sexual Aggression and Victimization Scale (SAV-S). Prevalence rates were established for different coercive strategies, sexual acts, and victim–perpetrator relationships. Both same-sex and opposite-sex victim–perpetrator constellations were examined. The overall victimization rate was 62.1% for women and 37.5% for men. The overall perpetration rate was 17.7% for men and 9.4% for women. Prevalence rates of both victimization and perpetration were higher for participants who had sexual contacts with both opposite-sex and same-sex partners than for participants with exclusively opposite-sex partners. Significant overlap was found between victim and perpetrator status for men and women as well as for participants with only opposite-sex and both opposite-sex and same-sex partners. A disparity between (higher) victimization and (lower) perpetration reports was found for both men and women, suggesting a general underreporting of perpetration rather than a gendered explanation in terms of social desirability or the perception of consent cues. The findings are placed in the international research literature on the prevalence of sexual aggression before and after the #metoo campaign, and their implications for prevention efforts are discussed.</p>	<p><i>Sexual aggression; sexual victimization; male victims; female perpetrators; same-sex relationships</i></p>
10	<p>Krahé, B. and Berger, A. (2021) "Pathways from college students' cognitive scripts for consensual sex to sexual victimization: A three-wave longitudinal study," The Journal of Sex Research, 58(9), pp. 1130–1139.</p>	Germany	<p>Quantitative</p> <p>N = 2425</p>	<p>Sexual scripts serve as cognitive representations of typical elements of sexual interactions that guide sexual behavior. To the extent that cognitive scripts for consensual sex comprise elements associated with a risk of experiencing nonconsensual sex, they may be indirectly linked to sexual victimization via risky sexual behavior. A longitudinal study with 2,425 college students in Germany (58% female) examined pathways from sexual scripts for consensual sex, sexual behavior, and sexual victimization over three data waves separated by 12-month intervals. Sexual scripts and behavior were defined as risky to the extent that they include known vulnerability factors for sexual victimization (casual sex, alcohol consumption, ambiguous communication of sexual intentions). Path analyses confirmed that more risky sexual scripts prospectively predicted more risky sexual behavior, which</p>	<p><i>sexual scripts; sexual victimization; sexual behavior; college students; Germany</i></p>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/00224499.2021.1972922 .			predicted higher odds of sexual victimization. The findings held for men and women and participants with exclusively opposite-sex and both same- and opposite-sex contacts. Moreover, reciprocal influences between risky scripts and risky sexual behavior were found over time, confirming the proposed mutual reinforcement of scripts and behavior. The findings have implications for conceptualizing the role of scripts for consensual sex as vulnerability factors for sexual victimization among women and men and may inform intervention efforts.	
11	Thomas Brorsen Smidt, Fredrik Bondestam, Gyða Margrét Pétursdóttir & Þorgerður Einarsdóttir (2020) Expanding gendered sites of resistance in the neoliberal academy, <i>European Journal of Higher Education</i> , 10:2, 115-129, Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/21568235.2018.1541753	Iceland	Qualitative	Neoliberalism has long found its way into higher education and made life hard for academics in a number of different ways. The literature that maps out resistance to this development focuses on the gendered aspects of labour-economic issues. However, this study argues that the zeitgeist of neoliberalism has gendered consequences far beyond market-based categories. Thirty-two in-depth interviews with current and former academics at the University of Iceland are analysed. They demonstrate that the conceptualization of gendered sites of resistance is in need of expansion. Academics still resist traditional neoliberal derivatives by (1) exiting the institution (2) complaining through official channels (3) refusing to take part in certain activities or (4) by directly confronting their superiors. However, these resistance strategies harbour new gendered sites of resistance related to tokenism, bullying and gendered harassment.	<i>Gender; neoliberalism; academia; resistance</i>
12	Pétursdóttir, G.M. (2017) "Fire-raising feminists: Embodied experience and activism in Academia," <i>European Journal of Women's Studies</i> , 24(1), pp. 85–99. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1350506815622513 .	Iceland	Qualitative	Sexual violence of various forms, be it sexual harassment or sexual abuse, perpetrated by male professors against their female students has gained societal visibility through media broadcasts. This article tells the tale of the 2013 recruitment to the University of Iceland of a former political party leader, minister and ambassador. He was publicly called out in 2012 for his alleged sexual offences, perpetrated some years earlier. The story is told from two different viewpoints: from that of the media and from the article author's own standpoint as assistant professor in gender studies with co-responsibility for his de-recruitment. In the media story, opinion leaders from the political, judicial and media spheres take centre stage. The author thus utilizes the concepts patriarchal homosociality and influencers. Based on the findings from the media analyses, the author lays out her defence and justification, using embodiment as the core of her argument. She draws on black feminist knowledge validation processes, more specifically, the ethic of caring and personal accountability. Furthermore, she explores affective feminist pedagogy, i.e., connecting mind and body through self-actualization. By contrasting the two accounts, that of the	<i>Affective feminist pedagogy; ethics of caring; ethics of personal accountability; homosocial patriarchy; sexual violence</i>

				media and her own feminist standpoint, the author sheds light on the role that influencers play in preserving patriarchal power and the status quo against 'fire-raising feminists' in academia and society at large.	
13	O'Connor, P. and Irvine, G. (2020) "Multi-level state interventions and gender equality in higher education institutions: The Irish case," <i>Administrative Sciences</i> , 10(4), p. 98. Available at: https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci10040098 .	Ireland	Qualitative	Much of the work on gender equality in higher educational institutions (HEIs) has concentrated on the organizational level. The original contribution of this article lies in its focus on state policy developments and interventions. We focus on Ireland as a specific national context, highlighting multi-level state interventions and looking at their impact on HEIs. Using secondary data analysis (including documentary analysis) and focusing particularly on the period since 2014, state initiatives to tackle the problem of gender inequality from various angles are outlined. They include the introduction of Athena SWAN; the Expert Group Review; the Gender Equality Taskforce; the Senior Academic Leadership Initiative; research funding agency initiatives and those around sexual harassment. In evaluating their impact, we look at the gender pay gap, the gender profile of the professoriate and senior management as well as other indicators of cultural change in HEIs. The article concludes that the best possibility of leveraging change arises when it is driven at the state (macro); the HEI (meso) and the situational (micro) level simultaneously, by gender competent leaders willing to tackle the historically male dominated, masculinist criteria, procedures, processes and micropolitical practices that are "normalized" in HEIs.	<i>state; gender equality; higher educational institutions; intervention s; multi-level; gender pay gap; gender parity; Irish; professoriate; Athena SWAN</i>
14	Goussinsky, R., Michael, K. and Yassour-Borochowitz, D. (2017) "Relationship dynamics and intimate partner violence among Israeli college students: The moderating effect of communication problems," <i>Journal of Interpersonal Violence</i> , 35(23-24), pp. 5812–5833.	Israel	Quantitative N 2004 = 465 N 2015 = 392	The present study, based on data from the International Dating Violence Study obtained in 2004 (N = 465) and on data obtained in 2015 (N = 392), estimated the prevalence of intimate partner violence (IPV) victimization and perpetration among Israeli college students. The main purpose of the study was to investigate whether communication problems (i.e., avoidant communication and disrespectful communication) intensify the effects of relationship dynamics (dominance, partner's controlling behavior, and jealousy) on physical IPV. A series of χ^2 analyses, independent t tests, and logistic regressions was conducted separately for each sample. Results revealed that in 2015, approximately 20% of the participants reported being a victim of at least one act of physical violence and more than 10% of the participants reported severely attacking a partner. Although there was a significant decline in the prevalence of the severe type of sexual violence victimization, most of the differences between the samples were not significant. The findings further showed that regardless of gender or age,	<i>Dating violence; domestic violence; predicting domestic violence; anything related to domestic violence</i>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260517724833 .			dominance significantly increased the odds of physical violence perpetration, and partner's controlling behavior significantly increased the odds of physical violence victimization. Finally, the interaction effects that were found suggest that when relationships are characterized by an imbalance of power, communication problems may increase the risk of physical violence. The current study provides initial support for the idea that communication difficulties may contribute to conflict escalation and exacerbate the effects of relationship risk factors on physical IPV.	
15	Tozzo, P. et al. (2021) "The usage of mobile apps to fight violence against women: A survey on a sample of female students belonging to an Italian University," International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 18(13), p. 6968. Available at: https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18136968 .	Italy	Quantitative N = 1782	The prevalence of violence against women continues to grow and this plague has had a huge impact from a clinical, social and judicial point of view. For this reason, alongside the efforts made at the legislative level to prevent the phenomenon and to improve assistance to victims in recent years, efforts to contain and better manage this phenomenon have also grown in the extra-legislative sphere: for example, through the application of new technological solutions and safety planning. In recent years, there has been an increase in the marketing of mobile phone apps dedicated to the prevention of violence against women, with different functions and different objectives. The purpose of this study is to investigate the knowledge and propensity to download this type of app in a group of 1782 Italian female university students. This research was performed using an online questionnaire administered to female students attending four different courses (law, medicine, healthcare professionals and political sciences) at one Italian university. Chi-square or Fisher's exact test was used to analyze associations between responses to questionnaire and the type and the year of course. The results show that 62.6% of our sample are unaware of the existence of these apps and that 79.5% of the sample would be willing to download one in the future. With regard to whom to turn to after a violent incident, the majority of those interviewed (43.9%) would turn to the police and not to health facilities. According to our findings, law female students (52.7%) think, more than any other category, that the most effective way to improve public safety and reduce the number of victims lies in legislative solutions. Our results suggest that, although this type of technology may be promising, it is necessary to improve the knowledge and dissemination of these apps in order to make them a useful tool for prevention, education and assistance in cases of violence against women.	<i>mobile apps; violence against women; survey; personal safety</i>

16	<p>Martini, M. and De Piccoli, N. (2020) "Evaluation of USVREACT: A staff training program to prevent sexual violence at universities," <i>Health Education & Behavior</i>, 48(4), pp. 507–515.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1090198120939487.</p>	Italy	Quantitative N = 172	<p>Interventions addressing the endemic of sexual violence at European universities are scarce, particularly those that take a bystander focus to sexual violence prevention and involve university staff. Evidence-based data on their effectiveness are also lacking. This article reports the description of a pilot evaluation study of the USVreact Italian training program addressed to university staff for counteracting sexual violence. We assessed initial (T1) representations of gender-based violence, rape myth acceptance, and attitudes to bystander intervention (172 participants), and evaluated the effectiveness of the course by comparing, via paired-sample t tests, the responses before and after (T2) training (66 participants). Comparison between pre- (T1) and posttraining (T2) responses indicated that the participants' ability to recognize subtle forms of violence and reduce rape myth acceptance was increased after training. Relatively few training programs based on the bystander approach to prevent gender-based violence at university have been performed to date in Europe and data on their effectiveness are scarce. Several limitations notwithstanding, the present pilot evaluation study provides suggestions for a more systematic evaluation of training interventions that address cultural legitimization of gender-based violence and that sustain bystander interventions in sexual assault prevention.</p>	<p><i>College health; formative evaluation; quantitative methods; violent behavior and prevention; worksite health promotion</i></p>
17	<p>Romito, P., Cedolin, C., Bastiani, F., & Saurel-Cubizolles, M.-J. (2019). "Disordered Eating Behaviors and Sexual Harassment in Italian Male and Female University Students." <i>Journal of Interpersonal Violence</i>, 34(14), 2960–2974.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260516664315</p>	Italy	Quantitative N = 759	<p>The aim of this study is to describe sexual harassment among Italian university students and analyze the relationship between harassment and disordered eating behaviors. An observational survey was conducted among university students at Trieste University (Italy) in spring 2014. Students answered an anonymous self-administered questionnaire about sexual harassment, including three domains—sexual harassment, unwanted comments on physical appearance, cyber-harassment—and disordered eating behaviors. The global sexual harassment index was computed with three levels: Level 0, no harassment; Level 1, harassment in at least one of the three domains; and Level 2, harassment in two or three domains. Disordered eating behaviors were classified by at least one of the following: (a) eating without being able to stop or vomiting at least once or twice a month, (b) using laxatives or diuretics at least once or twice a week, (c) monitoring weight every day, and (d) dieting at least very often. The sample included 759 students (347 men and 412 women; 18-29 years old). Experiencing sexual harassment was related to eating disorder symptoms for both genders with a regular gradient: the higher the harassment score, the more frequent the disordered eating behavior symptoms, even after adjusting for age and previous sexual violence. The association was stronger for males than females. Sexual harassment and disordered eating behaviors have long been considered mainly a female problem. Men are not exempt from these problems and in some cases may be more affected than women. The topics should be assessed in men and women.</p>	<p><i>disordered eating behaviors; sexual harassment; cyber harassment; university students; sexual violence</i></p>

18	<p>Bastiani, F., Romito, P. and Saurel-Cubizolles, M.-J. (2018) "Mental distress and sexual harassment in Italian university students," Archives of Women's Mental Health, 22(2), pp. 229–236.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/s00737-018-0886-2.</p>	Italy	Quantitative N = 759	<p>Only a few studies have analyzed the association between sexual harassment (SH) and mental health controlling for other types of violence. The aim of this study was to describe SH among male and female university students and analyze the association between harassment and mental distress controlling for sexual violence. An observational survey was conducted at Trieste University (Italy). Students answered an anonymous questionnaire about harassment that included three domains—sexual harassment, gender harassment, cyber harassment—and three psychological health indicators. The global harassment index was computed, with three levels: 0, no harassment; level 1, harassment in at least one of the three domains; and level 2, harassment in two or three domains. The symptoms of mental distress were measured by the 12-item General Health Questionnaire (GHQ) for depressive symptoms; a question about panic symptoms; and a question about general health. The sample included 759 students (412 women; 18 to 29 years old). After adjustment for age, birth country, couple relationship, employment status, mother's education, and previous sexual violence, the risk of mental distress was increased with harassment exposure. Men were affected in perceived health and depressive symptoms (GHQ score ≥ 6); women were affected in panic symptoms. Harassment has a strong negative impact on the mental health of victims; in some cases, men may be more affected than women. Clinicians should be aware of the negative impact of SH also on men.</p>	Prevalence, association SH and mental distress, student sample
19	<p>Amodeo, A.L., Esposito, C. and Bacchini, D. (2020) "Heterosexist microaggressions, student academic experience and perception of campus climate: Findings from an Italian higher education context," PLOS ONE, 15(4).</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0231580.</p>	Italy	Quantitative N = 471	<p>While overt instances of harassment and violence towards LGBTQ+ individuals have decreased in recent years, subtler forms of heterosexism still shape the social and academic experience of students in higher education contexts. Such forms, defined as microaggressions, frequently include environmental slights that communicate hostile and derogatory messages about one's sexual-minority status. However, there is some evidence suggesting that environmental microaggressions have deleterious effects on all students, regardless of their sexual orientation. The aim of the current study was to examine how heterosexist environmental microaggressions on campus contributed to heterosexual and non-heterosexual students' negative perceptions of campus climate. We also analyzed whether the effect of microaggressions on campus climate was mediated by student social integration on campus. Data were collected in 2018 through an anonymous web-based survey that involved students from a large university of Southern Italy. The sample consisted of 471 students from 18 to 33 years old. Thirty-eight (8.1%) students self-identified as non-heterosexual. Measures included self-reported experiences of environmental microaggressions on campus, student degree of satisfaction with peer-group and student-faculty interactions, perceptions of faculty concern for student development, and of the overall campus climate. The structural equation model showed that heterosexist environmental microaggressions on campus were associated with negative perceptions of campus climate through lowered satisfaction with peer-group interactions and perceptions of faculty concern for student development, for both heterosexual and non-heterosexual students. Overall, the findings of this study suggest that heterosexist microaggressions within campus environments are negatively associated with</p>	No keywords

				students' perceptions of campus climate, regardless of their sexual orientation. Both faculty and peers play an important role in creating an environment that supports the inclusivity of diversity and fosters a greater sense of belonging to the campus community.	
20	<p>Romito, P. et al. (2017) "Sexual harassment and menstrual disorders among Italian university women: A cross-sectional observational study," <i>Scandinavian Journal of Public Health</i>, 45(5), pp. 528–535.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1403494817705559.</p>	Italy	Quantitative N = 349	<p>Aims: Menstrual disorders and sexual harassment are common among young women and interfere with their life and activities. We aimed to describe the association of sexual harassment and menstrual disorders among female university students.</p> <p>Methods: This cross-sectional, observational study examined the association between sexual harassment and menstrual disorders in a sample of 349 university students in Italy. Students answered an anonymous self-administered questionnaire. Descriptive bivariate analyses and logistic regression analyses were performed. Main outcome measures were associations between levels of exposure to sexual harassment (none, levels 1 and 2) and five menstrual disorders (premenstrual symptoms, heavy bleeding, pain, irregular cycles, and amenorrhea).</p> <p>Results: Among the women interviewed (mean age 20.4 ± 1.45 years), 146 (41.8%) had experienced sexual harassment in the previous 12 months: 91 (26.1%) level 1 and 55 (15.7%) level 2. The frequency of premenstrual symptoms was 31.9% (n=110); heavy bleeding, 35.3% (n=124); pain, 51.4% (n=181); irregular cycles, 55.5% (n=195); and amenorrhea, 6.7% (n=23). After adjustment for age, place of birth, being in a couple relationship and receiving hormone therapy, the frequency of menstrual disorders, except for amenorrhea, was increased with sexual harassment, with a regular gradient from no harassment to level 2 harassment. Introducing factors of depression, specific gynaecological problems and lifetime sexual violence did not change the results. For instance, the adjusted odds ratios of premenstrual symptoms were 2.10 [1.19–3.68] for women with level 1 harassment and 3.58 [1.83–7.03] for women with level 2 compared with women without harassment exposure.</p> <p>Conclusions: Sexual harassment is related to the prevalence of menstrual disorders. Healthcare providers should encourage dialogue with patients and address the issue of sexual violence or harassment.</p>	Sexual harassment; sexual violence; menstrual disorders; premenstrual syndrome; dysmenorrhoea; adolescents; young women; students

21	<p>Kelmendi, K. and Baumgartner, F. (2017) "Exploring violence socialization and approval of intimate partner violence among university students in Kosovo," <i>Journal of Interpersonal Violence</i>, 35(5-6), pp. 1081–1107.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260517692336.</p>	Kosovo	Quantitative N = 700	<p>Intimate partner violence (IPV) among university students is a prevalent problem in many countries; however, it is not currently recognized in Kosovo as a social issue in terms of research, prevention, and intervention. The aim of this article was to examine the relationship between violence socialization experiences, approval of violence, and IPV perpetration/victimization among university students in Kosovo. The questionnaires were administered to a convenience sample of 700 students of University of Prishtina who were in relationship for 1 month or longer. The Revised Conflict Tactics Scale (CTS-2) was used for measuring physical, psychological, and sexual violence, whereas for measuring violence socialization and violence approval, scales from Personal and Relationships Profile (PRP) were used. Findings from this study show that there were statistically significant gender differences in terms of socialization and approval of violence among university students. Similarly, perpetrators and victims of IPV (physical, psychological, and sexual violence) showed higher rates of socialization of violence and tolerance toward IPV. Besides, findings indicate that approval of violence mediates the relationship between socialization of violence and IPV perpetration and victimization, for both genders. The implications of the current findings within a cultural context are also discussed.</p>	<p>dating violence; domestic violence; violence exposure; intergenerational transmission of trauma</p>
22	<p>Kamimura, A. et al. (2016) "Factors associated with perpetration of physical intimate partner violence among college students: Russia and Lithuania," <i>Deviant Behavior</i>, 38(2), pp. 130–140.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/01639625.2016.1196954.</p>	Lithuania (and Russia)	Quantitative N = 818	<p>This study examined factors associated with physical IPV perpetration in Russia and Lithuania. The data from the International Dating Violence Study 2001–2006 were analyzed (N= 818). Male and female perpetrators as compared to non-perpetrators of physical IPV have a higher prevalence of being perpetrators of other forms of IPV. Perpetrators of physical IPV as compared to non-perpetrators are more likely to have been victims of IPV. Male and female 'intimate terrorist' perpetrators exhibit different characteristics. Factors associated with IPV are different between male and female perpetrators. Interventions should focus on victimization and perpetration.</p>	<p><i>No keywords</i></p>

23	<p>Lerm Hayes, C.-M. (2020) "Art and research: A portrait of a humanities faculty as an inclusive workspace," <i>Krisis Journal for Contemporary Philosophy</i>, 40(1), pp. 180–202.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.21827/krisis.40.1.37009.</p>	Netherlands	Qualitative	<p>At a time when monuments are falling and learning processes accelerating, it seems apposite to pay attention also to artworks commissioned by established institutions in order to give form to good intentions. This essay focuses on a commissioned portrait of female professors, on art (history) education, Dutch art policy and the former colonial (VOC) site that the University of Amsterdam occupies, in order to aide this institution's desired process to become more inclusive. It proposes Art(istic) Research as a realm that can contribute a thoughtful positioning of research and universities in visual and public domains: a necessary ally. Since the essay was written in Summer 2019 (with additions), much has happened: the Faculty in question has been found to be the locus of ongoing sexual harassment. The student victims did not feel that the (internal) complaints procedures were safeguarding them. They went to the media. A first investigation found no systemic deficiencies. Since George Floyd's death, we know better what "systemic" means. The university's Board has admitted systemic failures. This essay is meant to show that art (history) and philosophy can jointly analyze organizations as a basis for necessary conversations, followed by action . During Covid lock-down, it became deceptively obvious how unimportant art is. An essay such as this, can hopefully show how art can indicate institutional culture: e.g. in relation to how embedded the principle to consult specialists is, even if this seems to be unimportant. And that is a matter of life and death.</p>	<p><i>Universities and art commissions;</i> <i>Artistic research;</i> <i>Universities and gender politics;</i> <i>Intersectionality;</i> <i>UvA history and VOC</i></p>
24	<p>Jussen, L. et al. (2019) "Underreported and unknown student harassment at the Faculty of Science," <i>PLOS ONE</i>, 14(4).</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0215067.</p>	Netherlands	Quantitative N = 613	<p>Reports of sexual harassment at medical faculties throughout the world, including the Radboud University, raised the question how prevalent this is at the Faculty of Science. We performed a survey among students to assess their experiences with harassment. This questionnaire consisted of questions from the EGERA survey, a questionnaire held among staff of multiple European Universities. We found that 9% of the respondents had observed or experienced harassment at the Faculty. Hardly any of these cases were reported to one of the institutional services. Moreover, most students did not now any of the provided services. We therefore suggest raising awareness on harassment and to make students more familiar with the trust person.</p>	<p><i>No keywords</i></p>

25	<p>Trysnes, I. et al. (2022) "Hot case-workers and Squint-eyed whores' - sexual harassment of Norwegian social- and health care students in practical training," NORA - Nordic Journal of Feminist and Gender Research, 30(2), pp. 124–139.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/08038740.2022.2030403.</p>	Norway	<p>Quantitative and qualitative</p> <p>N = 94</p>	<p>Sexual harassment is a societal challenge. Youth, women, students, and health care professionals are some of the groups most at risk for experiencing sexual harassment. In this study, we examine how higher education institutions and practice institutions handle sexual harassment and how students in practical training experience and cope with sexual harassment. A survey and in-depth interviews were conducted among nursing students and social work students at one Norwegian university. Our results indicate that students experience sexual harassment during practice that is an obligatory part of training, that guidance and follow-up are often lacking, and that they experience negative consequences from these incidents. We also identified a range of strategies used to cope with SH, strategies that are not necessarily compatible with a sound development as a health care professional.</p>	<p><i>Sexual harassment; students; higher education institutions; feminist institutionalism; practical training</i></p>
26	<p>Steine, I.M. et al. (2021) "Sexual harassment and assault predict sleep disturbances and is partly mediated by nightmares: Findings from a National Survey of all university students in Norway," Journal of Sleep Research, 30(6).</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1111/jsr.13338.</p>	Norway	<p>Quantitative</p> <p>N = 49 051</p>	<p>Sexual harassment and assault is common in most domains of society, and has been linked to several adverse outcomes, including reduced sleep quality. However, less is known about the possible impact of sexual harassment and assault on various sleep problems among university students. In a sample of 49,051 students in Norway (69.2% women), we examined i) the associations of varying extents of sexual harassment (unwanted sexual comments, looks or gestures, photographs, indecent exposure, and physical harassment) and sexual assault (attempted or completed rape), with</p> <p>meeting Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, fifth edition (DSM-5) diagnostic criteria of insomnia and with sleep duration, ii) the association of cumulative exposure to sexual harassment/assault with insomnia and sleep duration, and iii) to what extent nightmares could explain the association between sexual harassment and insomnia and sleep duration. For both genders, all forms of harassments with the exception of "indecent exposure" and "unwanted sexual photographs" for men were negatively associated with sleep duration, with the strongest associations being found for "rape" and "attempted rape". For both genders, the odds of insomnia increased as a function of cumulative harassment exposure. Similarly, a graded, negative association was found between cumulative harassment and sleep duration for both genders. Mediation analyses showed that 28% of the observed association between cumulative harassment and insomnia, and 15% of the association between cumulative harassment and sleep duration, was mediated by frequency of nightmares.</p>	<p><i>dose–response association; mediation; nightmare; insomnia; sexual abuse victims; sleep duration; student sample</i></p>

27	<p>Sivertsen, B. et al. (2019) "Sexual harassment and assault among university students in Norway: A cross-sectional prevalence study," <i>BMJ Open</i>, 9(6).</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-026993.</p>	Norway	<p>Quantitative</p> <p>N = 50 054</p>	<p>Objective: The aim of the current study was to provide estimates of both overall and specific forms of sexual harassment among male and female college and university students.</p> <p>Design and setting: Data stem from a recent national student health survey from 2018 for higher education in Norway (the SHoT study (Students' Health and Wellbeing Study)).</p> <p>Participants: 50 054 full-time students (69.1% women) aged 18–35 years participated, yielding a response rate of 31%.</p> <p>Main outcome measure: Sexual harassment was defined according to Norwegian legal regulations, and was assessed by self-report on seven items covering verbal, non-verbal and physical sexual harassment. We also collected data on the timeframe and frequency of the sexual harassment, in addition to the formal position of the perpetrator of the harassment.</p> <p>Results: Lifetime sexual harassment was reported by 24.2% (women 31.3%, men 8.0%), while 16.7% (women 21.6%, men 5.7%) reported having been sexually harassed within the past year. The most common forms of lifetime (ever having experienced) sexual harassments were 'sexual expressions, suggestions or comments about your body' and 'unwanted touching, hugging or kissing' (both 15.4%), while rape and rape attempt were reported by 3.4% and 2.1%, respectively. Exposure to all forms of past-year sexual harassments was significantly more common among women and the youngest age cohorts. Fellow students committed the past-year sexual harassment in 18%–29% of the instances, while a university staff member was reported to have committed the harassment in 0.6%–4.6% of cases.</p> <p>Conclusion: Given the potential consequences suffered by those exposed to sexual harassment and assault, both the institutions and student welfare organisations should intensify their efforts to put the theme on the agenda and provide both legal and health services to victims of sexual harassment. The low response rate means that care should be taken in interpreting and generalising the findings to the whole student population.</p>	<i>No keywords</i>
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28	<p>Tomaszewska, P. and Krahé, B. (2015) "Sexual aggression victimization and perpetration among female and male university students in Poland," <i>Journal of Interpersonal Violence</i>, 33(4), pp. 571–594.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260515609583</p>	Poland	<p>Quantitative N = 565</p>	<p>This study examined the prevalence of victimization and perpetration of sexual aggression since age 15 in a convenience sample of 565 Polish university students (356 females). The prevalence of sexual aggression was investigated for both males and females from the perspectives of both victims and perpetrators in relation to three coercive strategies, three different victim-perpetrator relationships, and four types of sexual acts. We also examined the extent to which alcohol was consumed in the context of sexually aggressive incidents. The overall self-reported victimization rate was 34.3% for females and 28.4% for males. The overall perpetration rate was 11.7% for males and 6.5% for females. The gender difference was significant only for perpetration. Prevalence rates of both victimization and perpetration were higher for people known to each other than for strangers. In the majority of victimization and perpetration incidents, alcohol was consumed by one or both parties involved. The findings are discussed in relation to the international evidence and the need for tailored risk prevention and reduction programs.</p>	<p><i>Sexual aggression; victimization; perpetration; alcohol; Poland</i></p>
29	<p>Lickiewicz, J. et al. (2019) "Perceptions of fear, likelihood of victimization, and confidence about dangerous situations among university women in Poland," <i>Journal of Interpersonal Violence</i>, 36(21-22), pp. 10660–10685.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/088626051988190</p>	Poland	<p>Quantitative N = 208</p>	<p>Polish women have not been studied in regard to fear, likelihood, or confidence about dangerous situations, nor has there been an instrument to measure those perceptions. The purpose of the study was fourfold: first, to present the Polish translation and validation of the Perception of Dangerous Situations Scale (PDSS-P) and second, to assess Polish women's perceived fear, likelihood, and confidence about dangerous situations using the PDSS-P (41 items). The third purpose was to determine to what degree the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES) and/or the Hope for Success Scale (KNS) correlated with any of the three subscales of the PDSS-P. The fourth purpose was to determine the congruence of the PDSS-P to the original PDSS. Two other tools (GSES and KNS) were administered to determine concurrent validity with the PDSS. A sample of 208 women aged 19 to 27 years (M = 21.04, SD = 1.88) participated in the study. Five factors were determined for each subscale, similar to the original version of the PDSS. Women reported they were more afraid of being raped by a stranger than being murdered. Their estimation of the likelihood of some serious events occurring was not congruent with statistical realities. The women thought the least likely events to happen to them in the next year would be being raped or beaten by someone they know, or being held prisoner by someone who wanted to murder them. Confidence to manage dangerous situations was low in cases of being raped by strangers or known people, being kidnapped, or being attacked. The GSES and KNS provided useful information, in that they did not measure the same constructs as the PDSS-P.</p>	<p><i>Fear of crime; General Self-Efficacy Scale; Hope for Success Scale; Perceptions of Dangerous Situations Scale; risk; safety; security; self-efficacy</i></p>

30	<p>Aleksiu, N. (2022) "Crossing the line: Violence against Jewish women and the new model of antisemitism in Poland in the 1930s," <i>Jewish Women in Modern Eastern and East Central Europe</i>, pp. 133–162.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-19463-4_6.</p>	Poland	Qualitative	<p>This article examines anti-Jewish violence in the Second Polish Republic through the lens of gender. By focusing on verbal and physical attacks against female Jewish students at Polish universities in the 1930s, it highlights the radicalization of the antisemitic movement among Poland's future elite. Jewish women experienced discrimination and increasingly also violence at Polish universities as Jews and as women. The assaults suggest the need to examine both gender and Jewish differences. Although all Jewish students were targets of violent antisemitic attacks, women were especially vulnerable when they dared transgress gender boundaries by acting in "unfeminine ways" and signifying their intellectual empowerment— talking back, resisting, or defending Jewish men under attack. Indeed, Jewish women who stood up to their attackers transgressed the norms of both gender and Jewishness, and were thus doubly exposed to aggression and violence. Using the contemporary Jewish press, university archives, memoirs and testimonies, the female Jewish experience and the response of male Jewish students and community activists are reconstructed. Understanding these assaults as a window into gender politics in Jewish student associations, the Jewish press and Jewish communal institutions, the author examines their place in the public discourse of the Second Polish Republic.</p>	<p><i>Violence; gender; interwar Poland; universities; Jewish students</i></p>
31	<p>Azevedo, V., Nunes, L.M. and Sani, A. (2022) "Is campus a place of (in)security and crime? perceptions and predictors among higher education students," <i>European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education</i>, 12(2), pp. 193–208.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.3390/ejihpe12020015.</p>	Portugal	Quantitative N = 775	<p>This paper addresses subjective insecurity, namely perceptions of (in)security and criminal variables on campus among Portuguese higher education students. Additionally, predictors of perceptions of (in)security and gender differences were also examined. The participants were 775 students and data were collected through the "Diagnosis of Local Security Questionnaire". Robbery, physical assault, theft, and sexual offenses were the most feared crimes. Additionally, robbery, theft, and public property damage were perceived as the most common on campus. Alcohol/drug consumption and juvenile conflicts/delinquency were the main reasons justifying criminal occurrences. Sociodemographic variables such as gender, age, education, and years of campus attendance, as well as criminal variables (e.g., perceived trend of crime, criminal occurrences, and crime promoters) predicted perceptions of (in)security. Females reported more fear than males of robbery, sexual offenses, physical aggression, and domestic violence. Therefore, preventive measures, including in the social domain and physical spaces, are mandatory to reduce violence on campus.</p>	<p><i>Violence; college; university; criminality; diagnosis of local security; subjective insecurity</i></p>

32	<p>Costa, F. (2020) "Borderless a study of violence against women in universities: Brazil, Portugal, and the U.K.," <i>Journal of international women's studies</i>, 21(2), pp. 169–177.</p> <p>Available at: https://vc.bridgew.edu/iwjs/vol21/iss2/14/</p>	Portugal, (UK, +Brazil)	Qualitative	<p>Brazilian university students report cases of rape on campus. In Portugal, young women experience humiliation and sexism when they enter university. In the UK, protests in an academic context put to the test policies for women. These narratives are present in a postdoctoral research project that will discuss violence against women in universities. One of the products resulting from this work will be a documentary that attempts to deal with the subjective perceptions of teachers, technicians, and students about gender violence in the Academy. Focusing on feminist epistemology that values experience as a way of knowing, this research has women as protagonists in both the denunciations and the execution of a video-activism on the subject.</p>	<p><i>Violence against women; sexual harassment; sexual violence; campus violence; Video-activism; university life; on campus.</i></p>
33	<p>Columban, A., Buse, M. and Macarie, C. (2020) "Students' sense and sensibilities. an exploratory study of gender perceptions at Romania's largest university," <i>Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences</i>, (61 E), pp. 5–24.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.24193/tras.61E.1</p>	Romania	Quantitative N = 275	<p>Academia is one of the main hubs for promoting gender equality and non-discrimination, yet very few programs in Romania actively tackle the topic. An assessment of students' perceptions is thus necessary in order to identify the level of awareness around gender issues and potential barriers hindering an inclusive academic environment. The present exploratory study aims to fill this gap by providing information on four dimensions of gender equality: attitudes towards gender equality, prevalence of gender stereotypes, gender-based violence and sexual harassment, and gender-based discrimination. The questionnaire was applied online and offline between October 2018 and March 2019 to 275 students enrolled in Bachelor, Master and Doctoral studies at BabeşBolyai University, Cluj-Napoca. The study found that students had a rather high awareness about gender issues in general and held favorable views towards gender equality and its enforcement. However, female students were more prone to stereotype, claiming more traits for themselves, and were more likely than their male counterparts to experience sexual harassment and discrimination regarding professional promotion. A series of implications for practitioners and recommendations are also discussed.</p>	<p><i>Gender equality; gender stereotypes; violence against women; discrimination; tertiary education; survey research.</i></p>
34	<p>Ferrer-Pérez, V.A. and Bosch-Fiol, E. (2020) "Sexual harassment at a Spanish public university: an examination of victims' experiences by gender and campus status," <i>JOURNAL OF GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE</i>, 4(1), pp. 41–58.</p>	Spain	Quantitative N students: 1521 N staff: 72	<p>The current study analyses the prevalence of sexual harassment among staff and undergraduate students at a Spanish public university. The EASIS-U, a 38-item questionnaire, was administered to a sample of 1,521 university students, and 172 staff members. Results show that 26.4% of teaching and research staff (TRS), 28.3% of administrative staff (AS), and 15.9% of the students had experienced at least one episode of sexual blackmail behaviour; 30.9% of TRS, 27.0% of AS and 16.0% of the students had experienced at least one episode of physical sexual harassment; and 23.7% of TRS, 34.4% of AS and 17.1% of the students had experienced at least one episode of verbal sexual harassment. A comparison of staff and students revealed significant differences in prevalence rates, with staff reporting higher rates of unwanted contact than students. Contrary to expectations,</p>	<p><i>Sexual harassment; prevalence; victims' experiences; university; Spain</i></p>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.1332/239868019X15764491770571			male students reported more sexual harassment than did female students. We analyse the possible reasons for these results.	
35	Osuna-Rodríguez, M. <i>et al.</i> (2020) "Perception of gender-based violence and sexual harassment in university students: Analysis of the information sources and risk within a relationship," <i>International journal of environmental research and public health</i> , 17(11), p. 3754. Available at: https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17113754	Spain	Quantitative N = 268	In a truly democratic society, there should be no place for any kind of discrimination or violence. Among the basic tools for eradicating discrimination and violence against women, education has a crucial role to play. Education about gender should be considered at all levels, in all year groups and across the curriculum, so as to improve education about this subject. Although these matters are increasingly addressed, at university level, including at postgraduate level, they are often forgotten. The purpose of this study is to break down the level of knowledge of gender-based violence and/or sexual stalking, the sources of information most widely used for developing this knowledge, and beliefs about situations of risk in relationships among a sample of 268 Science and Social Science students at the University of Córdoba (Spain). The analysis was descriptive, comparative and correlative. Means and standard deviations were analyzed, and correlations were used to establish possible relations among the variables. Cluster analysis was used to distribute the sample with respect to knowledge of violence and Student's t-test was used to identify differences between groups. The chi-squared test was used to find the association between variables such as situations of violence and places of residence. The results show that, although the experience of gender-based violence is among the least common sources of violence, there is evidence that these situations do exist, and the risk of violent acts and/or stalking is greater when couples break up. The perception of risk is higher when students have a greater knowledge of gender-based violence or sexual harassment and this perception is higher in women. As expected, greater knowledge is also associated with experience of this type of situation; however, place of residence was not linked to greater or lesser knowledge. Training in gender is considered essential and necessary in the university environment.	<i>student training; gender studies; gender-based violence; sexual harassment; university</i>

36	<p>Moral, M. V. & Pietro, P. (2022). Emotional Dependence and Partner Cyber Abuse Through Social Networks in Spanish University Students. <i>Revista Iberoamericana de Psicología y Salud</i>, 13(1), 15-27.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.23923/j.rips.2022.01.051</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 627	<p>The cyber abuse of a partner in young people is increasingly normalized and is associated with maladaptive relational patterns.</p> <p>Objective: Analyze the relationship between emotional dependence and control of the partner through social networks in the sentimental relationships of young people.</p> <p>Methods: 627 Spanish university students with an age range between 18 and 26 years (M = 21.27; SD = 1.72) participated in this study. Participants were evaluated in emotional dependence, risk of addiction to social networks, and cyberbullying perpetration and victimization.</p> <p>Results: Significant and positive relations were obtained among emotional dependence, cyber-control and victimization of online aggression. Likewise, it was found that boys exercised more control online towards their partners and that girls with emotional dependence had greater risk of addiction to new technologies.</p> <p>Conclusions: The link between emotional dependence and cyber-abuse in the couple is established, so that the need to promote proposals for prevention and psychosocial intervention is emphasized.</p>	<p><i>Emotional dependence; control; online; partner cyberabuse; young people</i></p>
37	<p>Beregal-Bolsas, M. <i>et al.</i> (2022) "Variables associated with a higher awareness of gender-based violence by students of the health sciences and social work," <i>Gaceta sanitaria</i>, 36(2), pp. 146–151.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaceta.2020.09.005</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 437	<p>Objective: To determine the attitudes towards equality and prevention of gender-based violence, and analyze variables associated with a higher awareness of gender-based violence by students of the health sciences and social work degrees. Method: A cross-sectional descriptive study was carried out. The sample consisted of 437 students of the health sciences and social work degrees at the University of Zaragoza (Spain) during 2018 and 2019. The variables of the study were: Socio-demographic variables, academic variables, feminism attitudes towards women's movement using Feminism and the women's movement scale (FWMS), attitudes on gender-based violence using the Gender Equality and Prevention of Gender-based Violence Scale (GEPGVS). A correlational study and multiple linear regression were performed, in order to analyze the associated variables.</p> <p>Results: Differences in attitudes towards gender-based violence were observed according to sex, age and attitudes in line with the feminist movement. Regarding the linear regression model, the results showed that the FWMS is a predictor of GEPGVS, as well as sex.</p> <p>Conclusions: Holding attitudes in line with the feminist movement is a factor that may be promoted in order to increase the awareness of gender-based violence.</p>	<p><i>Gender-based violence; awareness; health science and social work university students</i></p>

38	<p>Rodríguez-Rodríguez, I. and Heras-González, P. (2020) "How are universities using Information and Communication Technologies to face sexual harassment and how can they improve?," <i>Technology in society</i>, 62, p. 101274.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101274</p>	Spain	Qualitative	<p>Sadly, in 2020, sexual harassment and harassment on the grounds of sex are still a major social problem. In the digital era, these have acquired new aspects, but there are also new technological tools to fight against them. Usually public organizations have instruments to deal with these issues, but the presence of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) is minimal if at all. In this paper, we will show the scarce presence of these new technological measures in universities, and with a review of the literature, offer a set of measures to improve the management of sexual harassment and harassment on the grounds of sex. As a case study, we will present the situation of ICT in sexual harassment management in Spanish public universities.</p>	<p><i>Sexual harassment; university protocol; information and communication technologies</i></p>
39	<p>García-Díaz, V. <i>et al.</i> (2020) "Tolerance of intimate partner violence and sexist attitudes among health sciences students from three Spanish universities," <i>Gaceta sanitaria</i>, 34(2), pp. 179–185.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaceta.2019.01.003</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 1322	<p>Objective: To explore university health science students' intimate partner violence tolerance and sexist attitudes and to examine their trend throughout the academic years.</p> <p>Methods: Cross-sectional study of students of both sexes of the degrees of medicine, nursing, and psychology from three selected Spanish universities (n = 1,322). Data were collected anonymously using two validated scales: the Dating Violence Questionnaire (DVQ-R) and the Gender Role Attitudes Scale (GRAS). Logistic regressions were used to compare tolerance toward violence and sexist attitudes across the degrees. The evolution of these variables throughout different academic courses was assessed.</p> <p>Results: Of the sample, 62.8% were tolerant towards intimate partner violence. The percentage of tolerant students was significantly higher in Psychology (75.9%) than in Nursing (57.7%) and Medicine Degrees (60.3%). A higher percentage of sexist students was also found in psychology students (80.8%) than in nursing (62.2%) and medicine students (62.7%). Compared to the first-year students, female medicine students of the last courses were less tolerant to intimate partner violence (p-trend <0.001), and male medicine students had less sexist attitudes (p-trend = 0.002).</p> <p>Conclusions: Tolerance of intimate partner violence and sexist attitudes were very high, especially among psychology students. These indicators were significantly better among medicine students of higher courses, suggesting a positive effect of medical training. Intimate partner violence in the university education of the future health professionals should be addressed.</p>	<p><i>Intimate partner violence; sexism; attitudes; gender identity; health occupations students; universities</i></p>

40	<p>Víllora, B., Navarro, R. and Yubero, S. (2021) "The Role of Social-Interpersonal and Cognitive-Individual Factors in Cyber Dating Victimization and Perpetration: Comparing the Direct, Control, and Combined Forms of Abuse," <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i>, 36(17-18), pp. 8559–8584.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260519851172</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 1657	<p>The present study examined the relationship linking social-interpersonal factors (interpersonal dependency, social support, social skills), cognitive-individual factors (planning behavior and goal efficacy), and different victimization and perpetration forms of cyber dating abuse (direct abuse, control abuse, and the combination of both abuse types). The responses of 1,657 Spanish university students were analyzed (62.1% females, 37.1% males). The multinomial logistic regression model revealed similarities among the three victim groups and revealed that anxious attachment and lack of social support increased the likelihood of direct victimization, control victimization, and direct/control victimization. Differences were found in the three victim groups for social skills and planning behavior. Perpetration was significantly associated with anxious attachment in the three cyber dating perpetration forms. Differences were also found in emotional dependency, social support, and social skills among direct perpetrators, control perpetrators, and direct/ control perpetrators. The results revealed that interpersonal and cognitive factors correlated with cyber dating victimization and perpetration.</p>	<p><i>Cyber dating abuse; interpersonal dependency; resilience; social support; social skills; university students</i></p>
41	<p>Martín-Baena, D. <i>et al.</i> (2019) "The link between violence and suicidal behavior among female university students in Spain," <i>Journal of school violence</i>, 18(2), pp. 216–225.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/15388220.2018.1453823</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 540	<p>Objective: To explore the association between violence and suicidal behavior in female university students. Method: A convenience sample of 540 female students enrolled in the Nursing and Teacher Training Faculties at the University of Valencia was selected. Violence by partners, non-partners, and both was compared with suicidal thoughts and suicide attempts. An adjusted logistic regression and the Wald Test were performed to explore whether the effect on student's suicidal behavior differed if a partner or others committed violence. Results: 18.1% reported suicidal thoughts in the last month and 2.4% had attempted suicide in the past five years. Suicidal behavior was significantly higher in abused than in non-abused students, although the magnitude was higher when committed by a non-partner. Conclusions: All forms of violence are strongly associated with suicidal behavior. Understanding the relationship between violence and suicidal thoughts and attempts is a priority for reducing suicide behavior in young women.</p>	<p><i>Suicidal thoughts; suicide attempts; violence; women; university students</i></p>

42	<p>Canto, J.M. <i>et al.</i> (2020) "The influence of ideological variables in the denial of violence against women: The role of sexism and social dominance orientation in the Spanish context," <i>International journal of environmental research and public health</i>, 17(14), pp. 1–11.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17144934</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 215	<p>Violence against women in heterosexual intimate relationships is a major social problem with serious physical and psychological consequences for the victims. There is a line of research that seeks to analyze how ideological variables and contextual variables influence the way in which this type of violence is perceived. This study analyzed the relationship between hostile sexism, benevolent sexism and social dominance in the acceptance of the myths about violence against women in intimate relationships. A total of 215 Spanish university students (125 women and 90 men) participated in the research. The results indicate that hostile sexism and social dominance orientation act as factors that influence the acceptance of such myths in men. Benevolent sexism did not act in this way. The data reconfirm the importance of hostile sexism and social dominance orientation in the perception of violence against women, in this case, that which is committed by their partners (or ex-partners) in the area of intimate relationships.</p>	<i>sexism; social dominance orientation; violence against women</i>
43	<p>Villacampa, C. and Pujols, A. (2017) "Stalking victimisation: Prevalence and dynamics amongst Spanish university students," <i>European journal of crime, criminal law, and criminal justice</i>, 25(4), pp. 347–370</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1163/15718174-02504003</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 1162	<p>Stalking was recently criminalised in Spain and other European countries, following the signing of the Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence, despite a lack of empirical knowledge of victimisation by this phenomenon. Previous research carried out in the USA and in other European countries on victimisation by stalking with female samples has shown that young women are the most frequently victimised group. Based on those findings, research was conducted in Spain with a sample of 1,162 university students, including women and men. This paper presents the main findings of this research, determining the prevalence of stalking victimisation, the victim and stalker profiles, and the dynamics of this type of victimisation.</p>	<i>Stalking; victimisation prevalence; victim profile; offender profile; dynamics</i>
44	<p>Blanco, V. <i>et al.</i> (2022) "Sexual Victimization and Mental Health in Female University Students," <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i>, 37(15-16), pp. NP14215–NP14238.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/08862605211005148</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 871	<p>Although sexual assaults on female university students are a public health concern, studies that have examined this issue have not used behaviorally specific definitions of the various types of sexual victimization. Furthermore, hardly any data exists on female Spanish university students. The objectives of this study were to analyze the prevalence of different forms of sexual assault against female Spanish university students, determine the risk factors associated with sexual assault, analyze the association between sexual victimization and mental health problems, and determine the differential risk of more serious types of sexual assault. A cross-sectional study was conducted among a random sample of 871 students from the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) (mean age 20.7 years, SD = 2.8). The current study assessed various types of sexual violence (i.e., unwanted sexual contact, attempted coercion, coercion, attempted rape, rape), as well as rates of depression, anxiety, stress, eating disorders, substance abuse, suicide risk, and suicide attempts. Of the female students surveyed, 28.5% had</p>	<i>Sexual violence; university; women; rape; mental health; mental disorders; Spanish</i>

				suffered some form of sexual violence during the previous year, 22.3% reported unwanted sexual contact, 8.8% attempted coercion, 6.5% coercion, 10.4% attempted rape, and 7.9% had been raped. Lower risk was associated with having a partner and being heterosexual. Being 18 years of age and prior experiences of sexual victimization were associated with higher risk. Being the victim of attempted coercion was associated with a higher risk of depression, while victims of attempted rape were at higher risk for substance use. Rape victims were at the highest risk for all mental health conditions studied, with the exception of suicide attempts. Due to the high rates at which Spanish female university students experience sexual violence, planning and resources are needed to address their mental health needs, especially those who are victims of rape.	
45	Gallardo-Nieto, E.M. <i>et al.</i> (2021) "Sexual orientation, gender identity and gender expression-based violence in Catalan universities: qualitative findings from university students and staff," <i>Archives of public health = Archives belges de santé publique</i> , 79(1), p. 16. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1186/s13690-021-00532-4	Spain	Qualitative	Background: Hate crimes have raised in Spain and the gender and sexuality-based conflicts persist worldwide which leads to this problem having an effect on health and wellbeing. Following a focus of transforming Higher Education Institutions, this research analysed the problem that affects undergraduate students in six Spanish universities. The research goal is to improve the life quality of lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and intersex university students, breaking the silence that exists around the violence that this group suffer in Catalonia, Spain. Methods: Following the Communicative Methodology, this study has identified violence based on sexual orientation, gender identity or gender expression in the target universities and provided guidelines to improve antidiscrimination protocols. A qualitative method has reached experiences of university students, heads of equality commissions, professors and administrative staff regarding this conflict. Focussing on the qualitative research tools, 30 semi-structured interviews were conducted with university students and staff around issues related to the violence against lesbian, gay, bisexual transgender, queer and intersex students: 1) perception of violence and discrimination, 2) institutional measures, 3) actions against violence. An analysis of exclusionary and transformative dimensions was used to identify emergent themes. Results: We have identified two dimensions for the analysis given their impact in contributing or overcoming violence: exclusionary and transformative. A wide range of forms of violence on the grounds of sexual orientation, gender identity and gender expression perpetrated at universities have been identified as exclusionary facts and described by participants in the study. Equality commissions have not received reports of violence based on sexual orientation, gender identity or gender expression, and university staff shows certain unfamiliarity regarding the measures and politics to prevent and intervene in cases of violence against the lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and intersex community. Among the results identified as transformative are the ways through which actions of lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and intersex groups against violence and the professors' commitment to intervene have a relevant impact on student's wellbeing. An improvement and implementation of antidiscrimination protocols with mandatory applicability has also been documented.	<i>Violence; discrimination; social problem; health education; universities; sexual orientation; gender identity</i>

				Conclusions: Findings highlight the need of collecting more evidence that contributes to the improvement of protocols, measures and politics to protect all the members of the university community. A better understanding of violence based on sexual orientation, gender identity and gender expression in HEI's may guide national and international governments to improve the health and well-being of lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and intersex persons.	
46	Puigvert, L. <i>et al.</i> (2019) "Resistance to and Transformations of Gender-Based Violence in Spanish Universities: A Communicative Evaluation of Social Impact," <i>Journal of mixed methods research</i> , 13(3), pp. 361–380. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689817731170	Spain	Mixed methods	Researchers in many fields, especially those engaged in the study of gender-based violence, have shown an interest in using mixed designs as innovative methodological procedures to transform social realities. In this article, we introduce the "communicative evaluation of social impact" as a methodological tool to reveal the social impact achieved by a multiphase mixed methods design conducted sequentially on gender-based violence in Spanish universities. This tool shows the transformative power of mixed methods with a communicative orientation to generate new legislation, create proper conditions for reporting abuse, and establish new solidarity dynamics with and among the victims to promote violence-free universities.	<i>Mixed methods; communicative evaluation of social impact; gender-based violence</i>
47	Recalde-Esnoz, I., Castillo, H.D. and Montalvo, G. (2021) "Sexual Assault Myths Acceptance in University Campus: Construction and Validation of a Scale," <i>Social sciences (Basel)</i> , 10(12), p. 462. Available at: https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci10120462	Spain	Quantitative N = 367	The study related to the myths of rape has been carried out since the 1980s at different scales. However, the interaction between the acceptance of these rape myths (myths related to sexual abuse) and the nightlife scene—where alcohol consumption becomes the epi-center of this particular context—has not been specifically evaluated. In this work, a questionnaire has been developed considering different scales. It has been tested online in a population of 367 first-year undergraduate students at the University of Alcalá (Spain). The results of the exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis, as well as the reliability ones, indicate the adequacy of the scale construction and validation process for the university student population. In addition, the results obtained, in line with the specialized literature, indicate that the consumption of alcohol and other drugs appear as justifying elements of sexual violence, exonerating the aggressors and perpetrating the victim.	<i>Scale; validation; university campus; rape myths; sexual assault</i>

48	<p>Lombardo, E. and Bustelo, M. (2022) "Sexual and sexist harassment in Spanish universities: policy implementation and resistances against gender equality measures," <i>Journal of gender studies</i>, 31(1), pp. 8–22.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/09589236.2021.1924643</p>	Spain	Mixed methods	<p>The legal mandate to mainstream gender equality in Spain's universities has led to the establishment of gender equality units and the adoption of gender equality policy plans and protocols against sexual harassment. This research looks at how gender equality policies have been implemented within universities and what resisting and facilitating factors have hindered and promoted their implementation. These questions are addressed by studying the implementation of the 'Protocol against sexual and sexist harassment' at the biggest public Spanish university, Madrid Complutense University. Through a combination of content analysis, interviews, and a survey involving the university community, we show how the implementation of university policies against sexual harassment is dependent on a combination of factors against (obstacles/resistances) and in favour (opportunities/alliances). These factors include the form of institutionalization that gender equality took within the university, the existing formal and informal institutions, inertial resistances, and prevailing ideas about gender equality. We argue that implementation of the protocol was impeded by the scant awareness of the prevalence of harassment in daily university life, and the concomitant acceptance, by the academic community, of the phenomenon as a 'normal' practice.</p>	<p><i>Gender equality policies in universities; policy implementation; Spain; higher education</i></p>
49	<p>Durán, M., Megías, J.L. and Moya, M. (2018) "Male Peer Support to Hostile Sexist Attitudes Influences Rape Proclivity," <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i>, 33(14), pp. 2180–2196.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260515624212</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 134	<p>Sexual assault affects a large proportion of women in the world. Although most rapes are committed by one man, the act itself may be influenced by many (e.g., the peer group). Hostile sexism (HS) has repeatedly been associated with men's rape proclivity, but the influence exerted by the HS of the peer group on rape proclivity has not been investigated. In this study, we explored the impact of perceived male peer support to HS on participants' rape proclivity. A sample of Spanish undergraduate students from a university in the south of Spain (N = 134) completed the Ambivalent Sexism Inventory. Immediately afterwards, they received feedback on the supposed sexist responses of a peer group (high vs. low in HS); we kept the benevolent sexism (BS) of the peer group at medium levels. Next, we assessed participants' rape proclivity using acquaintance rape scenarios. Results showed an interaction between participants' own levels of HS and information about the HS of the peer group. Men high in HS reported higher rape proclivity in the high-HS peer-group condition than in the low-HS peer-group condition. By contrast, information on the peer group did not affect self-reported rape proclivity of men low in HS. Results also corroborated the relationship between participants' levels of HS and rape proclivity, and expanded the literature by revealing an unexpected influence of participants' BS on rape proclivity.</p>	<p><i>Ambivalent sexism; peer influence; rape proclivity; sexual violence</i></p>

50	<p>Dueñas, J.-M. <i>et al.</i> (2021) "Identifying violence against the LGBTI community in Catalan universities," <i>Life sciences, society and policy</i>, 17(1), p. 3.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1186/s40504-021-00112-y</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 571	<p>Social struggles have led to the legal recognition of the rights of LGBTI+ people in some countries. Even so, violence against LGBTI+ people is a social problem throughout the world, and has resulted in the vulnerability and victimization of the members of this group. In Spain, no research has been published to date that analyzes this problem in the university context. Considering the scarcity of studies on the identification of this type of violence in Spain, the main objective of this study was to identify violence against LGBTI+ people in Catalan universities. We administered a battery of questions to a sample of 571 university students from six universities in Catalonia (77.8% women) between 17 and 55 years old (M= 21.0; SD = 3.96). Of the 12 situations of violence presented, psychological violence was identified as the most common type. Within our sample, 61.0% reported either being aware of or having experienced some type of violence related to the university context and motivated by the sexual orientation, gender identity, or gender expression of the victim. The results also show that these types of violence in the university context are rarely reported, especially when they do not include physical violence. This study highlights a previously unreported problem and identifies future research avenues in university contexts.</p>	<p><i>Violence; LGBTI+ students; university students; sexual orientation; gender identity; gender expression</i></p>
51	<p>Llano-Suarez, A. <i>et al.</i> (2021) "Gender roles and intimate partner violence among female university students in Spain: A cross-sectional study," <i>PLoS one</i>, 16(11), p. e0259839.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0259839</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 1005	<p>Background: Traditional gender roles (GRs) have a considerable influence on relationships among couples. These can lead to negative health effects in women; however, their impact on intimate partner violence (IPV) has been less explored, especially among younger women.</p> <p>Objective: To explore the association between traditional GRs and several indicators of IPV on a sample of Spanish female university students involved in heterosexual dating relationships. Methods Across-sectional study involving female university students (n = 1,005) pursuing ten degrees (four Health Science degrees and six Social Sciences degrees). Data were collected using two validated scales: 1) the Questionnaire on the Gender Determinants of Contraception (COGANT), used to examine four traditional GRs (submissive, blind, and passive attitudes of female students, and male dominance), and 2) the Dating Violence Questionnaire-R (DVQ-R) scale, used to measure five types of IPV-behaviors (coercion, detachment, humiliation, sexual violence, and physical violence), perceived fear, entrapment, and abuse. Logistic and linear regressions were conducted to study the association between GR and a series of IPV indicators in dating relationships.</p> <p>Results: Traditional GRs were highly prevalent (57.0% submissive, 52.0% blind attitude, 75.7% passive, and 31.7% identified their boyfriend as being dominant). Up to 66.3% experienced some type of violent behavior. All GRs were significantly associated with IPV indicators. A submissive attitude in female students was the GR that was most strongly associated to total IPV-behavior (adjusted odd ratio [OR] = 3.18; 95% confidence interval [CI]: 2.29–4.42), followed by male dominance (OR =2.79: 95%CI:1.71: 4.54). Both GRs were also highly associated with perceived fear, entrapment, and abuse.</p> <p>Conclusions: A high presence of traditional GRs was found in the relationships held by female university students,</p>	<p><i>No keywords</i></p>

				which was significantly associated with IPV indicators. Universities must adopt policies for gender equality and raise awareness on dating violence.	
52	<p>Ruiz-Eugenio, L. <i>et al.</i> (2020) "Female university students' preferences for different types of sexual relationships: implications for gender-based violence prevention programs and policies," <i>BMC women's health</i>, 20(1), p. 266.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-020-01131-1</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 191	<p>Background: Gender-based violence among young women is a growing problem worldwide. The consequences of this victimization have been well reported in the scientific literature, among which negative health outcomes stand out. The factors influencing this problem are many; one highlighted by research is socialization into a dominant coercive discourse that associates sexual-affective attraction to males with violent attitudes and behaviors, while in turn, such discourse empties males with egalitarian behaviors from sexual attractiveness. This coercive discourse may be shaping the sexual preferences of female youth. The current paper explores young women's preferences for different types of sexual relationships and, more particularly, for what type of sexual affective relationships they coercively preferred men with violent attitudes and behavior.</p> <p>Methods: A quantitative, mixed-design vignette study was conducted with 191 college females in Spain. We focused the analysis only on responses about vignettes including narratives of men with violent attitudes and behaviors. In addition, we examined whether participants would report higher coerced preferences for violent men when asked about the coerced preferences of their female friends than when asked about their own preferences.</p> <p>Results: Only 28.95% of participants responded that their female friends would prefer a young man with violent behavior for a stable relationship, meanwhile 58.42% would do it for hooking up. When reporting about themselves, the difference was greater: 28.42% would prefer a young man with violent behavior for hooking up and just 5.78% for a stable relationship. Conclusions: The dominant coercive discourse that links attractiveness to people with violent attitudes and behaviors may be explaining the results obtained in this study. The findings can help eliminate the stereotype largely adopted by some intervention and prevention programs which assume that gender-based violence occurs mainly in stable relationships, considering that falling in love is the reason that lead women to suffer from violence. Our results can also support health professionals and others serving young women to enhance their identification of gender violence victimization, as well as our findings point to the need to include the evidence of gender violence in sporadic relationships in prevention programs and campaigns addressed to young women.</p>	<p><i>Dominant coercive discourse; dating violence; gender violence; intervention and prevention programs; young women; risk factors; social influence; socialization</i></p>

53	<p>Linares, R. <i>et al.</i> (2021) "Cyber-dating abuse in young adult couples: Relations with sexist attitudes and violence justification, smartphone usage and impulsivity," <i>PLoS one</i>, 16(6), p. e0253180.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0253180</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 697	<p>Technologies have become important for interaction in couples. However, in some cases, controlling and aggressive behaviors can occur in the context of virtual interactions in couples; this is known as cyber-dating abuse (CDA). Identifying factors linked to CDA, as perpetrator and victim, are relevant for its prevention; therefore, more research is needed in this novel field of study. To contribute to the literature, our first goal was to analyze the associations among certain risk factors for CDA perpetration and victimization of, i.e., sexist attitudes and violence justification, problematic smartphone usage and impulsivity; sex and age were also considered. The second goal was to study whether there were differences in direct aggression and control, from the perpetrator and victim perspectives, with consideration of the above-mentioned risk factors. Third, differences in the diverse range of control behaviors and direct aggression between women and men were explored. To this end, 697 young adults (aged between 18 and 35 years; 548 women) completed self-report questionnaires that allowed assessment of the above-mentioned variables. The results showed that, among the wide range of CDA behaviors, indirect ones such as control behaviors were the most common. The highest level of control was strongly associated with the inability to manage behaviors under certain emotional states, especially negative ones, along with problematic smartphone usage. Sex differences were also observed: men displayed more sexist attitudes and violence justification, and perceived that they were more controlled by their partners. Regarding CDA behaviors, men and women showed differences in control (e.g. men considered themselves to be more controlled in terms of location and status updates), and direct aggression (e.g. men used more insults and humiliations than women). The results were discussed in terms of the importance of better understanding these risk factors to attenuate the increasing prevalence of CDA in relationships.</p>	<i>No keywords</i>
54	<p>León, C.M., Fikre Butler, L. and Aizpurua, E. (2022) "Correlates of Fear of Victimization Among College Students in Spain: Gender Differences and Similarities," <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i>, 37(1-2), pp. NP147–NP175.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260520914560</p>	Spain	Quantitative N = 2112	<p>Past studies that have analyzed fear of victimization using samples composed of men and women have most frequently controlled for the effect of gender. This study not only controls for the effect of gender, but also examines how the predictors of fear of victimization may vary across gender. To do so, separate regression models for men and women were estimated and the corresponding z tests were calculated for the purpose of analyzing whether the differences between genders were significant. The results showed that women scored higher on the general fear of crime victimization scale, as well as for fear of becoming victims of each of the specific crimes under study. Religiosity had an equally significant effect on men and women's fear of victimization. Also, younger participants were more likely to fear being victims in the cases of both men and women, although this effect was even more pronounced among women. In addition, respondents' fear of victimization differed across gender based on sexual orientation. Finally, the results showed a few variables (political orientation and sexual victimization) that were only significant in the case of women, but not of men. The findings of this study confirm that fear of victimization and its predictors vary between women and men.</p>	<i>Media and violence; stalking; cultural contexts; criminology; sexual assault</i>

55	Romo Parra, C. <i>et al.</i> (2022) "Analysis from university students' viewpoint of social professionals in gender-based violence in Spain," <i>Social work education</i> , 41(6), pp. 1291–1312. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2021.1948985	Spain	Quantitative N = 336	Gender-based violence is a pandemic with global impact, and social welfare professionals play a central role in the fight against it. The main objective of this study was to describe and interpret the opinions of a sample of 336 students from the University of Malaga on professional practice in social intervention for gender-based violence. These students were studying degrees in Social Work, Psychology, and University Master's Degree in Equality and Gender and had previous theoretical and practical knowledge of the subject. A SWOT matrix was applied to collect the data, which were analyzed through ATLAS.ti software. The results clearly show that training and professional experience—and their opposites—articulate the main strengths and weaknesses of the professional collective. Regarding opportunities, students underline the role of resources in all forms, and deficient investment in resources and normative deficits emerge as the main threats. The diagnosis presented provides valuable information for the design of curriculums and public policies that reinforce the task of professionals, present and future, in social intervention for gender-based violence.	<i>Gender-based violence; university students; social intervention; professional competence; strengths; weaknesses; opportunities; threats</i>
56	Rodriguez-Rodriguez, I. and Heras-González, P. (2020) "A Study of the Protocols for Action on Sexual Harassment in Public Universities—Proposals for Improvement," <i>Social sciences (Basel)</i> , 9(8), p. 128. Available at: https://doi.org/10.3390/SOCSCI9080128	Spain	Mixed methods	Sexual harassment and harassment on the grounds of sex are social problems that still need to be solved in 2020. Universities are not immune to these issues and they generally determine a set of measures to be implemented, sometimes in the form of a protocol of action, in order to address the problem. After a review of the literature, this work will describe the development of these protocols in Spanish public universities, offering a compilation of the implemented means and procedures, but also others still to be added, creating a diagnosis of the position of Spanish universities, and suggestions about how to manage sexual harassment and harassment on the grounds of sex in a higher education environment.	<i>Sexual harassment; public universities; protocol; information and communication technologies</i>
57	Yolima Rodriguez-Burbano, A. <i>et al.</i> (2021) "Assessment of Ambivalent Sexism in University Students in Colombia and Spain: A Comparative Analysis," <i>International journal of environmental research and public health</i> , 18(3), p. 1009.	Spain & Colombia	Quantitative N = 374	(1) Background: Gender-based violence has no geographical, personal, or social boundaries. It constitutes a serious public health problem that affects the entire society. This research aims to identify and compare the level of ambivalent sexism in Spanish and Colombian university students and its relationship with sociodemographic factors. Ambivalent sexism, developed by Glick and Fiske (1996), is considered a new type of sexism since, for the first time, it combines negative and positive feelings that give rise to hostile and benevolent sexism, maintaining the subordination of women through punishment and rewards. (2) Methods: The methodology consisted of the application of the validated Spanish version of the Ambivalent Sexism Inventory (ASI) to a sample of 374 students in their final academic year of the Law program, of which	<i>Sexual education; knowledge of sexuality; ambivalent sexism; university; gender-based violence; sexism</i>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18031009			<p>21.7% were students at the University of Santander (Bucaramanga, Colombia), 45.5% at the University Rey Juan Carlos (Madrid, Spain), and the remaining 32.9% at the University of Seville (Seville, Spain).</p> <p>(3) Results: A high level of ambivalent sexism is reported in Colombian students nowadays. In the two countries, there are similarities (e.g., the great weight of religion and the variation in attitudes towards sexism in people who identify themselves as women, compared to male or students consulted that prefer not to answer) and differences (e.g., absence in Colombia of gender-specific legislation, low number of students who have received gender education in Spain).</p> <p>(4) Conclusions: These findings may contribute to the construction of laws that take into account the particular problems of women and the development of educational programs on gender that are offered in a transversal and permanent way and that take into account cultural factors and equity between men and women as an essential element in the training of future judges who have the legal responsibility to protect those who report gender violence.</p>	
58	<p>Kisiel, M.A. <i>et al.</i> (2020) "Medical students' self-reported gender discrimination and sexual harassment over time," <i>BMC medical education</i>, 20(1), pp. 503–9.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-020-02422-9</p>	Sweden	Quantitative, survey N first sample: 622 N second sample: 856	<p>Background: Gender discrimination (GD) and sexual harassment (SH) occur at all academic institutions worldwide. Medical students report high prevalence of GD and SH, which may negatively affect their education and health. There are indications that policies and reforms on reducing GD/SH are insufficient. Swedish medical students' experiences of GD/SH are monitored by course-evaluations and bi-annual student union evaluations; however, the response rate is usually low. The aim of this study was to compare the exposure to and context of self-reported GD/SH over an 11-year period amongst medical students at a Swedish university.</p> <p>Methods: In 2002, a questionnaire (n =622) was mailed to medical students' home addresses. It was repeated in 2013 and then distributed during mandatory lectures (n = 856). The questions used a behavioristic approach and asked about specific GH/SH experiences. Participation was voluntary and anonymous. The changes in prevalence over time were calculated by sampling weights in order to obtain comparable estimates, representative of both cohorts.</p> <p>Results: The response frequency was 55% (62% women) in 2002 and 81% (59% women) in 2013. The prevalence of GD tended to decrease for male and clinical students in comparison to female and pre-clinical peers. However, the prevalence of SH increased for female compared to male students. The ratio of SH for female pre-clinical students doubled in many instances; most often, the mistreatment occurred in the clinic. Medical doctors were indicated as perpetrators up to five times more often by all students in 2013.</p> <p>Conclusion: Our results show a disproportional change in exposure to GD/SH between female and male medical students, resulting in a widening of the gender gap regarding prevalence of GD and SH between 2002 and 2013. In</p>	<i>Gender discrimination; sexual harassment; medical students; Swedish university</i>

				particular, personal experiences of SH increased for both sexes. It is proof that institutional efforts to fight mistreatment might be ineffective.	
59	Mellgren, C. and Ivert, A.-K. (2019) "Is Women's Fear of Crime Fear of Sexual Assault? A Test of the Shadow of Sexual Assault Hypothesis in a Sample of Swedish University Students," <i>Violence against women</i> , 25(5), pp. 511–527. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1077801218793226	Sweden	Quantitative N = 2853	Prior research shows that women's higher fear of crime compared with men can largely be explained by women's fear of rape. Whether women's higher fear can also be explained by fear of nonviolent sexual harassment has not been explored. This study tested the shadow of sexual assault hypothesis in a sample of almost 3,000 Swedish university students. Our results confirm previous tests of the shadow thesis on the effect of fear of rape. In addition, we show that fear of sexual harassment also explained differences in fear between men and women. Based on the findings, we recommend that strategies to reduce sexual violence should focus on the entire continuum of violence against women.	<i>Fear of crime; sexual assault; Sweden</i>
60	Ustunel, A.O. (2021) "Young People's Views on Dating Violence Prevention in an Urban Turkish Context: Developing Effective Practices," <i>Journal of family violence</i> , 36(7), pp. 773–785. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/s10896-021-00271-8	Turkey	Qualitative	Dating violence (DV) among young people is increasingly recognized as a significant problem and preventive efforts targeting adolescents and young adults are being mobilized to tackle it. However, an accumulating body of evidence shows that these efforts fail to adequately capture young people's needs, particularly those from diverse cultures and contexts, and to incorporate their perspectives into practice. The present study aimed to address this gap by exploring young people's views on how DV can be prevented and what they expect from prevention programs in an urban Turkish context, where DV remains an under-studied issue and preventive efforts are only slowly progressing. Toward this goal, a qualitative research design was employed. Thirty-nine college students, aged 18–25, were recruited through convenience sampling and individually interviewed in a semi-structured manner. The interviews were transcribed and thematically analyzed from a social constructionist perspective. The analysis revealed five main themes that indicated young people's suggestions for and expectations from DV prevention: 1) setting new dating norms, 2) targeting socialization processes, 3) improving relational competence, 4) improving oneself, and 5) managing obstacles. The findings and practice implications are discussed within a contextual-ecological framework in the changing socio-cultural terrain of Turkey. The study highlights the fact that	<i>Dating violence prevention; college students; Turkey; traditional patriarchy; contextually-tailored practices; positive development</i>

				young people's views can guide the development of effective, contextually relevant, empowering, and collaborative practices, and indicates the value of listening to young people's voices in the field of DV prevention.	
61	Özaşçılar, M. and Ziyalar, N. (2017) "Unraveling the Determinants of Fear of Crime Among Men and Women in Istanbul: Examining the Impact of Perceived Risk and Fear of Sexual Assault," <i>International journal of offender therapy and comparative criminology</i> , 61(9), pp. 993–1010. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X15613334	Turkey	Quantitative N = 723	Studies have examined university students' fear of crime focusing on the relationship between the fear of sexual assault and fear of other crimes, termed the shadow of sexual assault hypothesis; however, no study to date has examined the shadow thesis in a Turkish context. Drawing on the shadow thesis, using a sample of 723 university students in Istanbul, this study focuses on the effect of fear of sexual assault and perceived risk of crime to general fear of crime among university students in Istanbul. Also, the predictors of fear of crime are explored to examine the relationship between lifestyle characteristics, constrained behaviors, and fear. The findings of the study supported the shadow thesis, indicating that fear of sexual assault shaped the nonsexual crimes, especially crimes involving face-to-face confrontations between the victim and offender. Furthermore, lifestyle characteristics are correlated with the men's fear of nonsexual crimes, particularly fear of robbery, aggravated assault, and burglary home.	<i>Fear of sexual assault; perceived risk of crime; Istanbul; university students</i>
62	Yılmaz, B., El, Çiçek and Aslan, E. (2022) "The sex-role of university students and their attitudes toward violence against women in the name of honor," <i>Journal of aggression, maltreatment & trauma</i> , 31(4), pp. 444–458.	Turkey	Quantitative N = 1133	Honor includes positive behaviors such as integrity, honesty and morality for both men and women. In some cultures, honor refers to sexual purity. It is very important to know and scientifically demonstrate the value judgments of university students about honor since they shape the future. This study examined the sex-role of university students and their attitudes toward violence against women in the name of honor in Turkey, one of the countries that has adopted the culture of honor. A total of 1,133 university students participated in this cross-sectional study. Data were collected by the researchers using the face-to-face interview method between February and May 2019. The data collection tools utilized were a participant information form, the Scale for Attitudes toward Violence against Women in the Name of Honor (SAVWNH) and the Bem Sex-Role Inventory. The mean score of the participants on the SAVWNH was 29.36 ± 7.21 . The study showed that the male gender, masculine gender	<i>Sex-role; violence; honor; women; university students</i>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/10926771.2021.1965060			role, extended family type and being born in a rural area negatively affected the attitudes toward violence against women in the name of honor. In conclusion, traditional beliefs of the patriarchal society were common among the university students despite their academic environment.	
63	Oflaz, Çiğdem <i>et al.</i> (2022) "Feeling Guilt and Shame Upon Psychological Dating Violence Victimization in College Women: The Further Role of Sexism," <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i> , p. 8862605221097443. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/08862605221097443	Turkey	Quantitative N = 219	Dating violence is manifested in different forms between romantic partners. Psychological violence, the most common form of dating violence, is more likely to affect women, eliciting feelings such as shame and guilt. The robust relationship of sexism to psychological dating violence victimization (PDVV) is well-documented but whether PDVV serves as a mechanism linking sexism to guilt and shame remains unexplored. This study, therefore, investigated the potential mediating role of PDVV in the association between sexist attitudes and feelings of guilt and shame. Dating college women (N = 219) from Turkey, an honor culture in which one's self-worth lies on one's evaluation as well as the assessment of what others think, participated in the study. High rates of PDVV were found in this culture, and structural equation modeling revealed that PDVV mediated the relationship between sexism and feelings of guilt and shame. These findings are discussed in terms of their implications for future research and how sexist attitudes might be challenged to reduce the adverse emotional effects experienced by women who are victims of psychological dating violence.	<i>Psychological dating violence victimization; sexism; shame and guilt; dating college women; structural equation modeling</i>
64	Ustunel, A.O. (2022) "Dating Violence in an Urban Turkish Context: Listening to Young People from an Intersectional Perspective," <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i> , 37(13-14), pp. NP11652–NP11682. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/088626052197441	Turkey	Qualitative	Intersectional approaches have challenged the field of domestic violence to pay more attention to diversity in women's experiences and highlighted the significance of their social contexts and positions, such as class, race, religion, in shaping their understanding of and responses to violence. In the dating violence (DV) literature, a similar call has been made to develop contextualized accounts of DV and to address the heterogeneity of young people through DV prevention programs. Nevertheless, to date, intersectional thinking has not been fully utilized in DV research. The present study aims to address this gap in the literature and investigate how young people make sense of and experience DV from an intersectional perspective in an urban Turkish context. The data for the current study came from individual interviews conducted with 39 college students, aged 18–25. The interviews inquired into how young people understood, explained, and experienced DV. The interviews were analyzed thematically, culminating into four main themes: (a) DV as control, (b) DV as resulting from traditional gender norms, (c) DV as women's fault, and (d) DV-related socialization processes. Some of these main themes were	<i>Dating violence; intersectionality; diversity; college students; Turkey; prevention practices</i>

				interpreted and experienced differently by the participants depending on their gender and the impact of traditional, Islamic, and egalitarian discourses on their accounts. The result demonstrated nuanced differences in young people’s meaning-making perspectives, needs, and vulnerabilities to DV. In the Turkish context, these results are intended to inform the burgeoning field of DV research and to guide the development of diversity-informed, culturally tailored, and context-sensitive prevention practices.	
65	<p>Calik, K.Y. (2018) “Attitudes of Turkish Academics Regarding Violence Against Women in the Name of Honor,” <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i>, 33(20), pp. 3232–3254.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260517739288</p>	Turkey	Quantitative N = 877	<p>Honor is an important concept that has a vital value in Turkey and affects many women’s lives and even causes death. It is of utmost importance to know and scientifically demonstrate the value judgments of the academics that lead and pioneer the society in our country where honor culture is adopted. Therefore, in Turkey, where thousands of women are exposed to violence every year, 877 academics participated in this descriptive study to determine the attitudes of academics toward violence against women in the name of honor. The data were collected using “The Scale for Attitudes Towards Violence Against Women in the Name of Honor (SAVWNH)” in the form of electronic questionnaires through email addresses of the academics working at different faculties of the university in the official website of the university in September 1 to October 1, 2015. In our study, academics’ “attitudes towards violence against women in the name of honor” were found low. That is, academics had negative attitudes toward the verbal or physical violence against women in the name of honor and opposed to the punishment of women for this reason. Nevertheless, the attitudes of those who were males; those who were not professors, associate professors, and assistant professors; those who were single; those who had lived in the district/village for a long time; those who had arranged marriages; those who used any kind of violence; and those who considered violence as a solution were found somewhat more conventional. These results showed that, for some academics, the traditional beliefs of the Turkish patriarchal society continued to be valid although they were included in university academic cultures. In fact, it is revealed here that social values, traditions, and customs are very effective and important on the formation of personality in socialization process.</p>	<p><i>Community violence; violence exposure; perceptions of domestic violence; domestic violence; cultural contexts</i></p>

66	<p>Siyez, D.M. <i>et al.</i> (2021) "Attitudes of the Turkish University Students and Staff Toward Sexual Harassment and Assault: Preliminary Psychometric Evaluation," <i>SAGE open</i>, 11(4), p. 215824402110503.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211050374</p>	Turkey	<p>Quantitative N first sample: 150 N second sample: 354</p>	<p>The aim of this study was to develop a scale to measure the attitudes of the university academic and administrative staff and students toward sexual harassment and assault, and examine its psychometric properties. After the development of the item pool and examination of the content validity of the intended items, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and parallel analysis was conducted and Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient was calculated collecting data from 150 participants (54.7% of female and 45.3% of male) for the initial version (comprised of 12 items) of the Attitudes Toward Sexual Harassment and Assault Scale (ATSHAS). In the second phase, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted with 354 participants (54% of female and 46% of male) for the revised version (10 items) of the ATSHAS. Additionally, Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient was calculated with second sample. After developing the item pool, the completion of the first phase of the study took 5 months, and the second phase took 4 months. The final version of the ATSHAS consisting of nine items demonstrated sufficient psychometric properties for measuring attitudes toward sexual harassment and assault in the university environment.</p>	<p><i>Sexual harassment; sexual assault; attitude; scale development</i></p>
67	<p>Toplu-Demirtaş, E., Murray, C. and Hatipoglu-Sümer, Z. (2019) "Attachment insecurity and restrictive engulfment in college student relationships: the mediating role of relationship satisfaction," <i>Journal of aggression, conflict and peace research</i>, 11(1), pp. 24–37.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1108/JACPR-11-2017-0333</p>	Turkey	<p>Quantitative N = 322</p>	<p>Purpose: Studies on restrictive engulfment (RE)– a subtype of psychological aggression in intimate relationships– have focused either on insecure attachment or relationship satisfaction, not both. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to investigate relationship satisfaction as a potential mediator of the associations between anxious and avoidant attachment and RE perpetration among college students.</p> <p>Design/methodology/approach: A sample of 322 college students (178 women, 137 men, and seven other gender-identified) completed the experiences in close relationship inventory, relationship assessment scale, and RE subscale of the multidimensional measure of emotional abuse.</p> <p>Findings: Among the sample, 89.3 and 90.5 percent of the college women and men, respectively, reported to have used isolating, restricting, monitoring, and controlling behaviors. The results of structural equation modeling revealed that all direct paths except for that from avoidant attachment to RE were significant. Moreover, significant indirect paths were identified from anxious and avoidant attachment to RE via relationship satisfaction.</p> <p>Research limitations/implications: The results of this study should be interpreted with consideration of the study's limitations. First, the data were drawn from a convenience sample of Turkish college students. Second, the design of the study is correlational; therefore, we cannot assume causality. Finally, this study utilized self-report and retrospective data. Practical implications: Though the findings are preliminary, they may inform college counselors and other mental health practitioners about the nature of RE within college students' dating relationships. College students who are unhappy with their dating relationships but still in those relationships (i.e. they choose not to leave) should be assessed for whether they are the perpetrators and/or recipients of psychological aggression, especially in light of the high rates of this form of aggression in the current and previous studies. Furthermore, assessing psychological dating aggression perpetrators for insecure attachment styles may help mental health</p>	<p><i>College students; relationship satisfaction; attachment insecurity; dating relationships; psychological aggression; restrictive engulfment</i></p>

				<p>professionals who work with college students, envisage the sessions toward areas in the need of improvement, such as their views of themselves and others. Self-esteem, feelings of insecurity and inadequacy in relationships, and dependency can be worked with these clients.</p> <p>Social implications: The results of this study also have implications for the prevention of psychological aggression before it occurs. The need for prevention programs is evident in the high rates of psychologically controlling behaviors among college students. It may be useful to implement campus wide programs to raise awareness regarding psychological aggression, such as through events, seminars, posters, flyers, and talks with student groups.</p> <p>Originality/value: Despite the limitations of this study, its findings offer insight into the factors that influence the perpetration of psychological aggression within dating relationships among college students. Adult attachment theory offers a useful lens for understanding the possible driving forces behind college students' controlling behaviors toward their dating partners. In particular, college students who demonstrate an insecure attachment style– and especially an anxious attachment style– combined with low levels of relationship satisfaction appear to be at a high risk for perpetrating RE behaviors.</p>	
68	<p>Beaujoulais, B., Mengo, C. and Karandikar, S. (2021) "An exploration of student, staff, and faculty perceptions on the nature of violence and its prevention at a university in Turkey," <i>International social work</i>, 64(4), pp. 496–510.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0020872819835588</p>	Turkey	Qualitative	<p>The nature of violence within universities in Turkey is an under-researched area. This qualitative study explored the nature of campus violence and its prevention in Turkey. Study results illuminate the nature and forms of violence on campus, and reveal informal and formal structures within the university that address violence prevention. Regarding safety and violence prevention on campus, study participants perceived (a) inadequate university response, (b) lack of policies and procedures, and (c) lack of training about responding to and preventing violence. Perceptions about feeling safe and reporting violence varied based on participant gender. Implications for practice and research are discussed.</p>	<p><i>Campus safety; higher education; Turkey, universities; violence</i></p>

69	<p>Ustunel, A.O. (2020) "A feminist approach to dating violence prevention: Creating change towards safety, equality and mutuality," <i>Feminism & psychology</i>, 30(2), pp. 143–164.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0959353519882462</p>	Turkey	Qualitative	<p>The effectiveness of dating violence prevention programs in changing behaviors, attitudes and knowledge related to perpetration and victimization has been well documented in the literature. However, little attention has been paid to the question of how such positive outcomes have been obtained, and the debate continues as to their underlying theoretical rationale. The present study aimed to fill this gap by designing a dating violence prevention program from a feminist approach and to investigate the processes of change with a constructivist grounded theory methodology. Towards this goal, 56 Turkish college students completed the program and later participated in semistructured individual interviews. The analysis showed that the program initiated a gradual move towards safety, equality and mutuality in dating and intimate relations through four processes: changing perspectives and norms, learning from peers, reflecting on self, and acting differently. Some of the processes were experienced differently depending on the nature of prior or current dating experiences and the strength of sexist beliefs. The present study argues that a feminist approach proves to be a useful framework for dating violence prevention efforts and concludes with recommendations for future preventive work.</p>	<p><i>Dating violence prevention; constructivist grounded theory; college students; Turkey; feminist psychotherapy approaches</i></p>
70	<p>Schuster, I. and Krahé, B. (2019) "Predictors of Sexual Aggression Perpetration Among Male and Female College Students: Cross-Cultural Evidence From Chile and Turkey," <i>Sexual abuse</i>, 31(3), pp. 318–343.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1079063218793632</p>	Turkey and Chile	Quantitative N Chile: 1098 N Turkey: 885	<p>This two-wave longitudinal study examined risky sexual scripts and sexual behavior regarding consensual sexual interactions, sexual self-esteem, initiation assertiveness, and religiosity as predictors of sexual aggression perpetration in a cross-cultural comparison of college students in Chile and Turkey. As predicted, risky sexual scripts were linked to higher odds of perpetration through more risky sexual behavior cross-sectionally in both the Chilean and the Turkish sample and indirectly predicted perpetration 12 months later. High sexual self-esteem increased the likelihood of perpetration via higher initiation assertiveness in the Turkish sample only. High religiosity reduced the odds of perpetration through less risky sexual scripts and less risky sexual behavior in both samples. In addition, high religiosity increased the probability of perpetration through lower sexual self-esteem in the Turkish sample. Implications of these findings and the role of cultural factors contributing to the differential functioning of religiosity and sexual self-esteem are discussed.</p>	<p><i>Sexual aggression perpetration; risk factors; sexual scripts, Chile; Turkey</i></p>
71	<p>Schuster, I. and Krahé, B. (2019) "Predicting Sexual Victimization Among College Students in Chile and Turkey: A Cross-Cultural Analysis," <i>Archives of sexual behavior</i>, 48(8), pp. 2565–2580.</p>	Turkey and Chile	Quantitative N Chile: 1098 N Turkey: 885	<p>To address the shortage of cross-cultural research on vulnerability factors of sexual victimization, this two-wave longitudinal study examined predictors of sexual victimization among female and male college students in Chile (N = 1098) and Turkey (N = 885). These two countries were selected based on theoretical considerations regarding religiosity and gender inequality. A path model was tested that conceptualized participants' risky scripts for consensual sex, risky sexual behavior, sexual self-esteem, refusal assertiveness, and religiosity at T1 as predictors of sexual victimization in the following 12 months, as assessed at T2, mediated through past experiences of sexual victimization. As predicted, more risky sexual scripts were linked to more risky sexual behavior and lower refusal assertiveness, indirectly increasing the odds of sexual victimization in both countries. Lower sexual self-esteem predicted a higher probability of sexual victimization through lower refusal assertiveness as well as through more</p>	<p><i>Sexual victimization; sexual scripts; religiosity; Chile; Turkey</i></p>

	<p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-018-1335-z</p>			<p>risky sexual behavior in both the Chilean and Turkish samples. Higher religiosity in Chile, a Christian country, and Turkey, a Muslim country, indirectly predicted a lower vulnerability to sexual victimization through less risky sexual scripts and less risky sexual behavior. In the Turkish sample only, higher religiosity predicted a higher vulnerability to sexual victimization through lower sexual self-esteem. The findings show that risky sexual scripts played a central role in the prediction of sexual victimization in both cultures, which has implications for prevention efforts.</p>	
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Appendix D – Articles on Intersectionality, 2017-2022

No	Reference	Country	Method	Abstract	Keywords
1	Anderson, B. and Naidu, C. (2022) “Fresh Meat: First Year Female Students Negotiating Sexual Violence on Campus Residences,” <i>South African journal of higher education</i> , 36(1), pp. 41–58. Available at: https://doi.org/10.20853/36-1-4800	South Africa	Qualitative	This article focuses on first-year black female students at the University of KwaZulu-Natal who were exposed to and experienced sexual violence. The aim of the study was, broadly, to determine how female students experience and negotiate gender, sexuality and violence in campus residences. Semi-structured individual interviews were utilised to generate data. The findings show that violence was shaped by gender and power dynamics. These students were first years, and predominantly from poor backgrounds, and therefore particularly vulnerable to sexual violence and unequal relationships. Alcohol, substance abuse and dangerous masculinised spaces further exacerbated their vulnerability. Poverty, scarce resources and gender intersect to produce vulnerability and constrained forms of their agency that translate into transactional relationships. The findings also suggest that being first year female students have implications for how these young women negotiated their newfound freedom away from the parental gaze. The study highlights the ways in which these first-year students are aware that sexual violence is prevalent on campus particularly in certain spaces such as Dark City and residence rooms. Members of the SRC and DSRA are cited as likely perpetrators of sexually predatory behaviours. We therefore propose that the Gender Based Violence Policy at UKZN should be introduced to first year students by way of induction courses, and that these courses should also include gender and sexuality education to help ensure that awareness around gender violence permeates the lives of all students.	<i>sexual violence, university student residences, vulnerability, first year female students, dangerous spaces, alcohol usage</i>
2	Atkinson, K. and Standing, K.E. (2019) “Changing the Culture? A Feminist Academic Activist Critique,” <i>Violence against women</i> , 25(11), pp. 1331–1351.	UK	Qualitative	The Universities UK (UUK) Taskforce report, Changing the Culture, has been seen as a turning point in U.K. universities’ responses to gender-based violence (GBV). Institutional changes have occurred as a response to grassroots feminist activism and resistance to GBV, focusing on sexual violence, harassment, and “lad culture” in universities. This article will argue that the neoliberal marketization of higher education, concurrent with the persistence of misogyny and patriarchy, creates an environment where GBV is normalized, and feminist voices are marginalized and silenced. Interviews with academics show support for victims/survivors on campus often falls to particular academic staff. When initiatives for change, led by institutional management, are limited to protecting the “reputation” of the university, it furthermore falls on academics to challenge not only GBV, but also the reactive and uncritical responses offered by institutions. We contend that national, institutional, and individual responses to GBV must consider the meaning of “cultural change” beyond policy reform, zero	<i>sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based violence, activism, academia, culture</i>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1077801219844609			tolerance campaigns, and condemnation of GBV. Attempts to enact true cultural change must analyze the broader issue of sexism, its intersections with further structural issues, and the ways in which this plays out within the neoliberal institution to the detriment of students and staff.	
3	Bravo-Moreno , A. (2022) "Demystifying the academy: Resistance, ethics and abuse of power," <i>Power and education</i> , 14(2), pp. 140–156. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/175774382111068283	USA	Qualitative	The purpose of this article is to examine academia and the abuse of power based on autoethnographic research. I draw on my experiences across 12 universities in different locations in Spain, the UK and the USA that expose the way power is embedded in institutions of higher education and how it is maintained. This article analyses the exploration of inequalities which concerns particular social divisions, for example, gender, social class, ethnicity, non-national status and the intersection of these categories in particular sociocultural and historical contexts where I conducted my studies, research and teaching for more than 30 years. Employing auto-ethnography has allowed me to examine multi-layered lived experiences in the three countries intertwined with axes of inequality. Thanks to the dual focus on individual experiences and social contexts, this article shows how different systems of domination have shaped my experiences as a student and as a member of faculty in a transnational context. This heuristic approach has challenged me to generate meaning within a framework of ethics and social justice, recognizing that academia often excludes and marginalizes. Thus, this qualitative research enables marginal voices and the articulation of silenced narratives, hence expanding our knowledge of the relationship between power and academia.	<i>Academia, abuse of power, gender, class, ethnicity, non-national status, ethics, Spain, UK, USA</i>
4	Burns, V.L. (2020) "Utilizing Intersectional Pedagogy in a Campus Sexual Assault Course," <i>Women & therapy</i> , 43(3-4), pp. 389–399. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/02703149.2020.1729471	USA	Qualitative	It is of critical importance that clinicians are trained in sexual assault prevention through an intersectional lens. In this article, I describe a campus sexual assault curriculum that interrogates the role of systematic oppression to prevent the erasure of marginalized identities. I then describe a group project where students create a sexual assault prevention program based on intersectional theory and the role of power and oppression. Finally, I describe improvement areas and specific ways training programs can ensure future practitioners are addressing privilege, oppression, and social change in their campus sexual assault work.	<i>Campus sexual assault; institutional activism; social action</i>
5	Christensen, M.C. and Harris, R.J. (2019) "Correlates of Bystander Readiness to Help Among a Diverse College Student Population: An	USA	Quantitative	This study seeks to understand which socio-demographic variables explain bystander readiness to help (BRH) among a diverse (via race/ethnicity) sample of college students. This study uses an intersectional approach by investigating how gender intersects with variables, specific to a college student population (e.g., class level, college of major, sexual harassment on campus), to influence readiness to help. The results are from a survey about campus climate experiences, which includes a stratified random sample of college students from a large Southwestern university in the United States, with	<i>Sexual violence prevention · Sexual harassment · Bystander</i>

	<p>Intersectional Perspective," <i>Research in higher education</i>, 60(8), pp. 1195–1226.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/s11162-018-09544-6</p>			<p>964 respondents. We conducted bivariate crosstabulations, comparisons of means, and multiple regressions. The multiple regression analyses illustrate that for women, the single most robust relationship with BRH is experiences with sexual harassment. For men, the strongest correlate is being a student within the college of liberal and fine arts. The practical and research implications of these findings are discussed.</p>	<p><i>readiness to help · Bystander intervention programs · Diversity · Intersectionality</i></p>
6	<p>Cohan, D.J. (2019) "'It Is Time to Make Our Way Home': How Contingent Labor Practices Impact Transformative Possibilities of Teaching About Violence Against Women," <i>Violence against women</i>, 25(11), pp. 1370–1387.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1077801219844601</p>	USA	Qualitative	<p>This article explores the intersection of teaching about gender-based violence and contingent employment. Drawing upon Patricia Hill Collins's (1986) theory of the outsider-within to illuminate how power differentials, access, and resources as insiders or outsiders shape knowledge production and ways of knowing, seeing, and being, the author applies this lens to the experience of contingent faculty. Relying on perspectives in feminist pedagogy, autoethnographic methods, and case studies of students studying trauma, this article exposes layers of personal and institutional brokenness. In delving into the connection of emotion and social structure, this article is intended for people interested in higher education's role and responsibility in preventing and responding to gender-based violence, the emotional life of the classroom, feminist pedagogy on trauma, mental health crisis in higher education, and overreliance on contingent laborers in higher education.</p>	<p><i>teaching about violence, contingent faculty, contingency, gender-based violence</i></p>
7	<p>Colpitts, E.M. (2022) "'Not even close to enough': sexual violence, intersectionality, and the neoliberal university," <i>Gender and education</i>, 34(2), pp. 151–166.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/09540253.2021.1924362</p>	Canada	Qualitative	<p>As universities face unprecedented pressure to respond to sexual violence, this article critically analyses how they engage with intersectionality in their responses. Based on research in the Canadian province of Ontario, I demonstrate that universities' commitments to intersectionality often fail to translate into practice. This failure results in anti-violence measures that do not address how systems of oppression shape vulnerability and access to support, or how the university is implicated in and constituted through these systems. When commitments to intersectionality are accepted at face value, they enable the university to brand their anti-violence measures as progressive and inclusive without necessarily addressing how sexual violence is produced and sustained through existing institutional power arrangements. As such, rather than celebrating universities for merely referencing intersectionality, I conclude that these commitments must be used to hold them accountable to the transformative work required to eradicate sexual violence on campus.</p>	<p><i>Violence; intersectionality; higher education; neoliberalism; education policy</i></p>

8	Gartner, R.E. (2021) "A New Gender Microaggressions Taxonomy for Undergraduate Women on College Campuses: A Qualitative Examination," <i>Violence against women</i> , 27(14), pp. 2768–2790. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/1077801220978804	USA	Qualitative	Gender microaggressions are everyday slights, insults, and invalidations theorized to create and sustain environments in which sexual harassment and assault of women is normative and permissible. Establishing a gender microaggressions taxonomy for undergraduate women may support efforts to improve campus climate and reduce sexual violence. This study aims to identify a gender microaggressions taxonomy for undergraduate women on college campuses. Five qualitative semi-structured focus groups (N = 23) were conducted with 18- to 25-year-old undergraduate women. Purposive sampling was employed and directed content analysis was performed. Seven themes emerged: invisibility, intersectionality, caretaker and nurturer, women-dominated occupations, presumed incompetence, sexual objectification, and environmental invalidations.	<i>gender microaggressions, discrimination, gender, sexual violence, university</i>
9	Vaccaro A et al. (2020) Gender and Ability Oppressions Shaping the Lives of College Students: An Intracategorical, Intersectional Analysis, <i>Journal of Women and Gender in Higher Education</i> , 13:2, 119-137 Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/26379112.2020.1780134	USA	Qualitative	Emergent findings from a constructivist grounded theory study explicate how gender and ability oppressions intersected to shape the experiences of 47 college students from four post-secondary institutions in the United States. The logics of oppression that have historically supported spurious arguments for the biological inferiority of women and the erasure of trans bodies have mirrored the arguments used to problematize disabled bodies—making this particular intracategorical analysis of students with minoritized gender and ability identities especially important. Rich student narratives detail how intersecting gender and ability oppressions reinforced stereotypes of weakness, fostered fears of violence, and engendered feelings of lack of safety on campus.	<i>No keywords</i>
10	Gomez, J.M. (2022) "Campus Sexual Harassment, Other Violence, and Racism, Oh my! Evidence From Black Women Undergraduates for a Culturally Competent University Approach to Title	USA	Quantitative	Relevant for Title IX federal legislation, the purpose of the current study is to examine cultural betrayal (within-group perpetrator) and sexual harassment (SH) with other violence and racial discrimination on Black women undergraduates' mental health. In a 60- minute online study (N = 162), over 50% experienced campus SH and other violence and/ or racial discrimination, with multi-victimization being related to anxiety and other mental health outcomes. Cultural betrayal SH did not predict mental health when controlling for between-group SH. Implications include the 2019 Critical-Interdisciplinary Sexual Violence Research Summit's comprehensive research agenda: Intersectional Approaches, Perpetration, Communications, Beyond Policy, and Sexual Violence and Equity	<i>campus sexual violence, title IX, cultural betrayal trauma theory, institutional courage, Black women undergraduates</i>

	IX," <i>Feminist criminology</i> , 17(3), pp. 368–383. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/15570851211062574				
11	Griner, S.B. <i>et al.</i> (2020) "The Intersection of Gender Identity and Violence: Victimization Experienced by Transgender College Students," <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i> , 35(23-24), pp. 5704–5725. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260517723743	USA	Quantitative	College students disproportionately experience victimization, stalking, and relationship violence when compared with other groups. Few studies explore victimization by the gender identity of college students, including those who identify as transgender. The purpose of this study is to explore the rates of violence experienced by transgender students compared with male and female college students. This study utilized the National College Health Assessment–II (NCHA-II) and included data from students (n = 82,538) across fall 2011, 2012, and 2013. Bivariate statistics and binary logistic regression were conducted to test the relationships between gender identity and victimization. Transgender students (n = 204) were compared with male (n = 27,322) and female (n = 55,012) students. After adjusting for individual factors, transgender students had higher odds of experiencing all nine types of violence when compared with males and higher odds of experiencing eight types of violence than females. Transgender students experienced the highest odds in crimes involving sexual victimization, including attempted sexual penetration (adjusted odds ratio [aOR]: 9.49, 95% confidence interval [CI] = [6.17, 14.59], d = 1.00), sexual penetration without consent (aOR: 9.06, 95% CI = [5.64, 14.53], d = 0.94), and being in a sexually abusive relationship (aOR: 6.48, 95% CI = [4.01, 10.49], d = 0.48), than did male students. Findings reveal increased odds of victimization among transgender students when compared with male and female students. Results demonstrate the need for more comprehensive violence prevention efforts in college settings.	<i>GLBT, domestic violence, sexual assault, violence against</i>
12	Hancock, K.P. and Daigle, L.E. (2021) "Double jeopardy?: Exploring the intersectionality of sexual/gender group membership, racial/ethnic group membership, and victimization risk," <i>Journal of ethnicity in criminal justice</i> , 19(2), pp. 140–162.	USA	Quantitative	Little research has been conducted to explore the impact of intersectionality among racial/ethnic minority groups and sexual/gender minority groups as it relates to violent, sexual, and stalking victimization risk. Using minority stress theory and routine activities-lifestyle exposure theory as a guide, the current study seeks to add to the literature by identifying risk factors for violent, sexual, and stalking victimization among a national sample of college students, while also exploring the intersections of race/ethnicity and sexual/gender minority status and how they may influence risk. Findings show that being a LGBTQ+ student increases victimization risk similarly for White students and racial/ethnic minority students. There are differences and similarities across victimization risk factors among these groups.	<i>College students; double jeopardy; double minority; minority stress; victimization</i>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/15377938.2021.1942373				
13	Harris, J.C. (2020) "Women of Color Undergraduate Students' Experiences with Campus Sexual Assault: An Intersectional Analysis," <i>Review of higher education</i> , 44(1), pp. 1–30. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1353/rhe.2020.0033	USA	Qualitative	Many higher education scholars, policy makers, and practitioners continue to ignore the intersections of race and gender when focusing on campus sexual assault (CSA) for the undergraduate student population. This race-evasive approach contributes to incomplete and inaccurate understandings about the ways Women of Color students experience CSA. Subsequently, race-evasive approaches often inform ineffective efforts to address and eradicate CSA for all campus populations, particularly for students with multiple minoritized identities. Guided by the concept of intersectionality, this research explores how intersecting systems of domination, specifically racism and sexism, influence 34 Women of Color undergraduate student survivors' experiences with CSA. Study findings demonstrate how an intersectional approach to CSA elicits information that guides more effective efforts to eradicate sexual assault.	<i>No keywords</i>
14	Harris, J.C., Karunaratne, N. and Gutzwa, J.A. (2021) "Effective Modalities for Healing from Campus Sexual Assault: Centering the Experiences of Women of Color Undergraduate Student Survivors," <i>Harvard educational review</i> , 91(2), pp. 248–272. Available at: https://doi.org/10.17763/1943-5045-91.2.248	USA	Qualitative	In this article, Jessica C. Harris, Nadeeka Karunaratne, and Justin A. Gutzwa examine the modalities Women of Color student survivors perceive as helpful in healing from campus sexual assault. Existing scholarship on healing from campus sexual assault largely relies on the reduction of psychological symptoms of trauma, an understanding that is often race-neutral and founded on the narratives of white women. Centering the experiences of 34 Women of Color undergraduate student survivors, this qualitative study reimagines healing through a race-conscious lens and positions it as a community-oriented and culturally contextual process that is often at odds with the ways US institutions of higher education aim to support survivors of sexual assault on their campuses. The authors' findings guide implications for how institutions and individuals can account for and support student survivors' multiple and intersecting identities in their healing journeys and also inform future research that centers minoritized students' experiences with sexual assault in postsecondary contexts.	<i>Higher education; qualitative research; Women of Color; healing-centered engagement</i>
15	Harris, K.L. (2017) "Re-situating organizational knowledge: Violence,	USA	Qualitative	Scholars have called repeatedly for more nuanced understandings of power and organizational knowledge, but researchers have yet to integrate available critical frameworks that could link these concepts. Moreover, existing analyses of power in organizational knowledge tend to focus on role differences but do not yet consider how social differences – including gender,	<i>critical organizational studies,</i>

	<p>intersectionality and the privilege of partial perspective,” <i>Human relations (New York)</i>, 70(3), pp. 263–285.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726716654745</p>			<p>race and sexuality – shape knowledge. Working from a practice-based approach, I draw upon standpoint theory and intersectionality to show how whiteness, masculinity and heteronormativity are embedded in organizational knowledge. I construct this argument using a case study at a US university known for having some of the best systems for building organizational knowledge about sexual violence on campus. I argue that the university’s practices – specifically those related to interpretation and definition – mask heterogeneity in knowledge across the university. I also show how practices give the university’s knowledge the appearance of neutrality and, subsequently, can unintentionally defer important organizational actions.</p>	<p><i>intersectionality, organizational knowledge, power, practice, rape, sexual violence, situated knowledge, standpoint theory, Title IX</i></p>
16	<p>Holland, K.J. and Cipriano, A.E. (2021) “Does a report = support? A qualitative analysis of college sexual assault survivors’ Title IX Office knowledge, perceptions, and experiences,” <i>Analyses of social issues and public policy</i>, 21(1), pp. 1054–1081.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1111/asap.12271</p>	USA	Qualitative	<p>Universities in the United States are required to remedy sexual assault under Title IX. Thus, college sexual assault survivors have the option to report to their university’s Title IX Office as a mechanism for seeking sanctions and accommodations. The current study examined what survivors think about the Title IX Office, the possibility of seeking help there, and experiences with the reporting processes. Additionally, we examined the intersection between survivors’ gender and sexual identity in their perceptions and interactions. We conducted qualitative interviews with 40 survivors at a large Midwestern University and analyzed these data using content analysis and thematic analysis. The majority knew about the Title IX Office and its function, but most did not use it. Campus climate often fostered service barriers, including the minimization of sexual assault, fear of negative treatment, and social–emotional concerns. Survivors who reported rarely saw accountability for their perpetrators and frequently experienced negative treatment from investigators. There were substantial inconsistencies in reporting processes across survivors. There were few differences in knowledge and barriers across sexual and gender identities, but only cisgender women reported. Findings suggest the value in reducing barriers fostered by the campus climate and establishing mechanisms for Title IX Office oversight and accountability.</p>	<p><i>No keywords</i></p>
17	<p>Jackson, J.M. (2019) “Breaking Out of the Ivory Tower: (Re)Thinking Inclusion of Women and Scholars of Color in the Academy,” <i>Journal of women,</i></p>	USA	Qualitative	<p>In this #MeToo moment, many women of color have called out those in power, namely men, who engage in sexual harassment and toxic masculinity. Furthermore, scholars, whose personal identities and research interests lie at the margins of gender, race, class, and sexuality, have drawn increasing attention to issues of gendered and racialized biases and harassment in the Academy. During our pre-conference session at the 2018 meeting of the American Political Science Association, we discussed substantive methods for reckoning with these conditions. We worked through the theoretical frameworks of Black Feminist and queer scholarship to orient ourselves toward actions that center the most marginalized. We identified methods for generating transformative solutions to campus and departmental problems facing students, faculty,</p>	<p><i>#MeToo; higher education; race; gender; Black feminism; intersectionality</i></p>

	<p><i>politics & policy</i>, 40(1), pp. 195–203.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/1554477X.2019.1565459</p>			<p>and staff with intersectional identities. In all, the workshop proved both effective and generative for all in attendance, providing those present with concrete tools to build more equitable departments and classrooms.</p>	
18	<p>Jeffrey, N.K. and Barata, P.C. (2020) "The Intersections of Normative Heterosexuality and Sexual Violence: University Men's Talk about Sexual Behavior in Intimate Relationships," <i>Sex roles</i>, 83(5-6), pp. 353–369.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-019-01110-3</p>	Canada	Qualitative	<p>Research on men's sexual violence against women has focused on individual- and peer-level contributors of sexual violence, with comparatively less focus on broader social contributors. Using four focus groups with a total of 29 Canadian heterosexual university men and a form of discourse analysis, we moved beyond this common focus. In particular, we examined how participants talked about sexual behaviors in intimate relationships and the dominant social norms or discourses about heterosexuality that they used. Participants' conversations constructed a dominant version of heterosexuality that is male-centered and may support sexual violence. Specifically, they suggested that men have a higher and uncontrollable sex drive; that heterosexual initiation and progression occur naturally and without (men's) verbal communication; and that men misinterpret women's ineffective communication and this miscommunication causes sexual violence. They positioned these heterosexuality practices and dynamics as biologically determined and as generally the same across occasions and people. Some men did challenge malecentered and sexual violence-supportive discourses with varying degrees of success at shifting the conversation. Our results have important implications and highlight the need to encourage men's critical engagement with alternative discourses about heterosexuality that do not support sexual violence and that privilege both women's and men's sexuality.</p>	<p><i>Heterosexuality . Sex offenses . Intimate partner violence . Discourse analysis . Social norms . Psychology of men</i></p>
19	<p>Kirkner, A. <i>et al.</i> (2022) "Campus Sexual Violence Victims with Disabilities: Disclosure and Help Seeking," <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i>, 37(9-10), pp. NP7156–NP7177.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260520967149</p>	USA	Quantitative	<p>Undergraduate students with disabilities represent an important population on college campuses. Yet the incidence of sexual violence and disclosing/ reporting of sexual violence among this population is understudied. This exploratory and largely descriptive study uses an intersectional framework to understand the sexual victimization of undergraduate students with disabilities at a large Mid-Atlantic academic institution. The sample consisted of students who completed a sexual violence module (N = 2,929) as part of a larger campus climate survey. Students with disabilities comprised a smaller sample within this group (n = 177) and descriptive and chi-square results from both groups of students are reported. Students with disabilities had a statistically significant higher likelihood of sexual violence victimization before coming to campus and while at the university, with much higher rates for precollege victimization than students with no disabilities. Disclosure rates were not different for students across the two groups, though students with disabilities were more likely to utilize formal sources of support, such as campus Title IX offices and mental health services. This study shows support for a strengths-based approach that recognizes that students with disabilities may be more likely to reach out to campus resources. The findings of</p>	<p><i>sexual assault, GLBT, reporting/disclosure, cultural contexts, vulnerability to abuse developmentally delayed</i></p>

				the study also underscore the need for culturally relevant victim services for students with disabilities. An evaluation of the culture of a university and its environment of openness, sharing, community, and protection (or lack thereof) can be a key point for future approaches to sexual violence on campus.	
20	Lichty, L.F., Rosenberg, K. and Laughlin, K. (2018) "Before there Is a Table: Small Wins to Build a Movement against Sexual and Relationship Violence in a University Context," <i>Journal of family violence</i> , 33(8), pp. 629–645. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/s10896-018-9986-z	USA	Qualitative	Addressing sexual and relationship violence (SRV) on campuses requires coordinated engagement from all members of the campus community; however, many campuses do not yet have the infrastructure or institutional commitment to build an all-campus action plan. In such cases, campuses lack the metaphorical table around which collaboration happens. This paper presents tensions and lessons learned so far from a faculty-staff-student partnership to build a movement toward university-wide collaborative practice. Through iterative, collaborative reflection on our context, practice, and intermediate outcomes, we identified recommendations for improving praxis in campus-based, intersectional anti-SRV organizing. Our analysis explores how our individual positionalities both open up and limit our potential to move this work forward. We share our guiding values and frameworks, including intersectional feminist attention to power and oppression; centering survivors and students; strategic collaboration within systems; and integrating self-care and other supportive practices for building a sustainable movement. Our emergent strategy, illustrated through ten lessons/ tensions and four case examples, focuses on finding close collaborators with shared SRV analysis; making the best use of resources and spaces we control; identifying meaningful small wins; and pursuing opportunities to connect to others through positive collaborations. Efforts to intentionally raise awareness and grow strategic institutional connections build momentum toward institutionally-supported campus-wide evaluation and reimagining of prevention and survivor-support efforts. While feminist collaborative social change is challenging, we celebrate and learn from our two steps forward to sustain us through the inevitable steps back. We write to stir a conversation where we help each other interpret and learn across our varied contexts.	<i>Sexual violence</i> <i>.Relationship violence</i> <i>.Campus</i> <i>.Highereducation</i> <i>.Participatory practice</i> <i>.Collaboration</i> <i>.Feminist praxis</i> <i>.Social change</i>
21	McMahon, S., Burnham, J. and Banyard, V.L. (2020) "Bystander Intervention as a Prevention Strategy for Campus Sexual Violence: Perceptions of Historically Minoritized College Students," <i>Prevention science</i> , 21(6), pp. 795–806.	USA	Qualitative	The bystander intervention approach to campus sexual violence has received increased attention as a promising prevention strategy. However, there lacks research on the perspective of historically minoritized students, such as students of color, LGBTQ-spectrum students, and the intersections thereof. As such, the purpose of this paper is to present the findings from an exploratory study regarding bystander intervention that focused exclusively on the perspectives of 101 racialized and/or LGBTQ spectrum students at three campuses across a large public university. Using concept mapping methodology, the study was conducted in three phases: brainstorming of statements about bystander intervention, sorting and rating of statements, and mapping and interpretation of the results. Using multidimensional scaling and hierarchical cluster analysis, a six-cluster solution was determined, representing key themes related to supporting students' efforts as helpful bystanders. Overall, findings indicate a need for bystander intervention efforts to widen their focus by employing an intersectional, social	<i>Sexual violence prevention</i> <i>.Minoritized populations</i> <i>.Concept mapping</i> <i>.Social justice</i>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/s11121-020-01134-2			justice lens. Study participants identified various forms of racism, homophobia, transphobia, and microaggressions as intertwined with their ability to be active bystanders on college campuses.	
22	Navarro, J.C. and Ratajczak, K. (2022) "Rape Myth Acceptance and General Self-Efficacy: Gender, Race, and Ethnic Differences of Knowing a Sexual Assault Victim among University Students," <i>Violence against women</i> , 28(15-16), pp. 3762–3784. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/10778012211068056	USA	Qualitative	Knowing a sexual assault victim and general self-efficacy (GSE) were examined as predictors of rape myth acceptance (RMA) among university students. Where knowing a sexual assault victim was associated with greater rejection of rape myths among female students, most notably White females, a null effect occurred on male students, except for Black males whose RMA increased. Higher self-efficacy predicted the overall rejection of rape myths differently among identity intersections, most prominently with victim blaming. Knowing a sexual assault victim moderated GSE and RMA for male students and Latinos. These findings offer practical and critical implications as universities grow in diversity.	<i>rape myth acceptance, sexual assault, efficacy, gender differences, racial/ethnic differences</i>
23	Ostridge, L. (2020) "Speaking Freely and Freedom of Speech: Why is Black Feminist Thought Left Out of Ontario University Sexual Violence Policies?," <i>Atlantis</i> , 41(1), pp. 59–71. Available at: https://doi.org/10.7202/1074016ar	Canada	Qualitative	As of January 1, 2017, the Province of Ontario has required all post-secondary institutions to create and maintain a stand-alone sexual assault policy that includes clearly stated complaint and response procedures. This paper brings to bear the influence of Black feminist thought as an analytic tool and politic on the outcomes and omissions of the development of these policies. Analyzing the stand-alone sexual violence policy of the University of Ottawa as a case study, the author conducted a critical discourse analysis with an intersectional lens to determine if intersectionality influenced the policy creation. Findings reveal that policymakers conceptualize gender in a one-dimensional manner, without attention to intersections of sexualized violence with racism and other systems of oppression. A policy with an ill-defined focus on gender can result in a colorblind policy that suggests that the institution should treat all students the same, regardless of systemic disadvantages they might face on the basis of race, class, gender, sexual orientation, or ability. This avoidance can create barriers to reporting. Neoliberalism and the changing university culture are discussed.	<i>campus sexual violence, critical discourse analysis, intersectionality, neoliberalism, sexual violence policy</i>

24	Patton, L.D. and Njoku, N.R. (2019) "Theorizing Black women's experiences with institution-sanctioned violence: a #BlackLivesMatter imperative toward Black liberation on campus," <i>International journal of qualitative studies in education</i> , 32(9), pp. 1162–1182. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2019.1645908	USA	Qualitative	Alicia Garza, Patrisse Cullors, and Opal Tometi are the three Black women and founders of #BlackLivesMatter (BLM). Despite being founded by Black women, public discourses about BLM often foreground Black men's lives, and deaths, at the hand of the state. When attention is given to the violence against Black women, they are either blamed for their victimization or rendered invisible altogether. Black women's labor as a driving force of the BLM movement is also largely unacknowledged. This manuscript explores intersectional failures in the treatment of Black women's contributions broadly, and within higher education, specifically. The authors argue that in addition to state-sanctioned violence, institution-sanctioned violence contributes to the erasure of Black women. Using the experiences of the BLM founders as an entry point, the authors illuminate multiple forms of institution-sanctioned violence experienced by Black women scholars and leaders who, despite their commitment to Black liberation and uplift, experienced marginalization. This article closes with Black women's liberation strategies to disrupt institution-sanctioned violence.	<i>Black women; violence; institutions</i>
25	Solinas-Saunders, M. (2021) "Sexual Violence Among College Students Attending a Nonresidential Campus," <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i> , 36(5-6), pp. NP2273–NP2297. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260518759978	USA	Quantitative	Using the empirical powers of theories of intersectionality, the study investigates the association between students' demographics (such as gender identity, race, ethnicity, age, and socioeconomic status) and sexual violence victimization. An anonymous survey was employed to collect data from a cluster random sample of 966 students attending face-to-face courses at a midsize urban nonresidential campus. The empirical findings suggest that being older and female are the only statistically significant factors in the analysis. As the first attempt to focus on students attending nonresidential programs in the United States, the study presents implications for policy and program implementation to include issues pertinent to students' diversity to better respond to students' risk of victimization.	<i>student sexual violence, demographics, intersectionality, nonresidential campus</i>
26	Täuber, S. (2022) "Women Academics' Intersectional Experiences of Policy Ineffectiveness in the European Context," <i>Frontiers in psychology</i> , 13, p. 810569.	Europe	Quantitative	Despite policy efforts targeted at making universities more inclusive and equitable, academia is still rife with harassment and bullying, and opportunities are far from equal for everyone. The present preregistered survey research (N=91) aimed to explore whether an intersectional approach can be useful to examine the tangible effects of policy ineffectiveness, even when legislative and ideologic constraints limit the possibility to conduct a full-fledged intersectional analysis. Policy ineffectiveness was operationalized as experiences of harassment, discrimination, institutional resistance to gender equality, and retaliation against reporters of misconduct in universities. Policy ineffectiveness was negatively related to women	<i>academia, policy ineffectiveness, psychological safety, voice, intersectional inequality,</i>

	Available at: https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.810569			academics' inclination to pursue an academic career. This relationship was mediated by lower levels of psychological safety associated with policy ineffectiveness. Importantly, women academics who differ from the majority on multiple dimensions show a stronger and more negative relationship between policy ineffectiveness and psychological safety. The study further shows that self-report measures are useful to uncover intersectional privilege afforded to overrepresented groups in academia. The study discusses the benefits of intersectional approaches for designing and implementing effective policies to tackle harassment and inequality in academia, even when the available methodologies are constrained by legislation and ideology. Overall, self-report measurement can have an important function for signalling areas that warrant further intersectional inquiry to ensure that policies serve everyone.	<i>intersectional privilege</i>
27	Whitfield, D.L. <i>et al.</i> (2021) "Experiences of Intimate Partner Violence Among Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender College Students: The Intersection of Gender, Race, and Sexual Orientation," <i>Journal of Interpersonal Violence</i> , 36(11-12), pp. NP6040–NP6064. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260518812071	USA	Quantitative	Lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) college students experience disproportionate rates of intimate partner violence (IPV) compared with their heterosexual and cisgender counterparts. Some studies report rates of IPV among lesbian, gay, and bisexual college students as high as 50%, and 9 times greater among transgender students compared with their cisgender peers. Few studies have investigated the impact of intersectional identity on experiencing different types of IPV, such as emotional, physical, and sexual IPV. The present study utilized the National College Health Assessment–II from 2011 to 2013 (n = 88,975) to examine the differences in types of IPV among college students based on sexual orientation, gender identity, and the intersection of these two identities. Bivariate Rao–Scott chi-square and multilevel logistic regression was used to test the associations between sexual orientation, gender identity, and the intersection of these identities on multiple types of IPV. Adjusting for covariates and school clustering, LGBT college students had higher odds of reporting emotional IPV (adjusted odds ratios [AORs] = 1.34-1.99), physical IPV (AOR = 1.58-2.93), and sexual IPV (AOR = 1.41-6.18). Bisexual and transgender college students demonstrated the highest odds of reporting IPV based on sexual orientation and gender identity, respectively. Intersectional identities were not significantly associated with IPV. These findings demonstrate a need for clinicians working with college students to be aware of the disproportionate prevalence of IPV among LGBT individuals, particularly for those clients those who identify as bisexual and/or transgender and participate in continuing education related to these populations. Furthermore, these findings illustrate the need for additional intersectional research with LGBT college students.	<i>lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, intimate partner violence, National College Health Assessment, intersectionality</i>
28	Wood, L. <i>et al.</i> (2021) "Sexual Harassment at Institutions of Higher Education: Prevalence, Risk, and Extent," <i>Journal of</i>	USA	Quantitative	Sexual harassment is a pervasive problem on college campuses. Across eight academic campuses, 16,754 students participated in an online study that included questions about sexual harassment victimization by a faculty/ staff member or by a peer since enrollment at their Institution of Higher Education (IHE). Utilizing an intersectional theory and hurdle models, this study explored the effects of gender, race/ethnicity, sexual orientation, age at enrollment, student status, and time spent at	<i>sexual harassment, GLBT, anything</i>

	<p><i>interpersonal violence</i>, 36(9-10), pp. 4520–4544.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260518791228</p>			<p>institution on students' risk for peer- and faculty/staff-perpetrated sexual harassment victimization, as well as the extent of victimization for students who experience harassment. Across institutions, 19% of students reported experiencing faculty/staff perpetrated sexual harassment and 30% reported experiencing peer perpetrated sexual harassment. Hypotheses related to intersectional impacts were partially supported, with most significant findings in main effects. Time at institution was found to increase both risk and extent of victimization of both types of harassment. Traditional undergraduate students, non-Latinx White students, female students, and gender and sexual minority students were found to be at increased risk for harassment. Being female increases the odds of experiencing both faculty/staff and peer sexual harassment by 86% and 147%, respectively. Latinx students and students with an ethnicity other than White reported less victimization, but those who reported sexual harassment faced greater extent of harassing behaviors. A discussion of these findings for institutional program planning and policy is explored.</p>	<p><i>related to sexual harassment</i></p>
29	<p>Wooten, S.C. (2017) "Revealing a hidden curriculum of Black women's erasure in sexual violence prevention policy," <i>Gender and education</i>, 29(3), pp. 405–417</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/09540253.2016.1225012</p>	USA	Qualitative	<p>This article aims to challenge the framework by which rape and sexual assault prevention in higher education are being constituted by centring Black women's experiences of sexual violence within a prevention and response policy framework. Numerous research studies exist in the literature regarding the specific experience of sexual violence for Black women within a national context that remains deeply committed to White supremacy [Buchanan, N. T., and A. J. Ormerod. 2002. "Racialized Sexual Harassment in the Lives of African American Women." <i>Women & Therapy</i> 25 (3/4): 107–124; Crenshaw, K. 1989. "Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics." <i>University of Chicago Legal Forum</i> 140: 139–167; Donovan, R., and M. Williams. 2002. "Living at the Intersection: The Effects of Racism and Sexism on Black Rape Survivors." <i>Women & Therapy</i> 25 (3/4): 95–105; McNair, L. D., and H. A. Neville. 1996. "African American Women Survivors of Sexual Assault: The Intersection of Race and Class." <i>Women & Therapy</i> 18 (3/4): 107–118; Omolade, B. 1989. "Black Women, Black men, and Tawana Brawley – The Shared Condition." <i>Harvard Women's Law Journal</i> 12: 11–23; West, C. 2002. "Battered, Black, and Blue: An Overview of Violence in the Lives of Black Women." <i>Women & Therapy</i> 25 (3/4): 5–27]. Using the critical pedagogy principle of 'hidden curriculum' or how what is directly communicated through educational processes also conveys unstated values, judgments, and regulatory norms, the author analyses the first report of the White House Task Force to Protect Students from Sexual Assault [2014. <i>Not Alone: The First Report of the White House Task Force to Protect Students from Sexual Assault</i>] for race-neutral language that contributes to the silencing of the sexual violence that Black college women experience. The necessity of race-conscious sexual assault policy is discussed.</p>	<p><i>Critical race theory; race and ethnicities; violence; whiteness; language; higher education; curriculum; education policy</i></p>

30	<p>Worthen, M.G.F. and Wallace, S.A. (2017) "Intersectionality and Perceptions About Sexual Assault Education and Reporting on College Campuses," <i>Family relations</i>, 66(1), pp. 180–196.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1111/fare.12240</p>	USA	Mixed-methods	<p>A mixed-methods design with an intersectional feminist framework was used with 1,899 students at a large Southern university to critically examine (a) how students view the issue of sexual assault on their own campus, (b) how they perceive the status of reporting sexual assault to campus officials, and (c) how they are responding overall to a campus-wide sexual assault education program. Some privileged groups, especially heterosexual men, were less informed than others about sexual assault and less supportive of campus sexual assault education. In contrast, some marginalized groups, including lesbian, gay, and bisexual students, perceived campus sexual assault to be a more serious issue than did other groups, but they were also most critical of heteronormative biases in most campus programming. Non-White students were most supportive of sexual assault education. Empirically driven implications for campus sexual assault programs are provided.</p>	<i>No keywords</i>
31	<p>Worthen, M.G.F. and Wallace, S.A. (2021) "Why Should I, the One Who Was Raped, Be Forced to Take Training in What Sexual Assault Is? Sexual Assault Survivors' and Those Who Know Survivors' Responses to a Campus Sexual Assault Education Program," <i>Journal of interpersonal violence</i>, 36(5-6), pp. NP2640–NP2674.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260518768571</p>	USA	Quantitative + Qualitative	<p>This study critically examines sexual assault survivors' (people with histories of sexual assault) and those who know survivors' (those who know and/or who are close to people with histories of sexual assault) responses to a mandatory online campus sexual assault education program using both quantitative survey data (N = 1,899) and qualitative narratives (n = 41) from a sample of students at a large southern university with special attention to gender, sexual identity, race, ethnicity, college group affiliations (student athletics, fraternities/sororities, LGBTQ [lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender, queer] ally programs), and the intersections between these identities and affiliations. The quantitative findings show that knowing/being a woman survivor is positively related to supportive attitudes toward the sexual assault education program and inversely, knowing/being a man survivor is negatively related to support of the program. In addition, being a woman, being gay/lesbian, being Black/African American, Asian/Pacific Islander, Native American/Alaskan Native, or another race, and being a sorority member are all significantly related to supportive attitudes toward the sexual assault education program. Furthermore, qualitative analyses revealed that the majority of personal survivors' narratives indicated traumatic/triggering responses whereas most of those who provided narratives about knowing survivors(s) indicated praiseworthy reactions. Overall, the current study offers empirically driven sexual assault education program implications that acknowledge survivors' and those who know survivors' experiences with the ultimate goal of determining how to best meet students' needs.</p>	<i>campus sexual assault, survivors, rape victims, gender, gay, lesbian, heterosexual, bisexual, race/ethnicity, fraternity/sorority, athlete, LGBTQ ally, college, university</i>
32	<p>Zelin, A., Burns, V.L. and Rogers, K.H. (2021) "Fighting Back Against College Campus Sexual Violence: Teaching and Supervising Courses to</p>	USA	Qualitative	<p>The present article focuses on how faculty at two different institutions independently developed academic courses utilizing feminist and intersectional theories to help empower students to "fight back" against college campus sexual violence. As college-aged women have one of the highest rates of sexual violence, it is imperative to provide them with the tools to successfully eradicate sexual violence. We discuss the two main components of our courses, rape culture and allyship, and</p>	<i>Allyship; college students; course design; rape culture; sexual</i>

	Empower Students,” <i>Women & therapy</i> , 44(3-4), pp. 391–414. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1080/02703149.2021.1961450			provide specific assigned readings, class discussion topics, and active learning and reflection assignments to help instructors develop their own sexual violence prevention courses	<i>assault; sexual violence</i>
33	Zounlome, N.O.O. <i>et al.</i> (2019) “No One . . . Saves Black Girls’: Black University Women’s Understanding of Sexual Violence,” <i>The Counseling psychologist</i> , 47(6), pp. 873–908. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1177/0011000019893654	USA	Qualitative	Although research has found that sexual violence is a serious issue on college campuses, the lack of diversity in previous samples calls into question the findings’ generalizability to non-White populations. Consequently, little is known about how Students of Color conceptualize sexual violence. Using an intersectional and phenomenological approach, we examined how Black/African American university women understand sexual violence, as well as their perceptions of cultural barriers to help-seeking and reporting this violence. Seven themes emerged: (a) Historical Legacy of Racialized Trauma Against Black Women, (b) Stereotypes of Hypersexualized Black Women, (c) Silence and Community Protection, (d) Duality of Black Spirituality and/or Religiosity, (e) Racial Injustice and Systemic Barriers to Help-Seeking and Reporting, (f) Stereotypes of Strong Black Women, and (g) Grassroots Healing and Empowerment of Black Communities. We provide recommendations for counselors and university staff to develop culturally grounded campus prevention initiatives for Black women.	<i>sexual violence, Black/African American women, intersectionality, phenomenology</i>

Appendix E – Articles on RFOs, 2017-2022

No.	Reference	Country	Method <i>Qualitative/quantitative N = sample size</i>	Abstract	Keywords
1	<p>O'Connor, P. and Irvine, G. (2020) "Multi-level state interventions and gender equality in higher education institutions: The Irish case," <i>Administrative Sciences</i>, 10(4), p. 98.</p> <p>Available at: https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci10040098</p>	Ireland	Qualitative	<p>Much of the work on gender equality in higher educational institutions (HEIs) has concentrated on the organizational level. The original contribution of this article lies in its focus on state policy developments and interventions. We focus on Ireland as a specific national context, highlighting multi-level state interventions and looking at their impact on HEIs. Using secondary data analysis (including documentary analysis) and focusing particularly on the period since 2014, state initiatives to tackle the problem of gender inequality from various angles are outlined. They include the introduction of Athena SWAN; the ExpFert Group Review; the Gender Equality Taskforce; the Senior Academic Leadership Initiative; research funding agency initiatives and those around sexual harassment. In evaluating their impact, we look at the gender pay gap, the gender profile of the professoriate and senior management as well as other indicators of cultural change in HEIs. The article concludes that the best possibility of leveraging change arises when it is driven at the state (macro); the HEI (meso) and the situational (micro) level simultaneously, by gender competent leaders willing to tackle the historically male dominated, masculinist criteria, procedures, processes and micropolitical practices that are "normalized" in HEIs.</p>	<p><i>state; gender equality; higher educational institutions; interventions; multi-level; gender pay gap; gender parity; Irish; professoriate; Athena SWAN</i></p>

Appendix F – Benchmark survey questions for national authorities

GENDERACTIONplus: BENCHMARKING OF NATIONAL/REGIONAL POLICIES

Scope and objective: This is a benchmarking exercise of **national (and regional as relevant) policies on gender equality in research, higher education and innovation** (NP on GE in RHEI) and focuses on the five thematic areas of GENDERACTIONplus (intersectionality and inclusiveness; gender-based violence; gender dimension in research, innovation and teaching; monitoring and evaluation in the ERA; institutional change through gender equality plans). **The objective is to establish what is in place in each country and what are emerging good practices we can learn from.**

Background: In 2021, gender equality in higher education, research and innovation has been reaffirmed as a priority for the new European Research Area (ERA).¹ By end of June 2022, Member States have indicated their interest in addressing ERA Action 5 (Gender equality and inclusiveness). New policy areas identified include intersectionality and inclusiveness and gender-based violence in academia. Further policy attention is required in the areas of the gender dimension in teaching, research and innovation; monitoring and evaluation of ERA policies and advancing institutional change through Gender Equality Plans, including monitoring and evaluation of the impact of GEPs on gender equality.

This benchmark is to set ground for current policies and developments at the national and regional level as relevant. As such, it will be an important contribution to ERA Policy Action 5 as the project is expected to provide policy input and advice on ERA Policy Action 5.

We kindly request all partners to provide as full answers as possible, including the links to potential policy documents and translations of the relevant text of the policy. Not answering a question or not providing information about policies when they are in place should be a last resort. Thank you!

With this benchmark, information is pursued that is not obtainable in other ways and hence the contribution of the project partners is vital.

Timeframe: 2017 – present time unless specified otherwise; the focus is on policies that are in force now and recent evolution

Who should complete: One answer per country is requested. Project partners (both beneficiaries and Associated Partners) are responsible for coordinating input to the benchmark with other relevant national bodies (as the case may be). Given the cooperation may be required between different national authorities or responsible persons in completing the benchmark survey, the questionnaire can be downloaded and shared as a .doc file. **The deadline for providing your input in the LimeSurvey is 6 November 2022.**

Main definitions

- **Law** is a set of rules that are created and enforceable by social or governmental institutions to regulate behaviour, adopted through a defined legislative process.
- **Policy** is a deliberate system of guidelines to guide decisions and achieve outcomes. It is a statement of intent and is implemented as a procedure or protocol. Policies are generally adopted by a governance body within an organization. For the purpose of this benchmark, policies are defined as adopted by national or regional governments in the form of official regulations, and procedures officially adopted by the governing body in the form of a document.

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Views and opinions expressed here are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

- **Policy measure** is an action taken by the national / regional authority that may be one-off, not embedded in a policy document and agreed.

A [glossary](#) is attached providing definitions of key concepts.

Notes:

- **in the case of requests for document translations to English, if there is/are no official document(s), machine translation(s) is/are sufficient;**
- **otherwise, an official institutional position is sought unless requested explicitly otherwise.**

¹ Communication from the Commission A new ERA for Research and Innovation ([COM/2020/628 final](#)); Council Conclusions on the New European Research Area of 1 December 2020 ([13567/20](#)); Council Conclusions on the future governance of the European Research Area ([14308/21](#)); The Ljubljana Declaration on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation (available [here](#)); [EU Pact for Research and Innovation](#).

There are 158 questions in this survey.

1. Background information

1.1 Partner institution *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- BUNDESMINISTERIUM FUER BILDUNG, WISSENSCHAFT UND FORSCHUNG
- Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science + Independent Research Fund Denmark, DFF
- Departement Economy, Science and Innovation
- Deutsches Zentrum für Luft
- FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGÍA, F.S.P., FECYT
- GOETEBORGS UNIVERSITET
- Higher Education Authority
- Institute for Advanced Studies
- Institute of Sociology of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic
- JOANNEUM RESEARCH FORSCHUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH
- Kunnskapsdepartementet
- Malta Council for Science and Technology (MCST)
- Maynooth University
- MINISTRY OF EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND SPORT (MIZS)
- Ministry of Education, Science and Sport of the Republic of Lithuania
- Ministry of Innovation, Science & Technology (MOST)
- Ministry of Science and Education (MZO)

- Ministry of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation
- National Commission for the Promotion of Equality
- National Documentation Centre
- National Information Processing Institute
- SYDDANSK UNIVERSITET
- Univerzita Mateja Bela
- VETENSKAP & ALLMANHET, VA
- Vilnius University Šiauliai Academy

1.2 Country *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- AT
- BE-Flanders
- BE-FWB
- CZ
- DE
- DK
- EL
- ES
- HR
- IE
- IL
- LT
- MT
- NO
- PL
- SE
- SI
- SK

1.3 Contact person for the benchmarking exercise (the person to be potentially contacted in the event supplementary information is needed).

*

Please write your answer here:

1.4 Email *

Please write your answer here:

1.5 Main responsible national authority responding to the benchmark: *

Please write your answer here:

1.6 Other national authorities contributing to the benchmark completion *

Please write your answer here:

1.7 Method of benchmark completion (please comment on the process of data and information gathering; especially for partners appointed by national authorities, comment on whether the answers reflect your expert assessment or whether they reflect the official position of the national authorities you have been appointed to represent in the project).

*

Please write your answer here:

2. National/regional anti-discrimination and/or equality laws and policies

This section serves to establish the existence of the main national laws and policies on gender equality / anti-discrimination / equal opportunities.

2.1 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a name and link to the main national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity law if relevant (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

For example, in the Czech Republic, this would be the [Antidiscrimination Act](#); this question is NOT asking about the law on higher education.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '8 [B21]' (2.1 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s) and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '8 [B21]' (2.1 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

2.2 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a name and link to the national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

For example, in the Czech Republic, this would be the [Gender Equality Strategy for 2021 – 2030](#); this question is NOT about the higher education policy or research, development and innovation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '11 [B22]' (2.2 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s) and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '11 [B22]' (2.2 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

3. New European Research Area (ERA)

Previous ERA National Action Plans (NAPs) have been particularly successful when based on a broad commitment. This section therefore seeks to establish the process through which the national authorities have determined the actions to sign up for in the new ERA.

3.1 Has the process of identifying the new ERA Actions to sign up for been participatory (e.g., organised events such as round tables or consultations with relevant stakeholders)?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify who has been involved in the process including the departments/units responsible for gender equality/diversity/equal opportunities.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '14 [C31]' (3.1 Has the process of identifying the new ERA Actions to sign up for been participatory (e.g., organised events such as round tables or consultations with relevant stakeholders)?)

Please write your answer here:

3.2 Do the ERA Action 5 topics included in the national response build on existing policy priorities and actions?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, which ones (such as national policy, the previous ERA NAPs): *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '16 [C32]' (3.2 Do the ERA Action 5 topics included in the national response build on existing policy priorities and actions?)

Please write your answer here:

4. Overall assessment of gender equality laws and policies in higher education and research and

This section serves to assess the existence of laws and policies specifically on gender equality in higher education and research and innovation and establish whether it is a priority for the national / regional authorities, who is responsible and what the most recent developments are.

As an example, the Czech Republic does not have a specific law or policy on gender equality in higher education and/or research so will answer “No” to 4.1 and 4.2. There is a [National RDI Policy Czech Republic 2021+](#) which addresses equality and work-life balance and there is [Gender Equality Strategy 2021-2030](#) which has a section dedicated to Knowledge (education and research). Hence, the answer will be “Yes” to 4.2.2 and these two documents would be provided.

4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.1.1 If yes, which bodies/authorities are responsible for implementing the law?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please write your answer here:

4.1.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived law on higher education, law on research and innovation or equality law?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify. Please provide a name and link (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '20 [D412]' (4.1.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived law on higher education, law on research and innovation or equality law?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '20 [D412]' (4.1.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived law on higher education, law on research and innovation or equality law?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.2.1 If yes, which institution/s are responsible for implementing the policy?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please write your answer here:

4.2.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived policy on higher education, policy on research and innovation or their combination or equality policy?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages and if not in English, provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '25 [D422]' (4.2.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived policy on higher education, policy on research and innovation or their combination or equality policy?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document, specify the relevant passages and if not in English, provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '25 [D422]' (4.2.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived policy on higher education, policy on research and innovation or their combination or equality policy?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

4.3 What are the most important policy developments at the national / regional level (as relevant on gender equality in RHEI in the last two years (e.g., adoption of whole new policy, adoption of a policy framework on fighting gender-based violence in higher education, adoption of a GEP requirement for all HEIs in the country etc.)?

*

Please write your answer here:

4.4 What have been the main facilitating factors for these developments?

*

Please write your answer here:

4.5a Please provide a name and link to the new developments at the national / regional level in question 4.3. Please provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Please write your answer here:

4.5b If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s) (please provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation).

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

4.6 What have been the main hindering factors for advancing gender equality policy in RHEI?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Resistance at institutional level
- Lack of economic resources
- Lack of human resources
- Lack of interest
- Not regarded as relevant
- Lack of research-based knowledge and data
- Other:

4.7 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.7.1 If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '33 [D47]' (4.7 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

4.8 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.8.1 If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '35 [D48]' (4.8 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

4.9 Specifically, to what extent has the [Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion](#) had an effect on gender equality in research & innovation in your country?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- To no extent
- To little extent
- To some extent
- To a large extent
- To a very large extent

4.9.1 What concrete effect the GEP requirement has had? *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- New GEPs have been approved in R&I institutions
- Workshops and training have been organised in the R&I field on GEPs at the national level
- An increase in requests/questions received by NCPs as a result of the eligibility criterion
- The EC recommended thematic areas have opened new lines of action in R&I institutions
- New tools and material developed on developing and implementing GEPs in R&I
- Increased national funding for GEP development
- Other:

4.9.2 Additional comment (please provide any other relevant information about the effect of the GEP requirement or discussions surrounding it that will help to better understand and contextualise the information provided in the survey). Please add NA if not applicable.

*

Please write your answer here:

5. Intersectionality

The Commission has stated a wish to broaden gender equality policies in research and innovation to intersections with other potential grounds for discrimination such as ethnicity, disability and sexual orientation. This section of the survey serves to assess to what extent this is addressed in EU Member States and Associated Countries.

5.1 Does the national/regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation address one or more of the following dimensions?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

Please provide a link to this law and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.2 Is this a recent development (last 3-5 years)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.3 If you do not have a national/regional law on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '44 [E53]' (5.3 If you do not have a national/regional law on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document, specify the relevant passages, and if not in English, provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '44 [E53]' (5.3 If you do not have a national/regional law on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality,

diversity and inclusion addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.4 If you have a national/regional policy on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, does this policy also address one or more of the following dimensions?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- None
- Other:

5.5 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy and initiatives, what are the terms most frequently used? Please tick all that apply:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality
- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity

- Inclusiveness/inclusion
- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- Other:

Please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please write your answer here:

Or please please upload the document, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.6 If you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is this a recent development (last 3-5 years)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide examples. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.7.1 Does this policy also address one or more of the following dimensions. Please tick all that apply:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age

- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

5.7.2 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy, what are the terms most frequently used? Please tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?))

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality
- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity
- Inclusiveness/inclusion
- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- None of the above
- Other:

Please provide a link, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?))

Please write your answer here:

Or please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.7.3 Is the inclusion of the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.) a recent development (last 3-5 years)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.8 Has your ministry or any other relevant national/regional authority faced any of the following obstacles in developing a policy including an intersectional approach? Please tick all that apply.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Uncertainty about the terminology to be used
- Lack of a unified understanding of the underlying concepts
- Gender equality as a policy topic is a struggle without other inequality grounds
- Resistance at higher education/research institutions
- Legal regulations restricting data collection (e.g., personal data protection)
- Lack of human resources
- Lack of economic resources
- Lack of interest / not regarded to be relevant
- Lack of disaggregated data on ethnic and other minorities

- Lack of research-based knowledge on gender and diversity in research in your country
- None
- Other:

5.9 Do you have national measures to support the implementation of inclusive/ intersectional policies in research?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.9.1 If yes, please tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '61 [E59]' (5.9 Do you have national measures to support the implementation of inclusive/ intersectional policies in research?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Reporting to national authorities on gender balance indicators
- Reporting to national authorities on indicators on other grounds of inequality (ethnicity, socio-economic status, age, disability etc.)
- National conferences
- Financial incentives (e.g., support to institutions for recruiting women in STEMM)
- Advisory centres for gender equality
- National committees appointed by ministries or other national bodies
- National awareness-raising campaigns
- Other:

5.10 What initiatives and knowledge are needed to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda at your ministry and on the policy agenda in the European Research Area? Please tick all that apply:

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Mutual learning initiatives
- Clear guidelines from the EC
- Advanced legal framework at national level
- Financial incentives and support

- Research commissioned on how to address the intersection of gender equality with other potential grounds of discrimination
- I don't know
- Other:

6. Inclusive research careers

The purpose of Section 6 is to map current and emerging strategies and policies on research careers. Through the information collected and analysed - pinpointing patterns, gaps and solutions, and deepening evidence-based knowledge - we will be able to develop strategic policy recommendations in order to promote more inclusive careers across MS and AC, careers conceived through the intersectional perspective. This converges with the challenge of building the new ERA, in line with the [Council Conclusions Deepening the European Research Area: Providing researchers with attractive and sustainable careers and working conditions and making brain circulation a reality](#), [Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe](#) and the [ERA Policy Agenda](#) (especially at the crossroad of Actions 4 and 5).

6.1 Are there national strategies/policies/policy measures in place, specifically focused on research careers in higher education and research and innovation institutions in your country?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '64 [F61]' (6.1 Are there national strategies/policies/policy measures in place, specifically focused on research careers in higher education and research and innovation institutions in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify (provide a link to the document online, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify (provide a link to the document online, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

Please, identify the strategies/policies/policy instruments, provide links and quote the exact references to the policies in 6.1 and 6. 2. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.3 Is attention to inclusive research careers in national policies or strategies a recent development (less than 3 years) or an established area of work (more than 3 years)? Please specify.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '75 [F63]' (6.3 Is attention to inclusive research careers in national policies or strategies a recent development (less than 3 years) or an established area of work (more than 3 years)? Please specify.)

Please write your answer here:

6.4 What do the inclusive measures of these strategies/policies/policy initiatives focus on? Tick all that apply:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Gender equality

- Gender bias
- Equal access to employment
- Career progression (including recruiting women to professorship and/ or academic leadership)
- Job Precarity
- Gender pay-gap
- Early careers
- Nonlinear careers
- International mobility
- Intersectoral mobility
- Interdisciplinary mobility
- Portability of social security
- Work-life balance
- Working conditions
- Skills and employability
- Professional visibility /recognition
- Research assessment
- Other:

Please add a short text to explain the context and content of all the previously selected measures in 6.4

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

6.4.1 Has Research Assessment been a topic before the launch of the [Reforming Research Assessment Initiative](#) and under action 3 of the European Research Area Policy Agenda?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '77 [F64]' (6.4 What do the inclusive measures of these strategies/policies/policy initiatives focus on? Tick all that apply:)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.4.2 Do any of the criteria for research assessment address gender inequality or other grounds of discrimination (across disciplines, research types, career stages, research roles, peer review, training and mentoring, other...)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '77 [F64]' (6.4 What do the inclusive measures of these strategies/policies/policy initiatives focus on? Tick all that apply:)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '80 [F642]' (6.4.2 Do any of the criteria for research assessment address gender inequality or other grounds of discrimination (across disciplines, research types, career stages, research roles, peer review, training and mentoring, other...)?)

Please write your answer here:

6.5 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy, what are the terms most frequently used in your policies and initiatives on inclusive research careers?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality
- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity
- Inclusiveness/inclusion
- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- None of the above
- Other:

Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation). Please comment/explain especially if multiple terms are used (non-mandatory)

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please write your answer here:

Or upload the document, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.6 Is there any kind of evaluation process on already adopted / implemented policies / initiatives? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, what are the key factors for the success in implementation? Please specify:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '85 [F66]' (6.6 Is there any kind of evaluation process on already adopted / implemented policies / initiatives?)

Please write your answer here:

6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.7.1 If yes, tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [F67]' (6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Illness
- Unemployment
- Work-life Balance
- Maternity and parental leave / support (e.g., length and allowance during the leave, ...) and post maternity /parental leave support while back to work
- Retirement
- Other:

6.7.2 Please explain shortly the differences in coverage in each selected situation: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [F67]' (6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?)

Please write your answer here:

6.7.3 Please identify in which of the above situations ticked in 6.7, gender discrimination, direct or indirect, is more likely to occur and what are the conditions (different conditions in the coverage by social security, work-life balance in Fellowship Holder Statutes versus General Labour Code, etc.).

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [F67]' (6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?)

Please write your answer here:

6.8 Are there other debates ongoing at the national level for more inclusive Social Security coverage?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '91 [F68]' (6.8 Are there other debates ongoing at the national level for more inclusive Social Security coverage?)

Please write your answer here:

6.9 Has your ministry or any other relevant national/regional authority faced any of the following obstacles in developing policies/policy initiatives and actions on gender-inclusive research careers?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Uncertainty about the terminology to be used
- Lack of a unified understanding of the underlying concepts
- Prevalent masculine notions about the research profession (total dedication, extreme focus on performance etc.)
- Not yet on the national agenda
- Still under preliminary debate
- Lack of political /societal awareness
- Lack of Gender Equality Structures
- Budgetary constraints
- Lack of gender disaggregated data
- None of the above
- Other:

6.10 What initiatives are needed to raise the issue of inclusive research careers on the national and European agenda? *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Mutual learning initiatives
- Clear guidelines from the European Commission (EC)
- Advanced legal framework at national level
- Financial incentives and support
- Other:

6.11 Based on your experience, what recommendations could you provide at the national level to promote the design and implementation of gender inclusive research careers?

Please write your answer here:

6.12 Please share case studies or good practices that have helped your country in strengthening inclusive research careers.

Please write your answer here:

7. Gender-Based Violence

Instruction: Please read your country reports from the UniSAFE project available on [the Zenodo community](#) (please use the search box at the top of the page to search for your country's national report) and indicate any new developments since 1 May 2021. Please note that the UniSAFE project covers EU-27 and among the Associated Countries Iceland, UK, Serbia and Turkey.

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) is defined as all forms of gendered violations and abuse, including but not limited to, physical violence, psychological violence, economic and financial violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender harassment, stalking, organisational violence and harassment. GBV can occur in both online and offline contexts, and also includes emerging forms of violence, experienced as violence, violations and abuse not yet necessarily named or recognised as violence.

Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) are defined as any public or private body financing research and innovation.

7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '97 [G71]' (7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '98 [G611]' (If yes, does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not available online please upload the document and highlight the relevant text. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '98 [G611]' (If yes, does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

If it is planned, please name the policy and any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '97 [G71]' (7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '97 [G71]' (7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.)

Please write your answer here:

7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- It is planned
- No, and it is not planned

- I don't know

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not available online, please upload the document and highlight the relevant text. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

If it is planned, please name the policy and any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'It is planned' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No, and it is not planned' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please write your answer here:

7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned

- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not available online, please upload the document and highlight the relevant text. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

If it is planned, please name the policy and any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

8. Gender dimension in research, teaching and innovation

This section focuses specifically on national initiatives – and regional where relevant – to promote the integration of the gender dimension in the content of research and innovation projects (i.e., sex/gender analysis in R&I). Note that these questions are not about gender balance in R&I teams. We encourage you to check our [glossary](#) for clarification of the concepts related to this section.

8.1 What kind of actions have been taken by your national authority at national level to promote the integration of the gender dimension into R&I?

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*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial incentives/support to promote the gender dimension in research and innovation
- Financial incentives/support to promote the gender dimension in teaching content
- A specific funding programme on gender studies is in place
- Requiring applicants to specify whether they are considering sex and/or gender in their research/ innovation proposal
- Inclusion of gender experts in the research teams is encouraged in the R&I calls
- Training on sex/gender analysis for the research team is considered as an eligible cost in national funding schemes
- Established processes to evaluate the integration of the sex/gender analysis into R&I (i.e., as part of the institution's mandate and through well-established guidelines on the evaluation)
- Positive action measures to favour projects that integrate sex and/or gender (go to the glossary for a definition of positive action measures)
- Guidelines on the gender dimension of R&I for applicants
- Guidelines on the gender dimension of R&I for evaluators
- Training on the gender dimension of R&I for applicants
- Training on the gender dimension of R&I for evaluators
- Experts on gender in R&I are included in the evaluation committees
- Communication campaign to make visible the support to sex/gender analysis
- Dissemination materials on the gender dimension in R&I available (videos, academic papers, leaflets...)
- Actions to promote sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula
- None of the above
- Other:

8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

8.2.1 If no, does your national authority plan to make a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes

- No

Please explain the context of the plans: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '115 [H821]' (8.2.1 If no, does your national authority plan to make a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.3 What kind of strategy or policy has your national authority adopted? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- National law
- Specific strategy, policy and/or measure (e.g., gender equality plan)
- Other:

Please provide the name of your national/regional official policy related to the information requested above, link(s) to supporting documents you consider relevant for the analysis and specify the relevant passages (if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages, and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

8.4 What are the main goals of your strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.5 Does your national/regional strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include an intersectional approach?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

8.5.1 If yes, tick off for which inequality grounds: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '121 [H85]' (8.5 Does your national/regional strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include an intersectional approach?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

8.6 Does your national/regional strategy or policy include the innovation and private sectors in the objective of producing non-biased knowledge and solutions for society as a whole?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

8.7 How is the strategy/policy on the gender dimension in R&I implemented? Please provide information on the unit(s) responsible for implementing the policy, the actions taken so far, and the structures developed for its implementation, including technical, human and economic resources.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.8 How is the policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I monitored? Please provide information on the actions and structures, if any, established to supervise the concrete actions developed by this national authority/other agents of the R&I system, the indicators used and their outcomes.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.9 Has the policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I been evaluated? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, what impact/outcome has your policy on the gender dimension in R&I made? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '126 [H89]' (8.9 Has the policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I been evaluated?)

Please write your answer here:

8.10 Please explain the challenges/obstacles, if any, the national authority/ies has/have faced in implementing this policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.11 If relevant, do regional RFOs in your country require the integration of the gender dimension in R&I projects?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable

8.12 Does your national authority have a policy or strategy aimed at promoting sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '130 [H12]' (8.12 Does your national authority have a policy or strategy aimed at promoting sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula?)

Please write your answer here:

Or upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '130 [H12]' (8.12 Does your national authority have a policy or strategy aimed at promoting sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

8.13 What would your national authority need to advance some of the measures mentioned above or others to promote the gender dimension in the R&I content?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial resources
- More awareness on the relevance on sex/gender analysis for R&I
- Exchange experiences on how to consider the gender dimension in R&I from an intersectional perspective
- Capacity-building
- Training materials
- Mandatory policies (e.g., conditional funding)
- I don't know
- Other:

9. GEP monitoring / Evaluating GEP impact

9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

9.2 If yes, is it mandated by:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- The law
- A policy
- Both
- Other

9.3 To which organisations does the GEP requirement apply? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Public HEIs
- Private HEIs
- Public RPOs
- Private RPOs
- Public administration bodies
- Private R&I sector companies with a certain number of employees
- Other:

9.4 Does the GEP requirement include intersections with other discriminatory grounds?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '137 [J94]' (9.4 Does the GEP requirement include intersections with other discriminatory grounds?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Ethnicity,
- Socio-economic background/class
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

9.5 Is the GEP requirement envisioned to contribute to the development of Inclusive Research Careers?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '139 [J95]' (9.5 Is the GEP requirement envisioned to contribute to the development of Inclusive Research Careers?)

Please write your answer here:

9.6 Does the national GEP requirement fulfil the following EU GEP mandatory building blocks?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please tick all that are required:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '141 [J960]' (9.6 Does the national GEP requirement fulfil the following EU GEP mandatory building blocks?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Publication: a formal document published on the institution's website and signed by the top management
- Dedicated resources: commitment of resources and expertise in gender equality to implement the plan
- Data collection and monitoring: sex/gender disaggregated data on personnel (and students, for the establishments concerned) and annual reporting based on indicators
- Training: awareness raising/training on gender equality and unconscious gender biases for staff and decision-makers

Please provide additional information here regarding the mandatory elements:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please write your answer here:

9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please briefly describe the following aspects:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

9.8 Are indicators defined for national/regional GEP monitoring by the responsible authority?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify these indicators:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '146 [J98]' (9.8 Are indicators defined for national/regional GEP monitoring by the responsible authority?)

Please write your answer here:

9.9 Is the monitoring of GEPs part of the national/ regional monitoring system/ policy only, or is it related to ERA monitoring activities? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- ERA policy
- National/ regional policy

- Both
- Other

9.10 Does a publicly available database of GEPs exist at the national/regional level?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide the link:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '149 [J910]' (9.10 Does a publicly available database of GEPs exist at the national/regional level?)

Please write your answer here:

9.11 Does this system measure impact in terms of the defined gender equality priorities (at national or international level)?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

9.12 Which features of GEPs does the system monitor? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- GEP is a publicly available document
- Dedicated resources are allocated for gender equality work
- System for collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data is in place
- Training and capacity building are planned
- Reporting on gender balance in leadership and decision-making
- Monitoring of gender equality in recruitment and promotion processes at the institutional level
- Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
- Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment are in place

- None of the above
- Other:

9.13 What impact on gender equality in your country have the following features of GEPs had (where 1= no impact, 5 = strong impact)?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	1	2	3	4	5
GEP is a publicly available document					
Dedicated resources are allocated for gender equality work					
System for collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data is in place					
Training and capacity building are planned					
Reporting on gender balance in leadership and decision-making					
Monitoring of gender equality in recruitment and promotion processes at the institutional level					
Integration of the gender					

**dimension into
research and
teaching
content**

**Measures
against
gender-based
violence
including
sexual
harassment are
in place**

**Other, please
specify**

9.14 Does a national evaluation system exist for GEP implementation? *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- It is planned
- No, and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please describe its main principles and the periodicity of the GEP implementation evaluation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '154 [J914]' (9.14 Does a national evaluation system exist for GEP implementation?)

Please write your answer here:

10. Relevant stakeholders and organisations

Note: the stakeholder organisations need not focus only on gender equality but could be concerned with other relevant issues (race/ethnicity, LGBTQI+ rights, international mobility, PhD associations, early-career researcher associations, precarity, position of returning researchers after international mobility etc.)

10.1 Which national stakeholders active in the field of research, higher education and/or innovation (NGOs, citizens/students/researchers/other associations) would be suitable for cooperation with GENDERACTIONplus in relation to citizen and stakeholder engagement? Please, provide the requested information below.

10.2 Please add any other comments, ideas or tips on public/citizen engagement:

Please write your answer here:

11. Final remarks

If there are aspects that this survey has not covered and you would like to share them, please add any comments here:

Please write your answer here:

Submit your survey.

Your response has been recorded. Thank you very much for your time!

Appendix G – Benchmark survey questions for RFOs

GENDERACTIONplus: BENCHMARKING OF RFO POLICIES

Scope and objectives: This is a benchmarking exercise of **RFO policies on gender equality in research, higher education and innovation** in the five thematic areas of GENDERACTIONplus (intersectionality and inclusiveness; gender-based violence; gender dimension in research, innovation and teaching; monitoring and evaluation in the ERA; institutional change through gender equality plans). **The objective is to establish what is in place at the RFO level and what are emerging good practices we can learn from.**

Background: In 2021, gender equality in higher education, research and innovation has been reaffirmed as a priority for the new European Research Area (ERA).¹ By end of June 2022, Member States have indicated their interest in addressing ERA Action 5 (Gender equality and inclusiveness). New policy areas identified include intersectionality and inclusiveness and gender-based violence in academia. Further policy attention is required in the areas of the gender dimension in teaching, research and innovation; monitoring and evaluation of ERA policies and advancing institutional change through Gender Equality Plans, including monitoring and evaluation of the impact of GEPs on gender equality.

This benchmark is then to set ground for current policies and developments at the RFO level as relevant; as such, it will be an important contribution to ERA Policy Action 5.

Timeframe: 2017 – present time unless specified otherwise; the focus is on policies that are in force now and recent evolution

Who should complete: One answer per RFO is requested. Project partners (both beneficiaries and Associated Partners) are responsible for coordinating input to the benchmark with other relevant national bodies (if necessary).

The deadline for providing your input in the LimeSurvey is 6 November 2022.

Main definitions

- **Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)** are defined as any public or private body financing research.
- **Law** is a set of rules that are created and enforceable by social or governmental institutions to regulate behaviour, adopted through a defined legislative process.
- **Policy** is a deliberate system of guidelines to guide decisions and achieve policy outcomes. It is a statement of intent and is implemented as a procedure or a protocol. Policies are generally adopted by a governance body within an organization. For the purpose of this benchmark, policies are defined as adopted by national or regional governments in the form of official regulations, procedures officially adopted by the governing body in the form of a document.
- **Policy measure** is intended to mean an action taken by the national / regional authority that may be one-off, not embedded in a policy document.

A [glossary](#) is attached providing definitions of key concepts.

Notes:

- in the case of requests for document translations to English, if there is/are no official document(s), machine translation(s) is/are sufficient;
- otherwise, an official institutional position is sought unless requested explicitly otherwise.

There are 122 questions in this survey.

1. Background information

1.1 Partner institution *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- BULGARIAN NATIONAL SCIENCE FUND
- Czech Science Foundation
- Dutch Research Council
- Estonian Research Council
- Fonds de la Recherche Scientifique
- Forte, Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare
- FUNDACAO PARA A CIENCIA E A TECNOLOGIA
- German Research Foundation (DFG)
- Health Research Board
- Independent Research Fund Denmark, DFF
- Irish Research Council (through beneficiary HEA)
- Kilden at the Research Council of Norway
- Malta Council for Science and Technology, MCST
- Regional Foundation for Biomedical Research
- Research and Innovation Foundation
- Research Council Lithuania
- Science Foundation Ireland
- Technologická agentura České Republiky
- The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey
- Unitatea Executiva pentru Finantarea Invatamantului Superior, a Cercetarii, Dezvoltarii si Inovarii
- Vilnius University Šiauliai Academy
- VINNOVA SWEDISH AGENCY FOR INNOVATION SYSTEMS

1.3 Contact person for the benchmarking exercise *

Please write your answer here:

1.4 Email *

Please write your answer here:

2. Areas of research and innovation supported by the RFO

2.1 Your RFO is supporting: *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- All
- Basic research / blue skies
- Applied research
- Innovation
- Other:

2.2 What areas of research and/or innovation does your organization provide funding for?

*

Please choose **all** that apply:

- All
- Social sciences
- Humanities
- Natural sciences
- Agricultural sciences
- Medical and health sciences
- Engineering and technical sciences
- Interdisciplinary research
- Other:

2.3 What types of organisations are eligible for funding at your RFO? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Public research institutions
- Private research institutions
- Public higher education institutions
- Private higher education institutions
- Small and medium-sized enterprises and start-ups
- Large companies
- Civil society organisations / non-governmental organisations
- Other:

3. Gender equality policies at the RFO level

3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.1.1 Are any actions or measures in place to advance gender equality at your RFO? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.2 When was it adopted? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please write your answer here:

3.3 Is there a responsible unit/person for implementing the policy? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify the position/unit responsible.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '10 [C312]' (3.3 Is there a responsible unit/person for implementing the policy?)

Please write your answer here:

3.4 Is this policy an internal Gender Equality Plan that complies with the Horizon Europe GEP requirement (covering the four building blocks)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.5 What resources are allocated to implement your RFO's gender equality policy (allocated budget, time, personnel)? Please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please write your answer here:

3.6a Please provide a name(s) and link(s) to the policy/ies mentioned in this overview section, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation of the relevant text of the policy (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '8 [C31a]' (3.1.1 Are any actions or measures in place to advance gender equality at your RFO?)

Please write your answer here:

3.6b If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '8 [C31a]' (3.1.1 Are any actions or measures in place to advance gender equality at your RFO?)

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

3.7 What are the most important policy developments on gender equality at your RFO in the last two years? *

Please write your answer here:

3.8 What have been the main facilitating factors for these developments? *

Please write your answer here:

3.9 Does your RFO have a GEP eligibility criterion in place toward host institutions of applicants? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Other

3.9.1 Has this GEP eligibility criterion been introduced in response to the Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [C35]' (3.9 Does your RFO have a GEP eligibility criterion in place toward host institutions of applicants?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.9.2 Is the GEP criterion compulsory to access your calls for proposals or tenders? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [C35]' (3.9 Does your RFO have a GEP eligibility criterion in place toward host institutions of applicants?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.9.3 If not, does having a GEP provide a bonus in the evaluation process? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '18 [C35]' (3.9 Does your RFO have a GEP eligibility criterion in place toward host institutions of applicants?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.9.4 If your RFO does not have a GEP eligibility criterion for applicants, has the Horizon Europe GEP requirement had any other effect at your RFO? (Please provide any other relevant information about the effect of the GEP eligibility criterion or discussions surrounding it that will help to better understand and contextualise the information provided in the survey): *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '18 [C35]' (3.9 Does your RFO have a GEP eligibility criterion in place toward host institutions of applicants?)

Please write your answer here:

3.10 What have been the main hindering factors or barriers for advancing gender equality policy/ policy measures at your RFO, for the internal policies? (e.g., equality among employees, transparency in career progression, measures against discrimination, etc.) *

Please write your answer here:

3.11 Have any policies been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '24 [C37]' (3.11 Have any policies been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

3.12 Have any measures / programmes of support been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify. *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '26 [C38]' (3.12 Have any measures / programmes of support been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

3.13 Have any internal policies been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify. For example, this can be due to a reorientation of policy toward mainstreaming gender or framing issues as SDGs.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '28 [C39]' (3.13 Have any internal policies been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

3.14 Have any measures / programmes addressing beneficiaries been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '30 [C310]' (3.14 Have any measures / programmes addressing beneficiaries been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

3.15 What have been the main hindering factors for advancing gender equality policy/ policy measures at your RFO, for the beneficiaries of the grants? (regarding both gender equality in research and innovation teams and the gender dimension in the content of the research and innovation project) *

Please write your answer here:

3.16 Have any policies been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '33 [C3120]' (3.16 Have any policies been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

3.17 Have any measures / programmes of support been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '35 [C3130]' (3.17 Have any measures / programmes of support been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

3.18 Have any internal policies been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify. For example, this can be due to the need to exclude potential beneficiaries that do not comply with GE requirements.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '37 [C3140]' (3.18 Have any internal policies been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

3.19 Have any measures/programmes been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '39 [C315]' (3.19 Have any measures/programmes been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

4. Intersectionality and inclusiveness

Intersectionality

The Commission has stated a wish to broaden gender equality policies in research and innovation to intersections with other potential grounds for discrimination such as ethnicity, disability and sexual orientation. This section of the survey serves to assess to what extent this is addressed in RFOs.

4.1 Does your RFO's gender equality policy also include one or more of the following dimensions? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- None
- Other:

4.2 Please specify the relevant passages of the document and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please write your answer here:

4.3 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy, what are the terms most frequently used? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- non-discrimination
- multiple discrimination (additive)
- intersectionality
- representation
- gender+ equality
- diversity
- inclusiveness/inclusion
- inclusive equality
- equity/equality
- Other:

4.4 Is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived policies or strategies at the level of your RFO (e.g., strategic plans, mission statement etc.)? Please provide examples: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '44 [D45]' (4.4 Is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived policies or strategies at the level of your RFO (e.g., strategic plans, mission statement etc.)? Please provide examples:)

Please write your answer here:

4.5 Has your RFO faced any of the following obstacles in developing a policy including an intersectional approach? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Lack of national policy in this field
- Uncertainty about the terminology to be used
- Lack of a unified understanding of the underlying concepts
- Gender equality as a policy topic is a struggle without other inequality grounds
- Resistance at management level at your institution
- Lack of human resources
- Lack of economic resources
- Lack of interest / not regarded to be relevant
- Lack of disaggregated data on ethnic and other minorities
- Lack of research-based knowledge on gender and diversity in research in your country
- None
- Other:

4.6 What initiatives and knowledge are needed to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the agenda in your RFO?

Please write your answer here:

5. Inclusive research careers

The purpose of section 5 is mapping current and emerging strategies and policies on research careers. Through the information collected and analysed - pinpointing patterns, gaps and solutions, and deepening evidence-based knowledge - we will be able to develop strategic policy recommendations in order to promote more inclusive careers across MS, the main target of this part of the survey, approaching them from an intersectional perspective. This converges to the crucial challenge that is

building the new ERA, a vision in line with the directions substantiated in the [Council Conclusions Deepening the European Research Area: Providing researchers with attractive and sustainable careers and working conditions and making brain circulation a reality](#), in the [Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe](#) and the [ERA Policy Agenda](#) (namely at the crossroad of actions 4 and 5).

Recognizing the growing role of RFOs in promoting gender-inclusive culture, this survey further aims at mapping particular framing conditions set by your institution with a diversified impact on the large spectrum of research careers.

5.1 Is your RFO involved in the discussions (as participating in expert groups, advisory bodies, other) on the research careers agenda? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, what is your role or contribution to the discussions on the research careers agenda? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '48 [E51]' (5.1 Is your RFO involved in the discussions (as participating in expert groups, advisory bodies, other) on the research careers agenda?)

Please write your answer here:

If not, why? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '48 [E51]' (5.1 Is your RFO involved in the discussions (as participating in expert groups, advisory bodies, other) on the research careers agenda?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- There is no discussion about inclusive research careers at all
- There is a discussion, but the national authority and the RFO are not articulated or not moving forward simultaneously
- Other:

5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.3 Has your RFO faced any of the following obstacles in developing strategies/ policies/ policy measures on gender inclusive careers? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Uncertainty about the terminology to be used
- Lack of a unified understanding of the underlying concepts
- Prevalent masculine notions about the research profession (total dedication, extreme focus on performance etc.)
- Not yet on the national agenda
- Still under preliminary debate
- Lack of political /societal awareness
- Lack of Gender Equality structures
- Budgetary constraints
- Lack of gender disaggregated data
- Other:

5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.5 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures identify any inequality grounds/diversity other than gender? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please check all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '54 [E523]' (5.5 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures identify any inequality grounds/diversity other than gender?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Religion
- Disability

- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Age
- Socio-economic background/class
- Political orientation
- Origin country
- Power relations
- Other:

5.6 Do these strategies/ policies/ policy measures have an intersectional perspective? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please indicate shortly the existing intersections. *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '56 [E524]' (5.6 Do these strategies/ policies/ policy measures have an intersectional perspective?)

Please write your answer here:

5.7a If available, provide a link to the document(s) online, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please write your answer here:

5.7b If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.8 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality, what are the terms most frequently used in your policies and initiatives on inclusive research careers? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '54 [E523]' (5.5 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures identify any inequality grounds/diversity other than gender?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality
- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity
- Inclusiveness/inclusion
- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- None of the above
- Other:

5.8.1 Please comment/explain especially if multiple terms are used: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '54 [E523]' (5.5 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures identify any inequality grounds/diversity other than gender?)

Please write your answer here:

5.8.2 Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation). *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please write your answer here:

5.9 Within the above identified strategies/policies /policy measures, what gender sensitive actions/initiatives were designed? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Access to Employment: diversity and equality of opportunities in recruitment and selection processes
- Performance evaluation and career progression
- Gender balanced peer review panels/panel's chair
- Gender balance in funding schemes, by setting up gender related topics
- Gender balance in funding schemes, by setting up target groups
- Incentives to mobility, namely international, and to returns
- Return grants for parents after a career break
- Gender bias awareness through training / reflection / skills development for peer review panels and panel chairs
- Rewards 'Women in research', in particular in the under-represented areas
- Other:

Please tick all that apply.

5.9.1 What groups are targeted by the funding schemes? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '63 [E54]' (5.9 Within the above identified strategies/policies /policy measures, what gender sensitive actions/initiatives were designed?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- PhD
- Postdocs
- Early-career researchers
- Mid-career excellence,
- Senior excellence
- Other

Please, specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '64 [E541]' (5.9.1 What groups are targeted by the funding schemes?)

Please write your answer here:

5.9.2 Please specify the relevant passages in the above-mentioned document(s) and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation). *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please write your answer here:

5.10 Is attention to inclusive research careers policies or strategies a recent development (less than 3 years) or an established area of work in your institution (more than 3 years)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Recent development
- Established area of work

Please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please write your answer here:

5.11 Are these policies/policy instruments/programmes of support already implemented? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.11.1 Is monitoring of these instruments in place, through any kind of evaluation process? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '69 [E56]' (5.11 Are these policies/policy instruments/programmes of support already implemented?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.11.2 What are the key factors for the success in implementation? Please share case studies or good practices that have helped your RFO in strengthening inclusive research careers.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at

question '69 [E56]' (5.11 Are these policies/policy instruments/programmes of support already implemented?)

Please write your answer here:

5.13 In the context of the social security system coverage, has your organisation implemented more favourable regulations or practices than the ones generally available/applied in the legal system (Labour Code)? Types of researcher positions - permanent or temporary – and PhD students with fellowships are to be considered. *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.13.1 If yes, please explain how, having in mind the following situations (illness, unemployment, work-life balance, maternity and parental leave / support - e.g., length and allowance during the leave, retirement, other - please describe).*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '72 [E57]' (5.13 In the context of the social security system coverage, has your organisation implemented more favourable regulations or practices than the ones generally available/applied in the legal system (Labour Code)? Types of researcher positions - permanent or temporary – and PhD students with fellowships are to be considered.)

Please write your answer here:

5.13.2 From your organisation's point of view, in which of the above situations does discrimination on gender mostly persist and how? (e.g., returning to work after a maternity /parental leave) *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '72 [E57]' (5.13 In the context of the social security system coverage, has your organisation implemented more favourable regulations or practices than the ones generally available/applied in the legal system (Labour Code)? Types of researcher positions - permanent or temporary – and PhD students with fellowships are to be considered.)

Please write your answer here:

5.14 Based on your experience, what recommendations could you provide to promote and improve the design and implementation of inclusive research careers?

Please write your answer here:

6. Gender-based violence

Instruction: Please read your country reports from the UniSAFE project available on the [Zenodo community](#) (please use the search box at the top of the page to search for your country's national report) and indicate any new developments at the level of your RFO since 2021 (please note that the UniSAFE project covers EU-27 and among the Associated Countries Iceland, UK, Serbia and Turkey).

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) is defined as all forms of gendered violations and abuse, including but not limited to, physical violence, psychological violence, economic and financial violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender harassment, stalking, organisational violence and harassment. GBV can occur in both online and offline contexts, and also includes emerging forms of violence, experienced as violence, violations and abuse not yet necessarily named or recognised as violence.

6.1 Does your RFO have a new or revised policy to address GBV in relation to the applicants, adopted since 1st of May 2021? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.2a If available, provide a link to the document(s) online, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '76 [F61]' (6.1 Does your RFO have a new or revised policy to address GBV in relation to the applicants, adopted since 1st of May 2021?)

Please write your answer here:

6.2b If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '76 [F61]' (6.1 Does your RFO have a new or revised policy to address GBV in relation to the applicants, adopted since 1st of May 2021?)

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.3 Does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '76 [F61]' (6.1 Does your RFO have a new or revised policy to address GBV in relation to the applicants, adopted since 1st of May 2021?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, tick off for which inequality grounds:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '79 [F612]' (6.3 Does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

Please add any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned ' at question '79 [F612]' (6.3 Does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned ' at question '79 [F612]' (6.3 Does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please write your answer here:

6.4 Has your RFO implemented any measures against GBV for the applicants in their funding schemes conditions since 1 May 2021? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '83 [E62]' (6.4 Has your RFO implemented any measures against GBV for the applicants in their funding schemes conditions since 1 May 2021?)

If it is planned, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '83 [E62]' (6.4 Has your RFO implemented any measures against GBV for the applicants in their funding schemes conditions since 1 May 2021?)

If no, please provide an explanation for why not:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '83 [E62]' (6.4 Has your RFO implemented any measures against GBV for the applicants in their funding schemes conditions since 1 May 2021?)

Please write your answer here:

6.5 Has your RFO introduced GBV as a priority topic in a funding scheme/programme to support research on GBV in universities and research organisations since 1 May 2021? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [E63]' (6.5 Has your RFO introduced GBV as a priority topic in a funding scheme/programme to support research on GBV in universities and research organisations since 1 May 2021?)

If it is planned, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '87 [E63]' (6.5 Has your RFO introduced GBV as a priority topic in a funding scheme/programme to support research on GBV in universities and research organisations since 1 May 2021?)

If no, please provide an explanation for why not:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '87 [E63]' (6.5 Has your RFO introduced GBV as a priority topic in a funding scheme/programme to support research on GBV in universities and research organisations since 1 May 2021?)

Please write your answer here:

6.6 Has your RFO put in place any actions or measures regarding GBV for the safety of researchers participating in projects funded since 1 May 2021? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '91 [E64]' (6.6 Has your RFO put in place any actions or measures regarding GBV for the safety of researchers participating in projects funded since 1 May 2021?)

If it is planned, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '91 [E64]' (6.6 Has your RFO put in place any actions or measures regarding GBV for the safety of researchers participating in projects funded since 1 May 2021?)

If no, please provide an explanation for not why

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '91 [E64]' (6.6 Has your RFO put in place any actions or measures regarding GBV for the safety of researchers participating in projects funded since 1 May 2021?)

Please write your answer here:

6.7 Does your RFO have systems/procedures for getting info from RPOs on misconduct in terms of GBV perpetrated by Principal Investigators and/or researchers applying for funding? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '95 [E65]' (6.7 Does your RFO have systems/procedures for getting info from RPOs on misconduct in terms of GBV perpetrated by Principal Investigators and/or researchers applying for funding?)

Please write your answer here:

If it is planned, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '95 [E65]' (6.7 Does your RFO have systems/procedures for getting info from RPOs on misconduct in terms of GBV perpetrated by Principal Investigators and/or researchers applying for funding?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '95 [E65]' (6.7 Does your RFO have systems/procedures for getting info from RPOs on misconduct in terms of GBV perpetrated by Principal Investigators and/or researchers applying for funding?)

Please write your answer here:

6.8 Are there any established procedures in your RFO for sanctioning perpetrators, when informed on misconduct in terms of GBV by an RPO? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '99 [F66]' (6.8 Are there any established procedures in your RFO for sanctioning perpetrators, when informed on misconduct in terms of GBV by an RPO?)

Please write your answer here:

If it is planned, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '99 [F66]' (6.8 Are there any established procedures in your RFO for sanctioning perpetrators, when informed on misconduct in terms of GBV by an RPO?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '99 [F66]' (6.8 Are there any established procedures in your RFO for sanctioning perpetrators, when informed on misconduct in terms of GBV by an RPO?)

Please write your answer here:

6.9 Do you know of any current ideas or suggestions proposed among the other RFOs in your country, targeting preventing GBV in research in the future through specific actions or measures? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '103 [F67]' (6.9 Do you know of any current ideas or suggestions proposed among the other RFOs in your country, targeting preventing GBV in research in the future through specific actions or measures?)

7. Gender dimension in research and innovation

This section focuses specifically on RFOs initiatives to promote the integration of the gender dimension in the content of research and innovation projects (i.e., sex/gender analysis in R&I). **Note that these questions are not about gender balance in R&I teams.** We encourage you to check our glossary for clarification of the concepts related to this section link to the [glossary](#).

7.1 What kind of actions has your RFO taken to promote the integration of the gender dimension into R&I? Please tick all that apply: *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial incentives/support to promote the gender dimension in research and innovation
- A specific funding programme on gender studies is in place
- Requiring applicants to specify whether they are considering sex and/or gender in their research/ innovation proposal
- Inclusion of gender experts in the research and innovation teams is encouraged in the R&I calls
- Training on sex/gender analysis for the research and innovation team is considered as an eligible cost in the RFO funding schemes
- Established processes to evaluate the integration of the sex/gender analysis into R&I (i.e., as part of the institution's mandate and through well-established guidelines on the evaluation)
- Positive action measures to favour projects that integrate sex and/or gender (go to the glossary for a definition of positive action measures)
- Guidelines on the gender dimension of R&I for applicants
- Guidelines on the gender dimension of R&I for evaluators
- Training on the gender dimension of R&I for applicants
- Training on the gender dimension of R&I for evaluators
- Experts on gender in R&I are included in the evaluation committees
- Communication campaign to make visible the support to sex/gender analysis
- Dissemination materials on the gender dimension in R&I available (videos, academic papers, leaflets...)
- Other:

7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

7.3a If available, provide a link to the RFO official policy related to the information requested above and other supporting documents you consider relevant for the analysis. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.3b If not publicly available online, please upload the RFO official policy related to the information requested above and other supporting documents you consider relevant for the analysis. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

7.4 What kind of strategy or policy has your RFO adopted? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- National law
- Specific strategy / policy / measure (e.g. gender equality plan)
- Other:

7.5 What are the main goals of your strategy or policy? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.6 Does your strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include an intersectional approach? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes

- No

If yes, tick off for which inequality grounds: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '111 [G75]' (7.6 Does your strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include an intersectional approach?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

7.7 Does your strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include the innovation and private sectors in the objective of producing non-biased knowledge and solutions for society? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

7.8 How is the strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I implemented? Please provide information on the unit(s) responsible for implementing the policy, the actions taken so far, and the structures developed for its implementation, including technical, human and economic resources. *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.9 How is the strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I monitored? Please provide information on the actions and structures, if any, established to supervise the concrete actions developed by the RFO/other agents of the R&I system, the indicators used and their outcomes. *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.10 Has the strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I been evaluated? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

What impact or outcome has your policy on the gender dimension in R&I made? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '116 [G79]' (7.10 Has the strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I been evaluated?)

Please write your answer here:

7.11 Please explain the challenges/obstacles, if any, that your RFO has faced in implementing this policy or strategy on the gender dimension in R&I: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.12 If no, does your RFO plan to make a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please explain the context of the plans: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '119 [G721]' (7.12 If no, does your RFO plan to make a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.13 What would your RFO need to advance some of the measures mentioned above or others to promote sex and gender analyses and integration of the gender dimension in the R&I content? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial resources
- More awareness on the relevance on sex/gender analysis for R&I
- Exchange experiences on how to consider the gender dimension in R&I from an intersectional perspective
- Capacity-building
- Training materials
- Mandatory policies (e.g., conditional funding)
- Other:

Please tick all that apply.

8. Relevant stakeholders and organisations

The stakeholder organisations need not focus only on gender equality but could be concerned with other relevant issues (incubators, innovation offices, knowledge transfer centres as well as race/ethnicity, LGBTQI+ rights, international mobility, PhD associations, early-career researcher associations, precarity, position of returning researchers after international mobility etc.).

8.1 Are there stakeholders for your RFO in the areas of gender equality, diversity, inclusiveness that may be relevant for citizen/stakeholder engagement in the GENDERACTIONplus project?

Submit your survey.

Your response has been recorded. Thank you very much for your time!

